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A Comparative Case study:

**The Key and Potential Roles of Social
Media in Festival Avignon OFF and
Edinburgh Festival Fringe**

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ABSTRACT

Due to the lack of social media study in event and festival industry, the unprecedented, high social media popularity of Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe and the alert of the shortage of audiences which supports the future growth of the festivals, this thesis aims (1) to give the global panorama of social media performances in two of the most representative art festivals, Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe, in 2019 and (2) to give constructive recommendations of further nourishing the participants' experiences via digital approach.

To make this thesis rigorous, multiple case study with embedded mixed method is selected as the research strategy to analyze and compare the two festivals individually and mutually. In the end, more than 12,500 social media data from Awario, Metricool and Social Blade, around 900 offline flyers and 26 semi-structured interviews have been collected and analyzed.

The key findings include: (1) Lack of “Stimulation” and “Program” in social media contents, (2) Fringe’s more diverse and international online audiences, (3) A leading role of traditional communication in both festivals, (4) Lack of differentiation of the flyers, (5) Ignorance of Instagram and Youtube in social media, (6) Absence of social media in Avignon Off, (7) Higher acceptance of “phygital” performances in Fringe and (8) Difficulty of having an immersive festival experience in the current edition.

The three recommendations for improving social media in Fringe and OFF include: (1) A centralized digital assistant, FES-visor, which facilitates visitors' whole journey, (2) Events and social media campaigns for higher satisfaction and media coverage and (3) Customer-oriented contents which actively respond to the customers.

Keywords: Social media, Marketing studies, Event and festival, Festival Avignon Off, Edinburgh Festival Fringe

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Chapter 1. Introduction

1.1. Background to the Topic

Europe is a paradise for events, especially for various types of art festivals. Full of emotions, joyfulness, happy moments are shared with families and friends. Arts and culture are soft but powerful mediums to improve people's life. Two of the most representative performing art festivals refer to Edinburgh Festival Fringe and Festival Avignon Off. With the ambition of reviving and encouraging the people after the World Wars, Festival Avignon and Edinburgh International Festival have allowed the top theater companies, comedians and directors worldwide who have passed the high-end selection process to showcase their performances to the public. As a result of the high entry barrier to both festivals and the wave of art's democratization at that time as a counterpart to so-called "high arts", Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe were created and became annual celebrations for the diversity of performing arts. In 2019, Avignon Off and Edinburgh Fringe have succeeded to hold more than thousands of shows and have welcomed a huge number of public, artists and professionals. This year Avignon Off hosted 1,592 shows in 139 different places. It's worth to mentioning that 1,134 shows were presented for the first time in Avignon, which indicates the festival's indispensable status in performing arts. The festival also gathered 2,640 performing arts professionals, 1,219 programmers, 259 institutions, 124 broadcasters and 605 journalists.

Although it's definitely a good sign that the scale of both festivals keeps increasing, the high performing costs and insufficient spectators become two of the most urgent and contemporary challenges to which the two festivals have to respond. Pierre Beffeyte, President of Festival Avignon Off, appreciated a lot on the increasing diversity of the performances, but at the same time, he revealed his worries about the rapid growth of the festival scale with the relatively shortage of spectators. During an interview, the president confirmed that "There is an urgent need to find new audiences and act in concert with

public authorities and theater directors” (Mebarek, 2019). What’s more, according to Marianne magazine, a shorter show duration, decreased decor and less actors depicted what the performing teams in Festival Avignon Off faced nowadays. 80% of the Avignon’s theaters were rented with the price from 12,000 to 22,000 euros for three weeks so most of the companies were just losing money if failing to make the future deals with the potential programmers and professionals (Egmond, 2019). Similarly, in Edinburgh, even if Edinburgh Festival Fringe in 2019 gained more ticket sales and welcomed more international performers, the unaffordable high rents may bring about the unsustainability and elitist of the festival in the recent future. In fact, the comedian, Barry Ferns, expressed his financial deficits around £35,000 due to his participation in 2018’s Fringe (Bakare, 2019). Despite having to take on the financial risk for showcasing their talents, the performers are still willing to participate in Edinburgh Fringe for the intention of developing their international careers, of listening to the direct feedback from the global spectators and of doing the networking with the culture industry professionals. While performing at the same time with more than thousands of teams during the three intensive weeks, how could performances be particularly outstanding and impressive and have a high attendance level as well? How could production teams promote their shows better to the potential audiences? For festival organizers, how could Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe find out the strategy which could welcome more audiences to catch up to the growth of the festivals and maintain the art diversity, which is the first mission for the two festivals?

Social media, still quite a new area for both Edinburgh Festival Fringe and Festival Avignon Off, might attract more young audiences, make their experiences more immersive and finally thrive the festivals even more. With the higher and higher internet accessibility and mobile penetration rate, social media is an extremely supportive friend in people’s daily lives. It’s a partner, a publication reader, an interactive communication tool, a patient buddy, a showcase of friends’ lives, a portable television, a news channel and an entertaining device etc. Especially the young users in the so-called Generation Y or Z, tend to use at least a couple of hours per day on social media to digest the new

information, to read the articles, to watch the videos or to chat with their friends. Although both Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe have started their social media policy and have actively promoted their social media in the recent years, the social media role in the two festivals has not been obvious and significant until the end of 2018. To illustrate, the author finds out that since 2006 until present, both Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe have regularly reached their peaks of popularity of search interest in web during the festivals (Figure 1.1.a.), but have not succeeded to have the equivalent peaks of popularity in social media until 2018 (Figure 1.1.b.). Surprisingly, both festivals this year have reached the significant mentions in social media. Does it imply that Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe have a huge progress in terms of the social media uses this year? What are the current and potential roles of social media in both festivals?

Figure 1.1.a. Google Trends: Interest over time – Web Search (2006-2019)

Figure 1.1.b. Awario: Share of Voice – Social Media Mentions (2006-2019)

So far, however, there has been little discussion about the social media research in the event and festival studies. This thesis aims (1) to capture the current panorama of the uses of social media in the 2019's edition of Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival

Fringe and (2) to give some constructive recommendations about how to use social media to further nourish the participants' experiences.

1.2. Scope and Delimitations

This research focuses on the investigation of actual and potential social media roles in Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe in 2019 particularly. The comparative research intends to the representation of the social media contemporary roles in the context of art festivals.

The assessment, analysis of social media, and offline communication were carried out. In detail, the social media analysis of Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe in 2019 will respond to the following aspects: (1) types of contents, (2) content efficiency, (3) influencers and opinions leaders and (4) locations. Next, the interviews with regard to the stakeholders' perceptions towards the social media in the festivals have been conducted in Avignon, France and Edinburgh, UK. In the end, the content analysis of offline communication, referring to flyers in the both festivals, has been completed based on the flyers collected likewise in these two destination cities.

This research concentrates on the four social media platforms, inclusive of Twitter and Facebook (Social networking), Instagram (Visual sharing) and Youtube (Video sharing), to investigate in the diverse and dynamic roles of social media from 30 days before the festivals until 5 days after the festivals.

1.3. Literature Review

Social media has various roles from the beginning to the end of the festivals. Social media breaks the traditional geographical barriers and empowers the people to do exchanges with others in the digital space. With regard to the definition, social media links with “the sharing of information, experiences, and perspectives throughout community-oriented websites” (Weinberg 2009, p.1). The similar center of interests, the homogeneous loyalty to the brands, the close life attitudes or lifestyles furthermore filter and assemble the people who share the same interests into groups, which is the concept of community. Compared to the role as a passive receiver in traditional media, social media users have the active role to decide what kind of contents they want to spread and with whom they want to share. Safko and Brake (2009, p.6) pointed out that social media referred to “activities, practices, and behaviors among communities of people who gather online to share information, knowledge, and opinions using conversational media”. With the conversational base, the social media is expected to facilitate the conversations and strengthen the connections in the community without any physical barrier. After 10-year transformation, social media has consolidated its role as a crucial vehicle of stimulating the information flows in more and more fields, even in entertainment (Shen, Hock Chuan, & Cheng, 2016). The notoriety of social media has been enhancing the grassroots right of discourse in the cyber environment, and the new types of figures, influencers and opinion leaders, who earn lots of credibility from their followers, are born and furthermore influence their fans by their updates, sharing and experiences.

In the contexts of events and festivals, because the main products are intangible and based on the personal experiences, the significance of utilizing social media to maintain the positive relationship among the stakeholders, inclusive of event organizers, the participants, the virtual audiences, the artists and the professionals is highlighted. Marketing communications provide the event organizers the pathway to enrich the participants’ experiences with the major intention “to inform, persuade, and remind consumers – directly or indirectly, about the products and brands they sell” (Kotler &

Keller, 2012). The active conversations and exchanges between the event organizers and the participants centering on the festivals conduce to the more intimate connections and the higher possibility to attract more potential audiences to actually participate in the festivals. For the purpose of highlighting the five key roles of social media in the event and festival studies, the marketing communication was used as the theoretical fundamental for four of the key roles, including (1) Advertising, (2) Marketing & Promotion, (3) Community Management & Word of Mouth. Then, because of the seasonal nature of annual festival, the short-term information for customers is highly essential to let the participants engaged. Thus, (4) Customer-oriented Information was determined to be the fourth key role of social media. In addition, due to the “blended” relationship between social media marketing and performance and the diverse roles of social media stated by Sam Miles (2017), the fifth key role of social media, (5) Art Creations, was determined to explore the potential of integrating social media into the live performances before, during or after the live shows for extending and enriching the audiences’ experiences.

1.3.1. Advertising

While making the shows with more than thousands of competitors around, doing the advertising efficiently is a way to make the shows “visible”, stimulate the interests, differentiate them with the others and create the competitive advantages for the potential audiences compared to other occupations. Advertising refers to any paid document for promoting the ideas, products or services with the forms of “print media, broadcast media, network media, electronic media, and display media” (Kotler & Keller, 2012). Although flyers are considered to be traditional and conventional, they still play an important role in the event industry nowadays. For example, printing has the second most likely position to receive a higher budget according to Event Industry Pulse Report 2019. Indeed, the most common communication vehicles in a festival like Festival Avignon Off or Edinburgh Festival Fringe are posters and flyers. To achieve the goals of gaining more spotlight and revenues for the live shows, the bottom-lines for an efficient flyer include: (1) clear texts, (2) key information — such as names, dates, time, locations, ticket prices,

call to actions, hashtags, websites etc., (3) visual hierarchy, (4) QR code and (5) color collocation (Eventbrite UK, 2019).

1.3.2. Marketing & Promotion

Social media eliminates the geographical limitations and enlarges potential audiences for the festivals. Thus, the festival organizers could utilize the traditional or online marketing and promotional tactics to attract potentially huger festival community and audiences to come for the shows or take any action. Weinberg (2009, p.3) pointed out the fact that social media marketing allows the enterprises to do the online promotion and communication with a more enormous community which might not be reachable with the conventional advertising methods merely.

For the purpose of obtaining a more significant size of participants, promotion globally represents all the communications which intend to notify or seduce the target audiences about products or services. As claimed by Kolter & Keller (2012), sales promotion composes of “consumer promotions (such as samples and coupons...), trade promotions and business and sales promotions”. Besides, there are other purposes for promotion such as rising awareness, generating public interests, enhancing sales and building up brand loyalty.

1.3.3. Community Management & Word of Mouth marketing

Community management is the process of monitoring the community, dealing with any positive or negative feedback in the short-term, including the customer insights in the company upcoming strategies. For brands, brand community on the social media could contribute to do the social listening and capture the customer insights not only to improve the whole current festival experiences from the beginning to the end; for customers, brand community allows them to do the exchanges in terms of experiences, information and relevant topics with the others who share the similar tastes, value systems or interests on some specific topics. The expected results of community management are to intensify

the positive and harmonious connection and relationship between the brands and the customers and further enhance the brand loyalty.

Word of mouth, referring to “people-to-people oral, written or electronic communications that relate to the merits or experiences of purchasing or using products or services” (Kolter & Keller, 2012), which is a personal, intimate but powerful medium to enhance the sense of belonging to the brand community, building up the conversations around the products, the services or the pertinent lifestyles among the actual and potential participants, friends or family members etc. Word of mouth is so important that 15,000 respondents confirmed that it’s the most crucial media (McConnell and Huba, 2006, p.26). Nowadays, social media leverages the impact of word of mouth from the private talks within a few people to the hustling conversations with hundreds of, thousands of virtual contacts on social media. Different from the classical, old-fashioned word of mouth, “thousands or sometimes even millions that are either participating or listening in (Meerman Scott, 2010, p.xvii). That is, the word of mouth has increased its impacts with the arrival of “phygital” era.

1.3.4. Customer-oriented Information

In a festival, the social media contents might enrich participants’ experiences. Well-balanced social media contents are expected to augment the festival attractiveness and deepen the relationship between the festivals and the participants. According to many marketing experts in leisure and entertainment industries, the purpose of customer-oriented information is to give sufficient, well-thought-out contents to make the customers more engaged during the entertainment and leisure activities. The five major types of Customer-oriented Information are as follows: (1) Program, (2) Information, (3) Customer Relations, (4) Emotion and (5) Stimulation.

1.3.5. Art Creations

Social media could not only play a communication and promotional role in festivals but also has the potential to welcome participants to engage in the process of the co-creation phase of performances.

As Sam Miles (2017) argued,

The relationship between social media marketing and performance is more hybridized than often assumed, with performances forming a creative development loop from producer to audience through performative social media. Harnessing the creative potential of social media platforms via “digital staging” encourages audience insight into process as well as product (Miles 2017, p.1).

That is, social media could highlight the role of participants and help them be engaged in the collective experiences.

Chapter 2. Research

2.1. Research Aim and Objective

The aim of this thesis is to enrich the most recent social media research in the contexts of event and festival studies, by taking two of the most representative performing art festivals, as examples, Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe in 2019. Because of the absence of existing academic research on the social media current roles and future potentials in art festivals, this thesis intends to clarify on this global social media landscape of the two festivals chiefly focusing on the social media analysis and the content analysis on the four major social media platforms, inclusive of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Youtube, from 30 days before the festival until 5 days after the festival in 2019.

The contribution of this research is to allow the festival organizers and the researchers in relevant fields to view the landscape of the roles and uses of social media in Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe in 2019 and to further develop their social media strategies in the recent future.

2.2. Research Strategy: multiple-case study

This is as an exploratory research with a bottom-up approach to capture the social media panorama in 2019's Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe and point out the future potentials. The research strategy of the comparative (multiple-case) study was adopted because the results nurtured by both quantitative and qualitative data might provide not only the objective facts to the readers but also sufficient elements to support them to better understand the whole scenarios, results and context from the qualitative side. In general, case study method was defined as “an empirical inquiry that investigates

a contemporary phenomenon within its real-life context; when the boundaries between phenomenon and context are not clearly evident; and in which multiple sources of evidence are used” (Yin, 2003, p.13). Yet, some scholars argued that it’s hard to use a single case study to be directly used to make a generalized and universal conclusion. That is, multiple-case study with a hybrid approach is globally more vigorous compared a single case study (Herriott & Firestone, 1983).

2.3. Research Questions

- What are the results of the organizer-generated social media contents in 2019?
- What are the results of the public-generated social media contents?
- How compatible are the flyers’ contents with the social media?
- What are the current roles and future potentials of social media?
- What are the social media comparisons between Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe?
- How could the two festivals strengthen their social media policy in the future?

2.4. Research Propositions

The main purpose of this research is to analyze and compare the current and potential roles of social media in Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe, and that the criteria will be used for judging the achievement of the thesis are as follows:

- whether it identifies the most efficient contents generated by the event organizers;
- whether it identifies the most efficient contents generated by the public;
- whether it provides a global panorama of the social media uses in both festivals;
- whether it points out the potential social media roles in the future;
- whether it provides the social media comparisons of the two festivals;

- whether it provides the pragmatic recommendations related to social media in art festivals.

2.5. Units of Analysis

In the event and festival industry, Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe are two of the most representative performing art festivals in Europe. Yet, the social media roles and their potentials could not be found in the recent event and festival studies. The absence points out the necessity to conduct this research to start to enrich this field. As Robert Yin claimed, the units of analysis can be event or entity as well (Yin, 2003). Therefore, the two primary units of analysis in this comparative study are Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe. The findings of this research might attract the event organizers, professionals, artists and the researchers to understand better the recent social media landscape in the both festivals.

2.6. Research Methodology: embedded mixed method

The research design of multiple case study allows the author to apply the mixed method as the methodology, which is the ideal approach to globally discuss the social media panorama of Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe. More specifically, the researcher conducted this thesis with the embedded design approach with both quantitative and qualitative data. The fundamental, a quantitative strand about the social media contents and the corresponding results, is supplemented with a qualitative one to depict the perceptions of the festival participants for further interpreting the insights. “In the embedded design, the supplemental strand is added to enhance the overall design in some way” (Creswell and Plano Clark, 2011). At the same time, quantitative data and qualitative data are expected to support each other to optimize the final interpretation of results and contributions of this project.

This project has multiple phases:

2.7. Data Collection

2.7.1. Quantitative Data — Social Media Monitoring Tool

The social media data of Festival Avignon Off have been collected from 05/06/2019 to 02/08/2019, while the data of Edinburgh Festival Fringe have been gathered from 03/07/2019 to 31/08/2019 via the social media monitoring software, Awario, Metricool and Social Blade. The data collecting period is from 30 days before the festivals until 5 days after the festivals.

Awario is a social listening and social media monitoring tool focusing on the conversations and discussions about the brands from the online audiences. Once the researchers set up the “topics” which they want to monitor within a time frame, Awario automatically collects the relevant contents and the quantifiable results (the number of mentions and reach and the relevant statistics) from 13 billion web pages daily and APIs. In this research, Awario has been used for tracking the public conversations about Avignon Off and Edinburgh Fringe. Thus, the topics are “Avignon Off” and “Edinburgh Fringe.” The tracked social media platforms encompasses Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Youtube.

Metricool is social media monitoring tool concentrating on the overall social media results focusing on certain accounts. In this research, Metricool has been used for understanding the contents of posts, the reactions (comments, likes or shares), the engagement rates and the relevant results from the side of event organizers. Therefore, the tracked social media accounts are “Avignon Le Off” and “Edinburgh Festival Fringe.” The tracked platforms are limited to Facebook and Twitter.

Related to the social media contents generated by the event organizers, the author will firstly identify the 15 most engaging posts in the social media platforms. The purposes of identifying the top engaging posts are (1) to see what kind of messages are highly “visible” to the online audiences and (2) to examine whether there is any difference in terms of contents among different social media platforms. All the posts are evaluated in five dimensions (Program, Information, Customer Relations, Emotion and Stimulation) according to the table below (Table 3.8.1.a.), and each of the posts is categorized into the 2 most related content variables.

Table 3.8.1.a. Types of Contents

	Variable	Definition	Measure	Option
1	Program	The post reminds audiences of dates and activities.	ordinal	0 = normal; 1 = positive
2	Information	The post gives festival’s general information.	ordinal	0 = normal; 1 = positive
3	Customer Relation	The post talks directly to the public to build up a nicer relationship.	ordinal	0 = normal; 1 = positive
4	Emotion	The post showcases the positive feelings of the festival.	ordinal	0 = normal; 1 = positive
5	Stimulation	The post calls for the audiences to join in activities or to take any action.	ordinal	0 = normal; 1 = positive

Social Blade, a social media tracking tool, was used for tracking the historical views of the two festivals’ videos on Youtube.

2.7.2. Quantitative Data — Offline Communication

The offline flyers of Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe in 2019 are used to verify the feasibility of utilizing the flyer contents directly on their social media. The flyers have been collected by the author himself at the festivals' sites in the two periods: (1) 05 – 06 July for Festival Avignon Off and (2) 16 – 17 August for Edinburgh Festival Fringe. The number of flyers of each festival ideally has to reach at least 100 so the samples are significant enough to do any further analysis. The size of the flyers is limited mainly from A5 to B5.

After collecting the flyers, the author examines whether all the flyers have the 27 communication variables (Table 3.8.2.a.) and builds up a database for further analysis and comparisons between the two festivals.

Table 3.8.2.a. Definitions of Communication Variables

	Variable	Definition	Measure	Option
1	Email	Any email contact	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
2	Website	Any website reference	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
3	Social media	Any social media reference, such as hashtag or account name	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
4	Video sharing web	Any video sharing site's reference	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
5	Summary	Any sentence explaining the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
6	Words of summary	The roughly total amount of words of the summary	Ratio	
7	Press (quotation)	Any quotation or review from the digital or traditional press	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
8	Number of press	The number of press shown	Ratio	
9	QR code	Any QR code	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
10	Local phone number	Any telephone number with the regional code of the festival	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
11	Corporate phone number	Any telephone number without the regional code	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
12	Other phone number	Any other telephone number except the variable (10) and (11)	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
13	Name of author	Creator's name of the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes

14	Name of director	Director's name of the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
15	Name of performer	Performer's name of the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
16	Performing dates	The performing period in the festival	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
17	Performing time	The performing time in the festival	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
18	Ticket price	The ticket price of the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
19	Duration	The duration of the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
20	Location	The location of the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
21	Visualization of the front page	The roughly visual proportion at the front page of flyers	Ratio	
22	Award	The prize won by the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
23	Marketing label	The label which stimulates ticket sales	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
24	100/500/1000 anniversary	The anniversary of the show	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
25	New creation	The show which is a new creation	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
26	Festival logo	The image which mentions the festival	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes
27	Discount	The discount which stimulates ticket sales	Nominal	0 = No, 1 = Yes

2.7.3. Qualitative Data — Stakeholders' Perceptions

The author travels to both Avignon Off and Edinburgh Fringe for conducting more than 10 face-to-face short interviews randomly for each festival. On the side of interview structure, Hashemnezhad (2015) pointed out that semi-structured interview composes of a set of open questions, which guides the interviewees into the main research direction of the interviewer. For this research, the semi-structured interview is the most suitable one because this structure allows the author to have the relevant results in a few minutes and to have the possibility to know some social media potentials which are not obvious for the author but perhaps significant for the interviewees.

The interviews have been conducted in French, English or Chinese as requested and have followed the interview schedule designed to measure their social media perceptions (Table 3.8.3.a.). To build up a panorama in the subject of social media roles in Festival Avignon Off and Edinburgh Festival Fringe, the potential interviewees have to belong to one of the three categories as follows: (1) Spectators, (2) Performers and (3) Professionals. To facilitate the interview process, the interviews have been recorded

orally, and all the relevant conversations are typed down for further analysis (Appendix 5.1.1.).

Table 3.8.3.a. Interview Schedule

1.	English — Do you use social media in general? French — Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ? Chinese — 您有使用社群媒體的習慣嗎?
2.	English — Do you use social media to prepare your coming? French — Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue ici ? Chinese — 有使用社群媒體準備您的到來嗎?
3.	English — Do you think the social media of the festival is useful? French — Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour un festival comme Avignon ? Chinese — 您覺得藝術節的社群媒體好用嗎?
4.	English — What kind of information do you want to get more from the social media of the festival? French — Quelle type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur le festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux? Chinese — 您會想在藝術節的社群媒體上找到何種資訊?)
5.	English — Do you think it's possible that one day the social media is integrated in a show creation? French— Est-ce que dans la création, les artistes pourraient, ou les producteurs pourraient intégrer les réseaux sociaux ? Chinese — 有沒有可能藝術家或製作人將社群媒體與藝術創作本身結合?)

2.8. Results

2.8.1. Quantitative Data — Social Media Monitoring Tool

2.8.1.1. Awario

2.8.1.1.1. Facebook

Festival Avignon Off

In this sector, Awario has collected 1,754 posts in Facebook. Among them, 1,057 posts have the complete data and are usable for analysis. Festival Avignon Off has been mentioned no more than 10 times per day one month before the festival starting date (5th July) on Facebook except 17th June (12 posts). Since 1st July, the daily times of mentioning “Avignon Off” on Facebook have started to be higher. Moreover, the daily volumes of mentions “Avignon Off” indicate a curve which well explains the rhythm of OFF’s online popularity and the fact that 72% posts mentioning OFF have been published “during” the festival (from 5th to 28th of July) (Figure 2.8.1.1.1.a.).

Figure 2.8.1.1.a. Festival Avignon Off: Number of Facebook Mentions

93% Facebook posts collected (981 out of 1,057), which clarified the locations of publications, such as city or country, have been included in the location analysis below (Figure 2.8.1.1.1.b.). By grouping the posts by the three geographical zones from the nearest (Zone 1) to the farthest (Zone 3) and sorting from the biggest to the smallest volume of posts by location, 67% of posts were published in Avignon, and 18% were published in Ile-de-France. The Facebook posts published in other countries have not

mentioned “Avignon Off” so much (roughly 2%); yet, Taiwan and Geneva have mentioned OFF (1% for each) more than the nearby city, Marseille (0%).

Figure 2.8.1.1.b. Festival Avignon Off: Facebook Mentions, Reach, Post Efficiency by Location

	City / Location	Number of FB Posts	% Posts	Reach	% Reach	Reach / Post
Zone 1	Avignon	667	63%	4,006,850	29%	6,007
	Village du Off	47	4%	1,572,600	12%	33,460
	Théâtre	16	2%	58,385	0%	3,649
	Lyon	39	4%	169,800	1%	4,354
	Marseille	2	0%	3,993	0%	1,997
Zone 2	Paris	128	12%	4,441,125	33%	34,696
	Saint-Germain-lès-Corbeil	40	4%	344,000	3%	8,600
	Saint-Germain-en-Laye	26	2%	1,008,300	7%	38,781
	Malakoff	1	0%	366,000	3%	366,000
Zone 3	Taiwan	7	1%	239,100	2%	34,157
	Switzerland	7	1%	222,200	2%	31,743
	Geneva	1	0%	210,800	2%	210,800
Total Data Files		1057	100%	13,636,701	100%	12,901
	<i>Split ></i>	981	93%	12,643,153	93%	12,888

On the right side of the Figure 2.8.1.1.b., Facebook reach represents the size of the audiences of the posts. Again, the Facebook posts which mentioned “Avignon Off” from Avignon and from Île-de-France have the most significant and the biggest sizes of audiences (41% reach from the posts in Avignon and 46% reach from the posts in Île-de-France; among them, 33% reach from Paris). The posts published from neighboring cities, Lyon and Marseille, have only 1% of the total reach.

On the rightmost column, the ratio of “Reach” divided by “Post” signifies the post efficiency. It’s worth highlighting that as the two main sources potentially influencing the most the online audiences about Festival Avignon Off, the posts from Paris have an almost 6 times higher post efficiency than the ones from Avignon. Besides, small size countries like Taiwan and Switzerland have reached the similar level of post efficiency as Paris, which is more than 31,000 Facebook audiences per post.

Edinburgh Festival Fringe

Awario has collected 1,787 posts in Facebook. 1,107 posts which have complete data are usable for further analysis. Fringe’s daily evolution of mentions neither shows the bell-

shape curve as OFF's nor has an obvious starting point of the increasing online popularity; instead, Edinburgh Festival Fringe has the corrugated curve until the middle of festival (12th August) and a high peak in the end (Figure 2.8.1.1.1.c.).

Figure 2.8.1.1.1.c. Edinburgh Festival Fringe: Number of Facebook Mentions

897 Facebook posts out of 1107 (81%) have mentioned the locations of posts (Figure 2.8.1.1.1.d.). At first, for both mentions and reach, roughly 70% are posted from the UK. According to the statistics, it is obvious that most of the mentions in Fringe are posted from Edinburgh (28%) and London (5%), Glasgow (3%), United States (4%) and Australia (3%).

The total amount of mentions from other cities in UK accounts for 21%, which explains that Fringe has a bigger diversity of its online audiences compared to Avignon OFF. Again, OFF's posts from Paris and from Avignon have accounted for 75% of its total mentions, while the overall percentage of mentions from the top 5 cities in Fringe does not surpass even 40%. Another prove is that Edinburgh, the city of Fringe, occupies merely 28% of the total mentions in Fringe compared to Avignon's 67% of the total mentions in OFF.

Edinburgh (19%), London (23%) and Other UK's cities (14%) have the biggest Facebook reach in Fringe. In addition, Fringe also has around 1% of online conversations in Singapore and India.

Figure 2.8.1.1.1.d. Festival Edinburgh Fringe: Facebook Mentions / Reach / Post Efficiency by Location

Facebook Posts mentioning "Edinburgh Fringe"					
CITY	Number of Posts	% POSTS	Reach	% REACH	Reach / Post
Edinburgh	313	28%	6,543,275	19%	20,905
London	58	5%	8,097,626	23%	139,614
Glasgow	37	3%	1,500,363	4%	40,550
Dublin	21	2%	1,909,000	5%	90,905
Newcastle upon Tyne	12	1%	317,366	1%	26,447
Durham	7	1%	18,271	0%	2,610
Manchester	5	0%	108,488	0%	21,698
Aberdeen	5	0%	86,035	0%	17,207
Cardiff	4	0%	114,392	0%	28,598
Leeds	2	0%	16,540	0%	8,270
Birmingham	1	0%	11,400	0%	11,400
The Secret Comedy Club Brighton	67	6%	174,200	0%	2,600
Assembly Festival	12	1%	19,800	0%	1,650
Other UK	227	21%	4,841,444	14%	21,328
<i>S/T United Kingdom</i>	771	70%	23,758,200	68%	30,815
Other Ireland	6	1%	2,054,800	6%	342,467
Australia	38	3%	1,193,102	3%	31,397
United States	41	4%	1,388,547	4%	33,867
France	20	2%	156,953	0%	7,848
Canada	15	1%	121,300	0%	8,087
India	2	0%	413,000	1%	206,500
Singapore	4	0%	218,423	1%	54,606
Total Database	1107	100%	35,078,208	100%	31,688
<i>Split ></i>	897	81%	29,304,325	84%	32,669

2.8.1.1.2. Twitter

Festival Avignon Off

Awario has collected 1,821 tweets mentioning “Avignon Off.” 1,401 usable posts, which have the complete data, were included in the analysis. At first, if ranking the posts by country from the biggest quantity to the smallest, the posts from France have contributed to significantly high mentions (1,141 tweets) compared to any other country. The second position was taken by the posts from United States (69 tweets). The third position includes the posts from a group of countries, inclusive of Australia (31 tweets), Taiwan (23 tweets), Belgium (23 tweets) and Switzerland (17 tweets) (Table 2.8.1.1.2.a.).

If sorting the posts by reach from the biggest to the smallest by country, France (10 M reach), United States (1 M reach), Belgium (146 K reach), Taiwan (77 K reach), Australia (72 K reach) and Switzerland (17 K reach) have the top rankings (Table 2.8.1.1.2.b.). Overall, France and United States have the top performances both in the number of mentions and reach.

Table 2.8.1.1.2.a.

Avignon Off: Twitter Mentions by Country

Tweets mentioning "Avignon Off" by Country			
Country	Number of Posts	% Posts	Reach
France	1,141	82%	10,091,160
United States	69	5%	1,100,508
Australia	31	2%	72,848
Belgium	23	2%	146,648
Taiwan	23	2%	77,329
Switzerland	17	1%	16,987
Spain	9	1%	27,419
Canada	9	1%	23,950
United Kingdom	8	1%	12,200
China	8	1%	14,013
Italy	6	0%	12,833

Table 2.8.1.1.2.b.

Avignon Off: Twitter Reach by Country

Tweets mentioning "Avignon Off" by Country			
Country	Number of Posts	Reach	% Reach
France	1,141	10,091,160	87%
United States	69	1,100,508	9%
Belgium	23	146,648	1%
Taiwan	23	77,329	1%
Australia	31	72,848	1%
Spain	9	27,419	0%
Canada	9	23,950	0%
Switzerland	17	16,987	0%
China	8	14,013	0%
Italy	6	12,833	0%
United Kingdom	8	12,200	0%

1,137 OFF's posts on Twitter have clarified their precise locations, such as cities. In France, the tweets from Paris (414 tweets), from others (298 tweets) and from Avignon (134 tweets) have accumulated the biggest number of tweets (Table 2.8.1.1.2.c.). Compared to Avignon Off's mentions on Facebook (Table 2.8.1.1.1.b.), OFF's mentions on Twitter were less dominated by Avignon & Paris but more diverse. OFF's mentions on Facebook are 75% from Paris & Avignon, while OFF's mentions on Twitter are 48% from Paris & Avignon with 26% from other cities. If taking a look at the city level, OFF's Twitter mentions are 36% from Paris and 12% from Avignon, while OFF's Facebook mentions are 12% from Paris and 63% from Avignon. In fact, OFF's Twitter mentions from Paris are 3 times more than the ones from Avignon. Both the neighboring cities, Marseille and Lyon, have 1.5% of the total mentions.

Table 2.8.1.1.2.c.

Table 2.8.1.1.2.d.

Avignon Off: Twitter Mentions by City (FR)

Avignon Off: Twitter Reach by City (FR)

Tweets mentioning "Avignon Off" by City in France				Tweets mentioning "Avignon Off" by City in France			
Country	Number of Posts	% Posts	Reach	Country	Number of Posts	Reach	% Reach
Paris	414	36%	8,182,668	Paris	414	8,182,668	81%
Others	298	26%	979,044	Others	298	979,044	10%
Avignon	134	12%	633,922	Avignon	134	633,922	6%
Rouen	43	4%	6,839	Marseille	33	57,755	1%
Marseille	33	3%	57,755	Berre-l'Étang	21	35,486	0%
Berre-l'Étang	21	2%	35,486	Lyon	17	25,421	0%
Lyon	17	1%	25,421	Limoges	3	17,515	0%
Bagneux	13	1%	10,550	Metz	1	16,900	0%
Antony	10	1%	4,657	Créteil	2	10,600	0%
Nîmes	7	1%	1,156	Bagneux	13	10,550	0%
Le Touquet-Paris-Plage	6	1%	2,616	Strasbourg	3	7,146	0%
Montpellier	5	0%	5,006	Rouen	43	6,839	0%
Bordeaux	5	0%	1,405	Saint-Ouen	2	6,700	0%
Nancy	5	0%	977	Hendaye	1	5,900	0%
Chalon-sur-Saône	4	0%	342	Saint-Cloud	1	5,400	0%
Aix-en-Provence	4	0%	4,476	Montpellier	5	5,006	0%
Annecy	4	0%	1,494	Antony	10	4,657	0%
Dordives	4	0%	2,704	Aix-en-Provence	4	4,476	0%

On the other side, if ranking the results from the biggest to the smallest reach by city in France, the posts from Paris (8 M reach), from Others (979 K reach), from Avignon (634 K reach) and from Marseille (58 K reach) have the best rankings (Table 2.8.1.1.2.d.). Here, the posts from Paris have 81% of OFF's total audiences on Twitter, which are more than double of its percentage of audiences on Facebook (33%). Besides, the neighboring

countries, Marseille and Lyon, have only nearly 1% reach of the online conversations on Twitter.

Opinion Leaders

The influential Twitter accounts in Paris, which have mentioned “Avignon Off” in their tweets include Chirstophe Barbier (504,500 reach), Marianne (405,500 reach), Télérama (366,800 reach), Francinfo plus (272,200 reach), Radio Nova (106,400 reach), Tristan Nitot (98,200 reach), Culturebox (79,500 reach), Le Figaro Culture (67,100 reach) , La1ere.fr (43,900 reach), Babelio (43,300 reach), Mona Chollet (40,900 reach), Politis (39,700 reach), Danielle Simonnet (33,600 reach), Jean-François Guyot (33,100 reach), Mediapart, le Club (29,700 reach) and Toute La Culture (24,400 reach). Most of the influential Twitter accounts belong to traditional press, and most of their posts are around stories and critics of the plays, the interviews with comedians or the event organizer, the guide or recommendations for show selection and some event reminders.

Edinburgh Festival Fringe

Awario has collected 9,797 tweets of Fringe. 7,219 tweets which have complete data are usable and included in the analysis. By sorting the tweets by volume of posts in descending order, the top four locations which have the most tweets mentioning “Edinburgh Fringe” contain the UK, the U.S., Scotland and Ireland (Table 2.9.1.1.2.e.). If sorting them by reach in descending order, the top four locations, which have the most significant sizes of audiences, include the UK, the U.S., India and Ireland (see Table 2.9.1.1.2.f.).

Table 2.9.1.1.2.e.

Table 2.9.1.1.2.f.

Edinburgh Fringe: Twitter Mentions by Country Edinburgh Fringe: Twitter Reach by Country

Tweets mentioning "Edinburgh Fringe" by Country				Tweets mentioning "Edinburgh Fringe" by Country			
Country	Number of Tweets	% Posts	Reach	Country	Number of Tweets	Reach	% Reach
United Kingdom	5,296	73%	60,105,256	United Kingdom	5,296	60,105,256	78%
United States	664	9%	5,332,661	United States	664	5,332,661	7%
Scotland	143	2%	379,175	India	39	3,486,787	4%
Ireland	138	2%	2,168,811	Ireland	138	2,168,811	3%
Australia	77	1%	412,892	France	58	1,071,498	1%
Canada	60	1%	282,605	Netherlands	55	996,464	1%
France	58	1%	1,071,498	Belgium	13	510,775	1%
England	57	1%	151,592	Cuba	1	467,600	1%
Netherlands	55	1%	996,464	Australia	77	412,892	1%
Jamaica	45	1%	133,409	Scotland	143	379,175	0%
India	39	1%	3,486,787	Canada	60	282,605	0%
Germany	35	0%	113,390	Gambia	2	197,600	0%
Japan	20	0%	27,479	South Sandwich Islands (UK)	9	185,914	0%
Spain	17	0%	51,715	England	57	151,592	0%
Liberia	16	0%	67,833	Jamaica	45	133,409	0%
Argentina	15	0%	26,698	Germany	35	113,390	0%
China	15	0%	18,203	South Africa	15	100,661	0%
South Africa	15	0%	100,661	Sardinia (Italy)	1	85,200	0%
New Zealand	15	0%	30,273	Holy See (Vatican City State)	3	84,600	0%

By arranging in order the numbers of tweets by location, the top cities which have the most tweets mentioning “Edinburgh Fringe” are Others (2,339 tweets), London (1,546 tweets), Edinburgh (948 tweets) and Glasgow (176 tweets) (Table 2.9.1.1.2.g.).

By sorting by the volume of reach, London (34%), Others (33%), Edinburgh (10%) and Mumbai (4%) have the biggest reach in Fringe (Table 2.9.1.1.2.h.).

Table 2.9.1.1.2.g.

Table 2.9.1.1.2.h.

Edinburgh Fringe: Twitter Mentions by City (UK) Edinburgh Fringe: Twitter Reach by City (UK)

Tweets mentioning "Edinburgh Fringe" by City				Tweets mentioning "Edinburgh Fringe" by City			
City	Number of Tweets	% Posts	Reach	City	Number of Tweets	Reach	% Reach
Others	2,339	32%	25,203,321	London	1,546	26,441,457	34%
London	1,546	21%	26,441,457	Others	2,339	25,203,321	33%
Edinburgh	948	13%	8,031,946	Edinburgh	948	8,031,946	10%
Glasgow	176	2%	1,115,355	Mumbai	10	3,464,200	4%
Manchester	58	1%	82,555	Glasgow	176	1,115,355	1%
Bristol	57	1%	162,238	Wells-next-the-Sea	7	1,012,800	1%
Dublin	56	1%	935,524	Dublin	56	935,524	1%
Birmingham	42	1%	94,870	Blackpool	6	796,025	1%
Leeds	41	1%	122,170	Au Gres	9	767,700	1%
Sheffield	40	1%	147,082	Knightsbridge	2	722,200	1%
Cardiff	39	1%	123,226	Bruxelles - Brussel	7	509,246	1%
Newcastle upon Tyne	38	1%	210,638	La Habana	1	467,600	1%
Liverpool	32	0%	56,799	New York City	22	310,658	0%
Hull	32	0%	149,757	Brighton	20	249,555	0%
Earth (US)	26	0%	161,722	Newcastle upon Tyne	38	210,638	0%
Aberdeen	25	0%	118,728	Limerick	4	210,151	0%
Durham	24	0%	28,009	Cambridge	20	210,026	0%
Norwich	23	0%	59,122	Kunkugang	2	197,600	0%
New York	22	0%	310,658	Bristol	57	162,238	0%
Melbourne	21	0%	56,371	Earth (US)	26	161,722	0%
Stratford-upon-Avon	21	0%	7,869	Hull	32	149,757	0%
Cambridge	20	0%	210,026	Sheffield	40	147,082	0%
				Cardiff	39	123,226	0%
				Leeds	41	122,170	0%
				Aberdeen	25	118,728	0%

2.8.1.1.3. Youtube

Festival Avignon Off

Awario has collected 217 videos from Youtube which have mentioned “Avignon Off.” The 30 top videos with the highest reach have occupied merely 67.3% of the total online audiences (184,677 reach) (Table 2.8.1.1.3.a.). That is, the visibility does not be given merely to a few videos like the situation in Edinburgh Fringe (Table 2.8.1.1.3.b.). Furthermore, the 7 top videos in terms of reach in Edinburgh Fringe have accounted for 95% of the total reach, while 7 top videos in terms of reach in Avignon Off have stood for 58% of the total reach.

The video contents in Avignon Off have the one-man comedy show, the news focusing on both Avignon In and Off, the promotional clips from the event organizer, the feedback from the participants, some teasers of the shows, the transportation service to Avignon,

the formal interviews conducted by the theatre magazine and the record of the bustling opening parade. Compared to Edinburgh Fringe, the top videos centering on Avignon Off do not give the spectator's or the artist's perspective but more formal and professional perspective. In fact, 2 out of 10 top videos mentioning "Edinburgh Fringe" give the viewers the chance to know what a day look like as a performer and as a visitor in the festival.

Table 2.8.1.1.3.a. Top 30 videos mentioning "Avignon Off" on Youtube

Youtube - Reach - Avignon OFF 2019								
	Channel	Title	Date	Duration	View	Comment	Reach	% Reach
1	Noman Hosni	LA VÉRITÉ SUR AVIGNON OFF - NOMAN HOSNI	7/22/2019	03:31	39,700	37	92,109	33.5%
2	France 3 Pays de la Loire	Théâtre : on vous emmène au festival d'Avignon !	7/15/2019	01:59	430	0	21,481	7.8%
3	NEW COM	En mode Off - épisode 04 - Festival OFF d'Avignon	7/5/2019	02:57	2,900	0	14,334	5.2%
4	NEW COM	Soirée des Partenaires du Festival OFF d'Avignon 2019	7/24/2019	02:47	1,200	0	11,787	4.3%
5	NEW COM	Le OFF n'est pas fatigué - Du 5 au 28 juillet 2019	7/24/2019	02:18	1,200	1	11,546	4.2%
6	Lolla Wesh	LA DERNIÈRE DU FESTIVAL OFF D'AVIGNON	7/27/2019	00:59	649	1	4,481	1.6%
7	rikedenimes	OFF AVIGNON 2019 : Wok'n Woll (Au Coin de la Lune Théâtre)	7/19/2019	07:10	235	0	3,826	1.4%
8	rikedenimes	AVIGNON OFF 2019 : Bérengère JULLIAN & Pierre MER (Passagers)	7/22/2019	05:09	168	0	3,780	1.4%
9	rikedenimes	AVIGNON OFF 2019 : Semeurs de Reï,ves (Au Coin de la Lune)	7/23/2019	06:37	122	0	3,742	1.4%
10	Avignon le OFF - Festival OFF d'Avignon (Avignon Festival &	REPORTAGE #1 - La parade d'ouverture #OFF19	7/6/2019	02:39	400	0	2,056	0.7%
11	Fabrice Splinder	#OFF19 - Festival OFF d'Avignon 2019 - Interview Hits play radio	7/12/2019	06:48	212	0	1,978	0.7%
12	Les Funambules	Les Funambules Bande-annonce Festival d'Avignon Off 2019 (Officiel)	6/18/2019	02:11	440	1	1,973	0.7%
13	Magali Coudray	CH+ BIFLUORÉE PASSE À TABLE AVIGNON OFF 2019	6/17/2019	01:39	687	0	1,916	0.7%
14	Avignon le OFF - Festival OFF d'Avignon (Avignon Festival & Compagnies / AF&C)	#OFF19 : La Famille Ortiz	7/13/2019	01:29	344	0	1,809	0.7%
15	Alexandr Glumov	ZhArt in Dresden. The way to Avignon OFF festival	7/23/2019	02:45	100	0	1,125	0.4%
16	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - LA MOITIÉ DU CIEL	7/18/2019	02:10	330	0	627	0.2%
17	Bintily Diallo	Que faut-il voir au Festival OFF d'Avignon 2019 ? (La Matinale LCI)	7/4/2019	03:08	399	0	626	0.2%
18	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - NOS PENIS DIVERGENT	7/9/2019	01:05	330	0	531	0.2%
19	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - J'ARRIVERAI PAR L'ASCENSEUR DE 22H43	7/9/2019	01:25	239	0	531	0.2%
20	Plain Chant [Marie]	QUE FAUT-IL ALLER VOIR AU FESTIVAL D'AVIGNON 2019 ? (IN/OFF)	7/6/2019	08:39	583	1	494	0.2%
21	Agence Clin d'Oeil	Grande Parade du Festival Off d'Avignon 2019	7/5/2019	07:29	698	1	461	0.2%
22	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - GLOBE STORY	7/8/2019	01:57	297	2	459	0.2%
23	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - LA PHÈDRE ETERNELLE	7/7/2019	01:54	234	0	428	0.2%
24	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - ECHOS RURAUX	7/11/2019	01:11	180	0	422	0.2%
25	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - LE CREPUSCULE	7/8/2019	02:22	186	0	417	0.2%
26	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - TOI TU TE TAIS	7/8/2019	01:54	165	0	401	0.1%
27	Profession Spectacle	AVIGNON 2019 - COMME DES POISSONS DANS L'EAU	7/16/2019	02:03	132	0	393	0.1%
28	巴黎臺灣文化中心CCTP	2019 Taiwan Avignon Off 臺灣外亞維儂藝術節	6/27/2019	01:24	208	0	342	0.1%
29	Klotilde -	TEASER KLOTILDE - AVIGNON OFF 2019	6/13/2019	01:17	181	1	328	0.1%
30	Odalva	Odalva - teaser Avignon Off 2019	6/13/2019	01:44	334	1	274	0.1%
Total Videos: 217								
Total Reach: 274,584								

Edinburgh Festival Fringe

Awario has collected 137 Youtube videos. Merely 124 ones have more than 1% of the total reach. Because the author could not access the location-oriented data of the videos shared, the location analysis for Youtube could not be conducted. Nevertheless, the author could do the analysis by reach, views and contents.

Table below at first indicates the top 10 videos which have obtained the biggest amount of Youtube reach (Table 2.8.1.1.3.b.). Around 95% of reach concentrated on three videos, published by Al Jazeera English, an English news channel based in the Middle East), Daily Mail and Guardian News, two British daily newspapers.

Table 2.8.1.1.3.b. Top 10 videos mentioning “Edinburgh Fringe” on Youtube

Youtube - Reach - Edinburgh Fringe 2019								
Video	Channel	Title	Date	Duration	View	Comment	Reach	% Reach
1	Al Jazeera English	Edinburgh arts festival offers performers counselling	5/8/2019	00:55	640	1	3,600,000	74%
2	Daily Mail	Olaf Falafel wins 2019 Edinburgh Fringe Festival joke	23/08/2019	00:52	2274	17	537,900	11%
3	Guardian News	Edinburgh Fringe's funniest jokes from 2012 to 2019	19/08/2019	00:48	20278	34	504,800	10%
4	Ali Clarkson	Drop And Roll At Edinburgh Fringe	27/08/2019	25:17	7327	72	73,200	2%
5	ChortleUK	Sara Barron at Fast Fringe	24/08/2019	04:07	635	0	27,100	1%
6	ChortleUK	Jack Tucker at Fast Fringe	24/08/2019	04:43	898	1	26,900	1%
7	ChortleUK	Helen Bauer on Fast Fringe	5/8/2019	03:54	679	0	26,900	1%
8	Lia Hatzakis	EDINBURGH FRINGE FESTIVAL VLOG! ft Hannah Witton	28/08/2019	23:15	11628	242	22,300	0%
9	Celebrity Radio by Alex Belfield	4* Review West End Producer FREE WILLY Edinburgh Fringe 2019	6/8/2019	03:06	60	0	18,200	0%
10	Celebrity Radio by Alex Belfield	1* REVIEW Friendsical The Musical Edinburgh Fringe 2019	6/8/2019	25:23	611	0	18,200	0%
Total Videos: 124								
Total Reach: 4,877,900								

In terms of video visibility, the video 3 focusing on the collection of the annual top Fringe jokes in the past seven years has gained more than 20 K views. It has inspired not only more online audiences to post more jokes in the comment sector below but also has opened the public debates on whether writing a joke based on a syndrome is appropriate or not.

Getting the second biggest volume of views, the video 8 shares the Youtuber's experience of participating in Edinburgh as a tourist. She used a friend-tone to share with her online audiences about everything in her journey, such as her accommodation, Edinburgh's historical street views and architecture, her transportation, her meals and her reunion with her friend.

The third most visible video about Fringe goes to video 4, which was filmed by a trick cyclist, another Youtuber, about his day in the festival. In the first part, he used a friend-tone and shared his news and stay in Edinburgh with the online audiences. The second part of the video did the introduction from the backstage to the equipment on the stage. The third part gave the performer perspective during the show, which allowed the online viewers to imagine as they were on the stage with him. In the comment sector, the live audiences were truly thankful for his efforts and recommended his wonderful show. Besides, his Youtube channel followers as well appreciated this video.

2.8.1.1.4. Instagram

Festival Avignon Off

Awario has collected 24 Instagram posts. In the photos below, the readers may feel and capture the atmosphere during the festival. The contents of posts are quite diversified, inclusive of the appreciation for the audiences, the interviews, information for the upcoming performances, the show promotion, the professional event and the scene of rehearsal.

(Avignon Le OFF, 2019)

(Laura Calu, 2019)

(Laurent Lamarca, 2019)

(Stéphanie Marino, 2019)

(Avignon Le OFF, 2019)

In the table below, the author sorted all the posts by reach from the biggest to the smallest and analyzed the contents of the best performance posts (Table 2.8.1.1.4.a.). The 12 posts below which have obtained 97% of the total reach.

The most “liked” post expressed both the humorist’s thankfulness for the arrival of the audiences and the spectators’ joyfulness after seeing the show (Laura Calu, 2019). In the comment sector, the online public was touched so much by the enormous emotions and by the positive feedback. Thus, the online audiences asked her to bring her show even to more cities. The second most liked post is the promotional post which announced the performer’s stay in Avignon and encouraged the viewers to buy the tickets. The third most liked post focuses on introducing the services in Village Off and welcoming the public to come.

Table 2.8.1.1.4.a. Top 12 posts mentioning “Avignon Off” on Instagram

Instagram - Reach - Avignon OFF 2019								
Author name	Author Info	Date	Post	Like	Comment	Reach	% Reach	
1	laura_calu	Humorist	7/30/2019	Encore un IMMENSE MERCI à ceux qui se sont déplacés pour venir voir “En Grand” durant le festival off d’Avignon. Maintenant place aux vacances ! 🌞 Vous pourrez retrouver “En Grand” dès la rentrée à Paris ...	1,985	39	168,375	61%
2	labrune_et_lesprunes	Comedian	7/14/2019	Les Petites Mains ! 15h - Collège de la Salle Avignon off #toseoornottosee #lespetitesmainsspectacle #festivalavignon #avignonoff #off19	35	3	26,338	10%
3	labrune_et_lesprunes	Comedian	7/7/2019	Venez ! Collège de la Salle. 15h. Avignon off, jusqu’au 28 juillet 🇫🇷 #lespetitesmainsspectacle #avignonoff #festivaloff #off19 #theatre	35	2	26,337	10%
4	lamarcalaurant	Performer	7/4/2019	Ce soir c’est la première du festival Off d’Avignon au Théâtre arrachecoeuroff ! La première d’une longue série jusqu’au 28 juillet!!! La billetterie est dans ma bio! #OYC2019 #TalentsAdami Photo : leoerem	314	5	5,758	2%
5	avignonleoff	Event Organ	7/6/2019	pratiques pour organiser votre programme pour le festival OFF d’Avignon 2019 🇫🇷🇫🇷 AF&C - ulysspicture	259	3	5,744	2%
6	avignonleoff	Event Organ	7/4/2019	🇫🇷 H-10 avant la grande #parade d’ouverture du #festival avignonleoff 🇫🇷 Nous sommes très heureux d’accueillir la batucada Oumpack 🇫🇷 pour accompagner les #artistes et #compagnies du #OFF19 ...	145	4	5,631	2%
7	avignonleoff	Event Organ	7/17/2019	... l’ #application Avignon OFF ! Vous pourrez y retrouver le #programme et la #billetterie ticket’OFF, l’agenda du Village du OFF, et bien d’autres ! âžš...	36	0	5,617	2%
8	avignonleoff	Event Organ	7/12/2019	... la rencontre le festival OFF d’Avignon, une fenÃ@tre sur le monde #1 à€€ à€€ à€€ à€€ [Retrouvez tout le programme du Focus sur FB ou sur la plateforme ...	64	1	5,546	2%
9	paris_art_com	News	7/17/2019	... dans le cadre du Off du Festival d’Avignon ! DÃ@tails sur le site. Ici : Edouard Hue (Cie Beaver Dam), Into Outside, 2016. Danse contemporaine. Â© Zoe ...	39	0	4,784	2%
10	paris_art_com	News	7/9/2019	... Fernandez. #danse #art #avignon #off #onydanse #hivernales #cdcn #festivalavignon #dansecontemporaine #chorÃ@graphes #crÃ@ation	34	0	4,754	2%
11	julie_combaluzier	Director	7/6/2019	LE SPECTACLE DU FESTIVAL D’AVIGNON 2019, le OFF suzanne.b.godillot est Marie-Antoinette tous les jours à 21h15 au Théâtre Barretta Place Saint-Didier à Avignon pour le plus grand festival de théâtre ouvert ...	105	5	4,351	2%
12	villedavignon	City	7/3/2019	Avignon fait son Festival ! Le Off, c’est du 5 juillet au 28 juillet. #avignon#avignonoff2019#affichage #off#off2019#festival#avignonleoff2019#avignoncité#théâtre #spectacle	131	1	2,579	1%
Total Posts: 24								
Total Reach: 273,848								

Edinburgh Festival Fringe

Awario has collected 105 Instagram posts which gained 1.7 M reach in total on Instagram. Among them, the author took the 10 posts which have gained the most reach to do further content analysis.

(Karen From Finance, 2019)

(BBC Radio 2, 2019)

(Sarah Millican, 2019)

(BBC Asian Network, 2019)

(Luke McGarry, 2019)

In the top 10 Instagram posts in terms of reach, the posts are mostly informal, intimate and relax. To illustrate, the contents include personal recommendations for show selection from the comedians, the announcement of the upcoming podcasts, the passionate associative activity in Fringe and the photo service for the visitors. If further ranking by the volume of likes, the most “liked” post, which has obtained 1,900 likes, is the interesting illustration by humorously depicting the interaction and exchange with Fringe’s leafleteer in the streets (Luke McGarry, 2019). The second- most “liked” post (Post 5) centers on the figure’s sharing of her nice journey in Fringe and her lovely marriage. The topic of marriage and her participation in a British baker TV show have resonated with lots of people and have stimulated them to give like or even some short comments.

Table 2.8.1.1.4.a. Top 10 posts mentioning “Edinburgh Fringe” on Instagram

Instagram - Reach - Edinburgh Fringe 2019								
	Author Name	Author Info	Date	Post	Like	Comment	Reach	% Reach
1	thesarahmillican	Comedian	8/14/2019	If you're at the Edinburgh fringe, I highly recommend hayles_ellis show. Proper laugh out loud funny all the way through. Grab a ticket. She's one of ...	782	9	298,531	16.9%
2	bbcradio2	Radio	7/29/2019	... Steve Wright to talk about starring in Eugene O'Neill's play 'Hughie' at Edinburgh Fringe Festival. Head to bbcsounds for the Big Guests podcast!	226	4	172,228	9.7%
3	bbcradio2	Radio	7/30/2019	... Guests podcast. The latest episode brings Comedian Matt Forde talking to Steve Wright about his Edinburgh Fringe shows! Head to bbcsounds. ?...	152	2	172,152	9.7%
4	alidawah	Org. founder	8/16/2019	SALAM team visits Edinburgh fringe festival to share the art of dawah via our actions & some dawah cakes . Full video of campaign & 60second ...	996	25	140,995	8.0%
5	brionymaybakes	Baker	8/16/2019	EDINBURGH FRINGE WAS AMAZING!!! It felt like capitals were necessary because I had the best time away with steve_briony's_husband • Life has been so ...	1,300	17	99,699	5.6%
6	flytographer	Photographer	7/25/2019	Are you a Fringe goer? Edinburgh's Fringe Fest takes over this historic city each year in August when thousands of performers and festival-goers ...	414	2	86,110	4.9%
7	bbcasiannetwork	News	8/29/2019	#AsianNetworkComedy at this year's Edinburgh Fringe Festival is live on BBC iPlayer NOW #edfringe	660	5	77,009	4.3%
8	lukeymcgarry	Cartoonist	8/11/2019	A classic in honor of Edinburgh Fringe. #fringe #edfringe #edinburgh #improv #comedy #theatre #illustration #drawingaday edfringe	1,900	29	48,082	2.7%
9	karenfromfinance	Drag queen	8/6/2019	... looks in London at therealdollydiamond 's game show Blankety Blanks. If you're in Edinburgh or Fringe this month be sure to check it out!!	685	4	47,742	2.7%
10	cambridgewords	Dictionary	8/5/2019	Which 2019 Edinburgh Fringe Festival act would you shout for an 'encore!?' Let us know in the comments ðŸ—£ #CambridgeWOTD	440	5	46,869	2.6%
Total Posts: 105								
Total Reach: 1,771,395								

2.8.1.2. *Metricool*

Metricool has tracked 166 Facebook posts, 160 Tweets and 24 Instagram posts published by Avignon Off from 5th June to 2th August in 2019. It has also monitored 359 Facebook posts, 551 tweets and 40 Instagram posts published by Edinburgh Fringe from 3rd July to 31th August in 2019. The definitions of the metrics are as follows: (1) Posts: volume of posts, (2) Reactions: volume of reactions, (3) Comments: volume of comments, (4) Shared: how many times people share the posts and (5) Engagement: by considering the Facebook algorithm and the advertising logic that more money you pay, more audiences you could reach, the engagement rate could be calculated as follows:

$$\frac{\text{Comments+Likes+Shares+Mentions}}{\text{Post Reach}} \quad (\text{Martín, n.d.})$$

2.8.1.2.1. Facebook

Festival Avignon Off

Figure 2.8.1.2.1.a. Social media Performance of OFF’s FB posts

The best OFF’s Facebook posts were published mainly between 2nd to 6th July and secondly at 28th July, which were exactly the beginning and the end of the festival. The best posts in the first peak in the early July mainly focused on the excitement of the launch of OFF’s app and the lively opening parade in which lots of artists, audiences and

professionals engaged. The contents, which created the second peak of reactions in the end of July, composed of the last call for participants to enjoy their last shows and events in OFF 2019 with their friends. The great emotion and enthusiasm were augmented thanks to all the images and videos. It's worth mentioning that 38% of reactions were in the first peak (373 reactions per day).

Table 2.8.1.2.1.a. FB Posts, reactions, comments and shares in different steps of festival

	AO.	Post	% Posts	Reactions	% Reactions	Comments	% Comments	Shared	% Shared
Before the festival	D-30~D-16	6	4%	154	3%	13	4%	76	5%
	D-15~D-0	22	13%	1917	39%	151	49%	502	35%
During the festival	D+0~D+8	40	24%	1282	26%	67	22%	501	35%
	D+9~D+16	49	30%	576	12%	26	8%	112	8%
	D+17~D+24	46	28%	860	18%	44	14%	207	15%
After the festival	D+25~D+29	3	2%	120	2%	8	3%	23	2%
Total		166	100%	4909	100%	309	100%	1421	100%

According to the table above (Table 2.8.1.2.a.), 82% of the total posts created by the event organizer, have been published during the festival. In terms of reactions, comments and shares, the highest summit is equivalent from 15 days before the festival until 8 days after the festival starting date, which has obtained 3,199 reactions, 218 comments and 1,003 shared times.

For doing the content analysis, the author took OFF's 15 posts which got the best engagement rates (Table 2.8.1.2.b. in the next page). To further categorize the contents of these 15 posts which the online audiences have engaged the most, the author evaluated them with the 5 dimensions model ((1) Program, (2) Information, (3) Customer Relations, (4) Emotion and (5) Stimulation) and did further content analysis (Figure 2.8.1.2.1.b.).

Figure 2.8.1.2.1.b. Content Analysis – Avignon Off’s top 15 FB posts

After conducting the content analysis, the research shows that the contents of the top 15 most engaged posts highlighted mainly the three dimensions: Customer Relations (10/30), Emotion (8/30) and Information (8/30). For having a great relationship with the audiences with an emotional approach, OFF’s Facebook posts has frequently appreciated the efforts of the artists, the companies and the public. In addition, OFF’s Facebook has launched a series of festival videos and photos for bringing the online audiences to the bustling opening parade, for visiting the principal spots, for “tasting” the remarkable performances and some spectators’ reviews as well. On the side of Information, OFF’s Facebook has given some practical information to fill the spectators’ informative gap and to facilitate their stays, such as the guidance towards Professional village and OFF village, the reminder for the professionals, the membership cards and the disability inclusion.

Table 2.8.1.2.1.b. Festival Avignon Off: Top 15 FB posts - Engagement Rates

	Post	Date	Reactions	Comments	Engagement
1	L'affichage des #compagnies du festival #OFF19 d'Avignon 2019 ©AF&C - ulysepicture	Jul 4, 2019	466	7	94.22
2	J-7 avant la #parade d'ouverture du #festival avignonleoff 2019 ! Les #compagnies du #OFF19 vous donnent rendez-vous le 4 juillet à 18h en bas de la rue Bonneterie, derrière les Halles pour un moment de fête qui lancera officiellement le festival et vous donnera un aperçu des #artistes présents ! La parade se terminera par un dj set au #VillageduOFF ! • crédit photos thomasobrienphotography	Jun 27, 2019	260	5	54.58
3	Le Village du #OFF19 et le Village des #professionnels ont ouvert leurs portes hier et vous accueillent de 10h à 2h ! Venez découvrir le cœur battant du #festival, ses services, son restaurant, son bar et ses concerts. Venez y rencontrer les #artistes, nous demander des informations pratiques pour organiser votre programme pour le festival OFF d'Avignon 2019 AF&C - ulysepicture	Jul 6, 2019	262	3	51.92
4	Du 5 au 28 juillet, la villedavignon est métamorphosée pour le #festival #OFF19 !	Jul 10, 2019	197	6	38.39
5	La réunion des #compagnies du festival #OFF19 d'Avignon est en cours à la Mairie de la Ville d'Avignon ! Nous sommes très heureux de rencontrer les #artistes de la 54ème édition du #festival ! J-3 !	Jul 2, 2019	170	1	34.55
6	Et toi, c'est quoi ta technique de tractage pour le #festival #OFF19 d'Avignon ? © AF&C - ulysepicture	Jul 12, 2019	182	2	34.19
7	Et vous, qu'est-ce que vous préférez dans les rues de la villedavignon pendant le #festival avignonleoff ?	Jul 23, 2019	177	3	31.17
8	H-10 avant la grande #parade d'ouverture du #festival avignonleoff Nous sommes très heureux d'accueillir la batucada Oumpack pour accompagner les #artistes et #compagnies du #OFF19 ! J-1 avant la 54ème édition du festival OFF d'Avignon, vous êtes prêts ? Rdv à 18h en bas de la rue Bonneterie - derrière les Halles pour le départ de la parade ;)	Jul 4, 2019	145	4	29.68
9	La parade d'ouverture du #festival #OFF19 a débuté ! Merci aux Oumpacks !!	Jul 4, 2019	146	0	29.08
10	Les lauréats du concours des plus belles #affiches du #festival OFF d'Avignon 2019, organisé par labnf, sur la scène du Village du #OFF19 ! © AF&C - ulysepicture	Jul 26, 2019	161	4	28.4
11	Le festival #OFF19 a été riche en émotions, en spectacles et en bonheurs, et c'est grâce à vous ! Merci Merci aux #artistes, aux #compagnies et structures de productions, aux #théâtres et à vous tous, publics de la 54ème édition du #festival, qui restez années après années curieux et passionnés de spectacle vivant ! C'est vous qui faites avignonleoff ! © AF&C - ulysepicture	Jul 30, 2019	3	3	23.99
12	Et vous, vous êtes déjà venus danser sur la piste du Village du #OFF19 ! © AF&C - ulysepicture	Jul 21, 2019	95	1	16.76
13	La veille au soir est au Village du #OFF19 !	Jul 7, 2019	84	0	16.33
14	La famiglia Rubinetti en #concert au Village du #OFF19 ! Merci à eux pour cette super ambiance ! Vous n'avez pas pu venir assister à ce super live ? Bonne nouvelle, ils reviennent demain	Jul 14, 2019	80	3	15.2
15	Pour la première fois au #festival #OFF19 d'Avignon, nous parlons des #politiques #culturelles avec le Relais Culture Europe, le British Council, le Goethe Institute, Hybridites France Chine, la Région Hauts de France, Spectacle vivant en Bretagne, EU Arts live et Cultures Solution. RDV au Village des professionnels pour suivre la rencontre ! #FocusInternational #OFF19 #PolitiqueCulturelles	Jul 13, 2019	79	3	15.13

Festival Edinburgh Fringe

Metricool has collected 359 posts published by the event organizers from 03/07/2019 to 31/08/2019. Compared to OFF's FB performance, Festival Edinburgh Fringe has a less concentrated curve in terms of reactions (see Figure 2.8.1.2.1.c.). The 4 dates which have gotten the biggest reactions are 19th & 30th in July and 9th & 26th in August. The contents include the countdown two weeks before the festival, a photo of Fringe's energetic employee, an elegant performer's photo and a final report for this edition.

Figure 2.8.1.2.1.c. Social media Performance of Fringe's FB posts

Table 2.8.1.2.1.c. Sum of FB posts, reactions, comments and shares in different steps of festival

	EF.	Post	% Posts	Reactions	% Reactions	Comments	% Comments	Shared	% Shared
Before the festival	D-30~D-16	34	9%	861	5%	39	3%	155	10%
	D-15~D-0	38	11%	6411	38%	275	21%	622	38%
During the festival	D+0~D+8	102	28%	2721	16%	126	10%	300	19%
	D+9~D+16	98	27%	800	5%	91	7%	106	7%
	D+17~D+25	79	22%	5192	31%	730	55%	411	25%
After the festival	D+26~D+30	8	2%	758	5%	55	4%	22	1%
Total		359	100%	16743	100%	1316	100%	1616	100%

At first, because the duration of Edinburgh Fringe has 1 day more compared to Avignon Off, the last one-third part of Fringe has 8+1 days in total. The biggest volume of posts has been published during the festival, which stands for 77% of the sum of posts. In terms of reactions, comments and shared times, there are two peaks in principal: (1) 15 days before the festival until 8 days after the starting date of the festival (54% of reactions, 31% of comments and 57% of shares) and (2) the last 9 days before the end of the festival (31% of reactions, 55% of comments, 25% of shares).

The contents in the top 15 Facebook posts of Edinburgh Fringe concentrate on Emotion (14/30) and Customer Relations (7/30). Most of the FB posts highlighted the emotional side uniquely. Besides, Fringe’s Facebook tended to maintain a good relationship with the participants by reminding the upcoming festival via emotional countdown photos, by highlighting the collective efforts of Fringe’s team to make this edition come true and by sharing the photos of elegant and energetic performers. Besides, on the informative side, Fringe published a video which depicted the process of building up the sites to welcome the audiences. Also, Fringe shared the information about the shows which gave the 2 for 1 discount.

Figure 2.8.1.2.1.d. Content Analysis – Edinburgh Fringe’s top 15 FB posts

Table 2.8.1.2.1.d. Festival Avignon Off: Top 15 FB posts - Engagement Rates

	Post	Date	Reactions	Comments	Shared	Engagement
1	You made it! See you in 2020 🤖 #MakeYourFringe	8/26/2019	3126	125	157	19.41
2	Leaping into the Fringe weekend like...	8/9/2019	1996	63	101	12.45
3	The High Street is starting to look very Fringey indeed! 🤖 #MakeYourFringe	7/30/2019	1849	91	128	12.06
4	Who's excited?	7/19/2019	1363	53	124	9.04
5	Get 2for1 tickets from a choice of 1,000s of shows at this year's Fringe 🎫	7/18/2019	937	18	85	6.11
6	It all begins this Friday! #MakeYourFringe	7/29/2019	790	53	103	5.52
7	That was the 2019 Edinburgh Festival Fringe! #MakeYourFringe	8/26/2019	645	55	176	4.99
8	It's time to #MakeYourFringe 🌟	8/2/2019	354	23	100	2.77
9	Proof that you never know what might #MakeYourFringe 🤖	8/16/2019	349	16	6	2.12
10	Happy #WorldFringeDay! 🌍🤖🤖🤖	7/11/2019	298	8	47	2.08
11	Get a flavour of today's Virgin Money Fringe Street Events as we take a walk along the Fringe's iconic Royal Mile.	8/17/2019	253	39	33	1.86
12	Just one more day left for you to #MakeYourFringe!	8/25/2019	293	23	7	1.84
13	A huge hello from the Fringe Society team who'll be helping to #MakeYourFringe this August 🤖	7/26/2019	292	12	11	1.84
14	The Fringe begins next week! #MakeYourFringe #MondayMotivation	7/22/2019	229	12	22	1.54
15	Three weeks 🤖 #MakeYourFringe	7/12/2019	220	10	26	1.51

2.8.1.2.2. Twitter

Festival Avignon Off

OFF’s Twitter’s performance has a less concentrated distribution than its Facebook, but has roughly a bell shape from the beginning to the end of the festival. The 3 most outstanding periods which obtained the most reactions are (1) 2nd to 5th July (2) 11th to 15th July and (3) 22th to 23th July. Similar to its Facebook, the principal contents of the first peak relate to OFF’s opening parade and the launch of its app. The success of the second peak could partially contribute to a large volume of tweets published, which has occupied 68% of the total tweets (109 out of 160 tweets). The contents of the third peak focus on the beneficiaries for the young locals and the call for participants for the party in the OFF village before the end of the festival (see figure 2.8.1.2.2.a.)

Figure 2.8.1.2.2.a. Social media Performance of OFF’s Tweets

Table 2.8.1.2.2.a. Tweets, likes, retweets in different steps of festival

	AO.	Post	% Posts	Likes	% Likes	Retweets	% Retweets	Likes + Retweets	% (Likes + Retweets)
Before the festival	D-30~D-16	7	4%	17	3%	3	1%	20	2%
	D-15~D-0	14	9%	193	30%	82	20%	275	26%
	D+0~D+8	48	30%	128	20%	107	26%	235	22%
During the festival	D+9~D+16	79	49%	194	30%	165	40%	359	34%
	D+17~D+24	11	7%	99	15%	48	12%	147	14%
After the festival	D+25~D+29	1	1%	19	3%	3	1%	22	2%
Total		160	100%	650	100%	408	100%	1058	100%

According to the Table above, the biggest volume of tweets was published in the first two weeks of the festival, which represents 79% of the total tweets (Table 2.8.1.2.2.a.). 80% likes and 86% of the retweets have occurred the most from two weeks before the festival until the second week of the festival.

Figure 2.8.1.2.2.b. Content Analysis – Avignon Off’s Top 15 Tweets

Twitter of Avignon Off highlighted the informative contents more than its Facebook. According to the author’s research, OFF’s Top 15 Twitter contents are mainly informative (10/28), communicate about the upcoming programs (6/28) and still maintain Customer Relations (5/28). By contrast, OFF’s Twitter conveyed less emotional contents (3/28) to the online audiences and even published some images which may have an emotionally negative effect. OFF’s Twitter functioned more like an interactive F&Q bulletin board, which offered the tool for the online readers to have some practical information and news around the festival.

Table 2.8.1.2.2.b. Festival Avignon Off: Top 15 Tweets - Engagement Rates

	Post	Date	Likes	Retweets	Likes + Retweets
1	La parade d'ouverture du #festival #OFF19 d'Avignon emmenée par la batucada Oumpack 🎉 Merci à eux et aux #artistes du festival pour cette grande fête !	4-Jul-19	28	9	37
2	⚠️ Compagnies, producteurs et théâtres du festival OFF d'Avignon 2019 ⚠️ Suite aux différentes alertes canicule, l'affichage pour le festival #OFF19 débutera le mercredi 3 juillet à 10h (et non à 14h comme précédemment indiqué) !	28-Jun-19	18	19	37
3	Un grand merci à @Anne_Hidalgo pour sa visite au @VillageduOFF. 394 spectacles produits par des structures basées à @Paris soit 25 % des spectacles du #OFF19 Des synergies à mettre en place pour accompagner au mieux les compagnies qui participent au #festival OFF d'Avignon.	17-Jul-19	27	8	35
4	Notre équipe technique travaille d'arrache pied pour que le @VillageduOFF soit prêt à vous accueillir demain à la suite de la #parade d'ouverture du #festival ! Un grand bravo à eux ! J-2 avant le #OFF19 !! @AF&C - @UlyssePicture	3-Jul-19	27	5	32
5	Vous l'attendiez avec impatience, bonne nouvelle, l'application Avignon OFF 2019 est disponible dans les stores (Android et Apple) !!! À vos smartphones, prêts, téléchargez 📲 Encore un grand merci à @nympheastudio pour leur travail !	4-Jul-19	18	11	29
6	Merci au Ministre de la Culture @franckriester pour les échanges avec les jeunes utilisateurs (abonné.e.s du #OFF19) du @pass_Culture ce matin @VillageduOFF Retours d'expérience des jeunes pour améliorer l'application dans les mois à venir @MinistereCC	15-Jul-19	17	9	26
7	Le #festival #OFF19 d'Avignon se poursuit jusqu'au 28 juillet 🎉🎉🎉 Vous avez entre 12 et 25 ans et/ou vous êtes avignonnais ? Nous vous réservons des surprises pour la dernière semaine du festival ! 📣 Attention bons plans dans le tweet qui suit 📣	22-Jul-19	15	8	23
8	Les jeunes du #Vaucluse peuvent utiliser leur @pass_Culture pour s'abonner au #OFF19 et accéder à des moments d'échanges avec les artistes du #festival OFF d'Avignon la semaine prochaine au @VillageduOFF @MinistereCC @franckriester	15-Jul-19	13	10	23
9	Merci ! https://t.co/nXtbNZE30D Préfet de Vaucluse @Prefet84 · Jul 28 Ils n'étaient pas sur scène pendant ces trois semaines de juillet. Grâce à eux aussi, le @FestivalAvignon et le @avignoneoff se sont bien déroulés. Merci à @PoliceNationale (#DDSP84 & #CRS), @armedeterre (#sentinelle), @sdis84 sans oublier effectifs d'@Avignon & @CroixBlanche84	29-Jul-19	19	3	22
10	Les lauréats du concours des plus belles #affiches du festival #OFF19 d'Avignon, organisé par la @laBnF, sur la scène du @VillageduOFF ! @ AF&C - @UlyssePicture	26-Jul-19	16	6	22
11	J-7 avant la #parade d'ouverture du #festival @avignoneoff 2019 🎉🎉 Les compagnies du #OFF19 vous donnent rendez-vous le 4/07 rue Bonneterie pour un moment de fête qui lancera officiellement le festival et vous donnera un aperçu des #artistes présents ! (link: https://urlz.fr/a3sG)	27-Jun-19	13	9	22
12	Le festival continue jusqu'au 28 juillet! Vous artistes, vous (link: http://avignonnais.es) avignonnais.es, vous public, vous êtes (link: http://xn--invit-fsa.es) invité.es à tirer le fil rouge et poursuivre par une fête au Village du OFF 🎉 RDV mardi 23 juillet au Palais des Papes à 22h00 ! Dress code : rouge ! 🍷🎉	22-Jul-19	13	8	21
13	La dame blanche est au Village du OFF pour le bal de clôture du #OFF19 ! Merci à eux et à vous tous pour cette super ambiance	27-Jul-19	17	3	20
14	Soirée de la région @hautsdefrance au @VillageduOFF #OFF19 Un partenariat amorcé en 2018 qui s'est concrétisé par la signature d'une convention.Ce soir, des annonces de soutiens supplémentaires pour la venue des compagnies HDF aux prochaines édition du #festival OFF d'Avignon	11-Jul-19	10	8	18
15	PDJ de presse du jeudi @VillageduOFF Point à J+6 : 1ers chiffres du nombre d'abonnés #OFF19 & de places vendues sur la #billetterie @ticketOFF19 📍 Focus international du 12-14 juillet 📍 Rencontres & ateliers mis en place par nos partenaires Merci aux journalistes présents 🙏	11-Jul-19	12	6	18

Festival Edinburgh Fringe (TW)

Metricool has collected 551 Tweets which generated by Edinburgh Fringe. There is no obvious curve which explains the increasing reactions during the festival. Instead, the peaks which have the best reactions are separated at four different dates: (1) 11th July, (2) 26th July, (3) 2nd August and (4) 26th August.

Figure 2.8.1.2.2.c. Social media Performance of Fringe’s Tweets

According to the table below, the highest volume of tweets was published in the first week of the festival, which stands for 29% of the total tweets (Table 2.8.1.2.2.c.). That is, 20 tweets per day were posted in this short period. Besides, around 56% likes and tweets were given from two weeks before the festival until the first week of the festival.

Table 2.8.1.2.2.c. Tweets, likes, retweets in different steps of festival

	EF	Post	% Posts	Likes	% Likes	Retweets	% Retweets	Likes + Retweets	%(Likes + Retweets)
Before the	D-30~D-16	100	18%	1960	18%	492	21%	2452	18%
	D-15~D-0	112	20%	3017	27%	716	31%	3733	28%
During the festival	D+0~D+8	160	29%	3047	28%	731	31%	3778	28%
	D+9~D+16	79	14%	1068	10%	226	10%	1294	10%
	D+17~D+25	84	15%	1639	15%	155	7%	1794	13%
After the festival	D+26~D+30	16	3%	266	2%	16	1%	282	2%
Total		551	100%	10997	100%	2336	100%	13333	100%

Table 2.8.1.2.2.d. Content Analysis – Edinburgh Fringe’s Top 15 Tweets

Table 2.8.1.2.2.e. Edinburgh Fringe: Top 15 Tweets - Engagement Rates

No.	Post	Date	Likes	Retweets	Likes + Retweets
1	Whisper it quietly... It's day one of the Fringe 🐼 #MakeYourFringe #edfringe	8/2/2019	1066	234	1300
2	You made it! 🐼 Thank you for being a part of the 2019 Edinburgh Festival Fringe! 🐼 #MakeYourFringe #edfringe https://t.co/nEoKmpBxS7	8/26/2019	567	127	694
3	You made it! See you in 2020 🐼 #MakeYourFringe #edfringe https://t.co/jiPFJZj4Te	8/26/2019	404	78	482
4	A huge hello from the Fringe Society team who'll be helping to #MakeYourFringe this August 🐼 #edfringe https://t.co/n4uHh87vg2	7/26/2019	389	37	426
5	Happy #WorldFringeDay! 🐼🐼🐼 #MakeYourFringe #edfringe https://t.co/6XfVKKDsKv	7/11/2019	330	87	417
6	The Fringe is an arts festival 🐼🐼 Be kind to each other 🐼 It's the best way to # MakeYourFringe 🐼 https://t.co/WDbYRlLdaO	8/4/2019	328	70	398
7	Are you ready to #MakeYourFringe? It's easy to get started 🐼 https://t.co/uNeW9o9mXY #FridayThoughts... https://t.co/9TWOdJaOXM	7/26/2019	265	106	371
8	The stage is set. It's time to #MakeYourFringe! 🐼🐼 https://t.co/ia2nE9XsCh	8/2/2019	217	68	285
9	It's 0:00 UK time and #WorldFringeDay 2019 has now begun in Edinburgh! 🐼 Today we celebrate openness and freedom... https://t.co/FxhuMcwEVI	7/11/2019	211	72	283
10	Happy Fringe Eve Eve Eve! #MakeYourFringe #edfringe https://t.co/9D62NgT4rw	7/30/2019	206	42	248
11	It all begins this Friday! 🐼 #MakeYourFringe #MondayMotivation #edfringe https://t.co/nVTyf8KPrS	7/29/2019	203	43	246
12	Fancy 2for1 tickets from a choice of 1,000s of shows at this year's Fringe? 🐼 Here's how you can get your hands o... https://t.co/VDYKDixN6y	7/18/2019	157	78	235
13	We're incredibly excited to announce that the Fringe has been unveiled by @lonelyplanet as the number one travel ex... https://t.co/PrA03K4AmV	8/13/2019	183	44	227
14	Pippin can't wait to get stuck in to a day at the Fringe 🐼 #DogsAtTheFringe #MakeYourFringe #edfringe https://t.co/rmb4tfqxgT	8/11/2019	206	9	215
15	Who's excited? #MakeYourFringe #edfringe https://t.co/gKZ8e9Aafj	7/19/2019	170	38	208

2.8.1.3. Social Blade

Festival Avignon Off

Figure 2.9.1.3.a.

Figure 2.9.1.3.b.

Festival Edinburgh Fringe

Figure 2.9.1.3.c.

Figure 2.9.1.3.d.

2.8.2. Quantitative Data — Offline Communication

The goals are (1) to verify the flyers' contents in the two festivals based on the 27 variables — email, website, social media, youtube, summary, words of summary, press (quotation), number of press, QR code, local phone number, corporate phone number, other phone number, author, director, performer(s), dates, time, price, duration, location, percentage of illustration, award(s), marketing label, anniversary, new creation, festival

logo and discount — and (2) to see whether the current flyers are ready to be transformed directly into the digital form on their social media.

The author has been successful to collect 458 flyers in Avignon Off in the size of B5 and 323 flyers in the size of mostly A5 and B5 in Edinburgh Fringe. Most of the flyers in both festivals do provide the general information. The flyers in Avignon Off have location and time (100%), story summary (95%), dates (91%), performers (84%), authors (77%), directors (71%), local phone (69%) and website (66%), which allow the potential audiences to know the general information, to be attracted by the emerging or well-known casts, authors or directors and finally to book the tickets with the phone call or with the URL. Edinburgh Fringe has the similar figures in terms of location, time, summary and dates, but Edinburgh’s flyers mentioned about website around 15% more than Avignon Off. That is, the public in Edinburgh might have a bigger chance to use the website to book their tickets or to do any further actions in their festival experiences.

One of the main differences between the two festivals is that the flyers of Avignon Off highlighted more about the performers, authors and directors than the ones of Edinburgh Fringe. In Edinburgh Fringe, sometimes the performing team was replaced by the name of the production company and the theatre. Another main difference is that the flyers in Edinburgh Fringe mentioned the social media references, such as social media logos,

three times more than the ones in Avignon Off. By consequence, the author could assume that the public in Edinburgh has a relatively lower barrier to take actions on their social media for the show.

In terms of the similarity between the flyers in the two festivals, more than half of the flyers did add the remarks or reviews from the press, which gives the short testimony and the taste of the shows to the readers. By putting the press remarks on the flyers, the shows will have more credibility and added value to the potential audiences. Besides, neither the flyers in OFF nor the ones in Fringe include frequently the marketing labels, such as “Success in OFF 2018,” and the awards obtained. In this way, the shows lost the powerful weapons to highlight their unique proposition and differentiate them with others.

To be outstanding in more than thousands of shows, the face-to-face contact with the support of flyers plays an important role to attract more potential audiences to come into the performing spaces and have a seat. The more the emotional value and the higher credibility a flyer could bring, the more quickly the ticket will be sold out. Because the

emotional value is truly hard to judge, the author assumes that the bigger the visual percentage of the flyers at the front page, the bigger chance that the show will catch the eyes of flyer receivers. Based on the flyers which the author collected, the performing groups in both festivals did make the front page of flyers truly visualized. The flyers in Avignon Off tended to have at least 70% of the visual; while the flyers in Edinburgh Fringe had 85% to 90% of the visual contents.

2.8.3. Qualitative Data — Stakeholders’ Perceptions

After completing both the field trips to Avignon and Edinburgh, for Festival Avignon Off, the author has successfully conducted 13 semi-structured interviews with 17 national and international spectators, 3 artists and 8 professionals (Table 2.9.3.a.); for Festival Edinburgh Fringe, the author has successfully conducted as well 13 semi-structured interviews with 11 national and international spectators, 3 artists and 1 professional (Table 2.9.3.b.). All the interviews are executed by the author with a voice recorder. To avoid any data privacy dispute, all the interviewees’ names were replaced with their roles in the festival and the ordinal number.

In the next section, the author will summarize and characterize the different social media perceptions and uses for (A) the spectators, (B) the artists and (C) the professionals, which are the three main stakeholders in the festivals, to present a panorama in the social media landscape both in Festival Avignon Off and in Festival Edinburgh Fringe in 2019.

Table 2.9.3.a. Interviewees in Festival Avignon Off

Code	Length	Interviewee	Nation	Gender	Age	Note
AA-1.	03:59	Spectator 1	France	Female	55/60	Couple
		Spectator 2	France	Male	55/60	
AA-2.	02:31	Spectator 3	France	Male	60	Friends
		Spectator 4	France	Male	60	
		Spectator 5	France	Male	60	
AA-3.	03:56	Spectator 6	Taiwan	Female	30/40	Tourists of south of France

		Spectator 7	Taiwan	Female	30/40	
AA-4.	05:20	Spectator 8	France	Female	25/30	Close friends
		Spectator 9	France	Female	25/30	
		Spectator 10	France	Female	25/30	
		Spectator 11	France	Male	25/30	
		Spectator 12	France	Male	25/30	
AA-5.	03:07	Spectator 13	France	Female	25/28	Close friends from Alsace
		Spectator 14	France	Female	25/28	
AA-6.	02:01	Spectator 15	France	Female	55/60	Tourists from area around
		Spectator 16	France	Female	55/60	
AA-7.	08:57	Spectator 17	France	Female	18	Local
BA-1.	04:41	Artist 1	France	Male	35/40	Comedy actor from Paris
CA-1.	07:43	Artist 2	France	Male	30/35	Comedy actor
		Artist 3	France	Male	35/40	Comedy actor
		Professional 1	France	Male	45/50	Show producer
		Professional 2	France	Female	30	Team member
CA-2.	06:14	Professional 3	France	Male	50/55	Director of a crowdfunding / sponsoring platform
		Professional 4	France	Female	30	Project assistant of a crowdfunding / sponsoring platform
CA-3.	10:29	Professional 5	France	Male	55	Show Producer
		Professional 6	France	Male	65/70	Show diffuser
CA-4.	02:57	Professional 7	France	Male	30	Stage Manager at Avignon Off Village from Montpellier
CA-5.	05:39	Professional 8	France	Male	36	Youtuber in film industry, local

Table 2.9.3.b. Interviewees in Festival Edinburgh Fringe

Code	Length	Interviewee	Nation	Gender	Age	Note
AE-1.	08:11	Spectator 1	The UK	Male	60/70	Couple from Manchester
		Spectator 2	The UK	Female	60/70	
AE-2.	05:56	Spectator 3	The UK	Female	15/20	Mother and daughters from Glasgow
		Spectator 4	The UK	Female	55	
		Spectator 5	The UK	Female	15/20	
AE-3.	02:58	Spectator 6	The UK	Female	25/30	Twins from Yorkshire
		Spectator 7	The UK	Female	25/30	

AE-4.	04:23	Spectator 8	Japan	Male	55/60	Edinburgh long-term resident from Niigata
AE-5.	09:17	Spectator 9	The UK	Female	55/60	Primary school teacher from Manchester
AE-6.	03:58	Spectator 10	The UK	Female	25/30	Visitor from Ireland
AE-7.	5 mins	Spectator 11	The UK	Male	75/80	Local
AE-8.	10:04	Spectator 12	The UK	Male	55	Visitor from Manchester / London
AE-9.	15:43	Spectator 13	The UK	Female	24	Visitor from Dublin
BE-1.	05:14	Artist 1	The UK	Female	50	
BE-2.	09:11	Artist 2	The UK	Female	30	Artist from Hull
BE-3.	03:59	Artist 3	The UK	Female	45	
CE-1.	07:05	Professional 1	Malaysia	Female	25/30	Public Relations for dance group

2.8.3.1. Festival Avignon Off 2019

Spectators

The blurring line between Festival Avignon Off and Festival Avignon

In the main street of Festival Avignon Off, it was hard to tell the clear distinction between Festival Avignon IN and OFF. All the flags flying along the main street were marked “Festival d’Avignon,” and the participants, especially newcomers, could not easily tell whether the posters everywhere were in the system OFF or not.

The major and targeted participants of Avignon Off are 40+ years old tourists from the French speaking area but mainly from Paris

According to a young local interviewee, who have regularly participated in Festival Avignon Off, she claimed that the average age of the spectators was around forty years old, and that the young public could not easily afford the expenses even with a reduction card. The participants are mainly tourists from the French-speaking countries. And most of the tourists are from Paris due to Avignon’s high reputation in theatre.

The resisting, traditional position of Festival Avignon Off

No matter for a newcomer or a patron, no matter for the young or the old, social media in Avignon Off is not wildly used. They prefer to take a huge book of the program and to interact with the leafleteers to do their selections. The spectators could enjoy the pop-up performances made by the performers during their lunch time and appreciate the free performance in the streets.

For the respondents who are more than 50 years old, they claimed that the social media is more for the young people, not for them. Yet, even for the young participants, they confirmed that the spirit of Avignon is truly to have the traditional face-to-face exchanges, and that they prepare for their trip based on their previous experiences and word-of-mouth from their families or friends rather than use social media.

General but not efficient

Some spectators claimed that it might be difficult to have an efficient social media because the information is too fragmented, especially when you have more than 1000 shows to present. For the young spectators, they do not learn so much from the official social media but directly go to the website to get the necessary information. Even if currently the spectators do not use the application and social media of Avignon Off, they confirmed their interest and positive attitude in the social media and in the app if it's helpful in the festival experiences, including searching for the ideal shows, showing the whole program, booking the tickets and showing the reviews.

The perception of the social media contents is strongly limited in the promotional and informative usages

In terms of the potential uses of social media, most of my respondents answered that social media could be used to read the program and posts and share the photos. They tend to use social media to collect information but not make any reaction. None of them

started to talk about the possibility to have an immersive festival experience thanks to social media.

The language, French, a barrier for non-French-speakers on social media

In terms of language, social media of Avignon Off is not convenient for the international non-French-speakers. All the contents on OFF's social media were in French. They reluctant to enter theaters easily because of the fear of knowing nothing after sitting for a few hours.

Artists

Critical and strategic, an extended stage to attract more potential audiences

Social media is not only an informative platform but a contact point to build up a closer relationship between artists and online audiences and to call for further actions. For example, Artiste 1 confirmed to me that especially Instagram became an important communication channel for her to deepen the impression of the public and to encourage the online public to buy tickets. She posted a lot of small, funny videos and photos to keep in touch with her online audiences continually, to do the promotion and to develop the strategic communication. For example, artists could use the fact that they engage in Avignon Off as a great reference to communicate with her online public in Paris.

A social listening tool

An artist highlighted the importance of getting feedback from the spectators and visitors on the social media, which allows him to do more targeted communication with the specific groups earlier before the opening of festival Avignon Off.

Better this year but shall develop even faster to catch up

According to Artiste 1, it's necessary for Festival Avignon Off to develop its social media because all the people have the smartphones now. The usage of the hashtag "Avignon Off 2019" and high emotional contents, such as opening, parade and posters, helped a lot in terms of visibility and made OFF's social media this year more performative than before, but Avignon Off still had a big room to progress in terms of social media compared to other festivals.

An open but medium position towards the social media

For Artist 1, it's possible to use live Facebook to make a short video to attract the attention of the online audiences, but making videos for more than 5 minutes might not be acceptable. Besides, integrating videos on social media as a part of creation is perceived to be too risky. Once a bad video is spread on social media, the artist career might end up.

A catalyst among the stakeholders

Even if Village Off was released in 2019, there was still a big distance between the stakeholders. Social media, app and special events might become the bridge to stimulate the interactions and exchanges among them.

Professionals - Producers

A useful communication tool for the shows but not a part of art creation

According to a producer assistant, social media has two main functions: communication and targeted advertisement. The producer stated that it's necessary to use social media as a communication way to do the promotion, to share all the practical information, to talk about the artists, contents, experiences and show structure. Social media is around the public, which has the function like the blog and shares the pertinent articles, images,

contents and the press release. By doing the targeted advertisement, the producers could know better about the statistics and how people react to the contents. As well, the producers could figure out the communication plan which corresponds to its targets. Yet, producers believe that the live show shall stay in the room. It's fine to do the short live Facebook to do the promotion but not to involve in the art creation.

Have a more useful social media and app

The producer expected that one day festival's app and social media could facilitate the spectators to find their ideal shows easily.

The balance between the offline and digital communication

Spectators could view the catalog, reserve the tickets and give their comments on the two digital sites, "Ticket Off" and "To See Or Not To See", which dedicate to e-word-of-mouth. The producer claimed that because too much information is posted every day on social media, it's hard to provide the target audiences with specific contents. The promotion on the floor, the traditional word-of-mouth, has a great impact on the show promotion. The face-to-face contact is also the essence of Avignon OFF.

Relatively weak exchanges between professionals and professionals, or between spectators and spectators

Yes, there are lots of opportunity to have exchanges between spectators and artists, but there are not so many events which may enrich the overall experiences. According to one respondent, as a member of a production company, she hoped to have more events where she could do the networking with other professionals. Another respondent also mentioned his wish to meet with new person during the festival.

Professionals - Project financing company

Offline and online communication are equally important.

To illustrate, the big book (catalog) of Avignon Off gives a lot of information, but the social media allows the people to mobilize. Social media is a modern way to increase the impression for the information, especially visualized ones.

The functions of social media

Firstly, social media, a tool allows artists to talk with its community. Secondly, social media allows the event organizer to share the contents of its events. Thirdly, social media allows the institution or organization to communicate with the news, some small stories. To create a more immersive experience, it's better to present more reviews and analysis from others for the shows. The ideal solution might be to create a map to know about the detail information during the festival quickly (what, when, the five stars show which will start in 1 hour)

2.8.3.2. Festival Edinburgh Fringe 2019

Usage of Twitter

Professionals and artists seem to use more Twitter. Young spectators are quite often on Twitter and tend to get used to the quick rhythm and the high volume of tweets. Some spectators only read the tweets without taking any further action. Spectators use Twitter for conversation, read the reviews and obtain the practical festival information. Active spectators tend to share the show information before the show and publish the reviews on their social media. The PR officer of Theatre stated that their Twitter's contents are mainly about the show information, critics and audiences' reviews, and that the social media mainstream in Fringe is more Twitter than any other platform.

Usage of Facebook

Spectators use Facebook to read, to get information and to contact with their close contacts. Facebook was perceived to be used more by the elder people. Posting frequently on Facebook might disturb the young spectators; on the other side, posting too less might make them feel bored and dull. The middle-aged people tend to launch their political debates on Facebook.

Use of Youtube

For the artist interviewees, using Youtube, a video sharing website, to do show promotion is not preferable because creating video contents takes so much time compared to posting promotional photos on Instagram.

Use of Instagram

Spectators post nice pictures and stories on Instagram. The PR officer pointed out that their Instagram's contents are more informal, such as photos, stories and photos behind-the-scenes. The artist interviewee indicated the importance of visualized messages for attracting younger audiences on Instagram.

Preparing for Arrival in Edinburgh

The PR officer revealed that her team started to promote the show with videos and related information one month, two months before their arrival in Edinburgh.

One artist did promote her show with her personal social media accounts, and her team created a brand-new Instagram page for her show two weeks before the performance. Another artist indicated her team has posted a lot to promote their arrival in Fringe in the last three months before the festival. The other artist said that her team used social media to inform and stimulate the people to see the shows.

Some spectators use Twitter only to read the reviews, but the young spectators use social media to track the comedians, to obtain their guides, to select the shows and to know the locations, activities and other festival tips. The audiences' goal is to verify the popularity and the quality of the performances. What's more, the spectators also tend to use Messenger, Facebook or Whatsapp to organize their trips with their friends.

Fringe's Social Media

Role: The artists and the PR officer confirmed that Edinburgh Fringe did not utilize its social media to help to promote their shows, but they could understand the difficulty to promote more than 4,000 performing groups in three weeks. The main contents on the official accounts are more formal and general around the festival news and the to-do-list.

Perspective: One artist expects to have some small summaries about the casts, company and critics of her show on Fringe's social media. The other artist suggested Fringe could make good use of numerous festival photos, posters and banners as visual contents on Instagram.

The first improvement came to a spectator's minds was to access the performers' links directly from Fringe's social media. Because Fringe's social media has such a huge amount of information, the enhanced informative connections might help especially the newcomers a lot. Furthermore, another spectator suggested to have the information directly from Fringe's tweets rather than merely have an URL so she could have a stronger immersive feeling in her festival experience.

Besides, the spectator also expects to have a more transparent ticket sales system for having a comfortable audience size and to have more information about free shows, review podcasts, directions, event information and reviews via social media, sometimes with Live.

Social Media & Live Performance

The PR officer claimed that mostly the performers use the social media to empower the audiences to change the final results of the show.

One artist said that live show is essential but she couldn't deny that some audiences love to have some "warm-ups" before the show. Another artist stated that instead of seeing publishing videos on social media as a threat for her career, she believed and appreciated that she may have smaller but "more useful and more engaged audiences" owe to the support from social media. The other artist pointed out that she has seen some techniques to let the audiences engage more in the show, but she could not use them in her show easily.

Most of the spectators claim that once the social media could make them more engaged in the live shows, they are interested in trying this new hybrid mixture of social media and live performance. A multimedia immersive experience is highly welcomed especially by the young people. Another young spectator claimed that if the live show is partially online, she will have higher interests to buy the tickets. In addition, the small materials on social media are expected to give the flavors of shows, which could help them make better decisions in choosing the shows.

Social media & Promotion

Managing social media is a must for an artist nowadays. Even if a performer in Fringe tried not to use it, her team and the venue people pushed her to work on it for obtaining the younger audiences. As she claimed " , it seems to be able to galvanize audiences in some way."

A spectator said that it's nicer if she could have more offline interactions with the performers, which will benefit to the comedians as well due to the word of mouth.

Word-of-Mouth

E-word of mouth: Most of the spectators search for reviews while using Twitter during the festival. Some tend to select the shows and wait for the endorsement from their online friends. One spectator searched for personal recommendations from her former colleague to capture the "buzzes".

Word-of-mouth: a spectator got some personal recommendations from leafleteers.

Fringe's Unique Values

Most of the interviewees travelled to Edinburgh for Edinburgh Fringe out of their passion towards theatre. Atmosphere, human touch, performer's growth and meeting with celebrities are the main values in Edinburgh Fringe from the spectator's perspective. Spectators stated that they loved Fringe's atmosphere and enjoyed a lot to talk with the random leafleteers in the streets, which could not be replaced by the well-calculated, highly homogeneous social media contents. Another spectator mentioned that Edinburgh Fringe allowed her to witness the progress of the comedians year by year. The other spectator showed her excitement while mentioning that Edinburgh was a place where she could meet all the people she has followed on Twitter in her real life.

Communication

Some spectators preferred to carry the thick catalog and to explore in the streets. A spectator claimed that he preferred to use the app rather than the heavy book. Yet, In the app, there is no access to know what's going on now but only the list of shows. Another spectator thinks that there are so many flyers anyway so she will not read them if they are not attractive enough.

Spectators – (17 - 27.5 yr old, 6 people, Spectator 3, 5, 6, 7, 10, 13)

About the social media use in their daily life, the most favorite to the least favorite platforms are Twitter & Instagram, Facebook and Youtube. Both Twitter and Instagram get 83.3% mentioned rate from all the spectators, and half of them claimed that they use them “mostly” in general. A spectator uses Instagram mostly during the holidays. Using Facebook is perceived as the elder users (Spectator 13). Even if Facebook is mentioned by two-third of the spectators, they claimed that they “slightly” or even only use it for study purposes. Another point is that Youtube has only one mention but is considered as one of her favorite social media, where she mostly consumes the contents made by the Youtubers she follows without creating the video contents herself (Spectator 13).

The second aspect is to see how the spectators use the social media to prepare for their trips. The three most frequent uses, which get 3 times mention for each, are (1) to update what people they follow do this year, (2) to search for recommendations from the reliable sources, such as comedians and former colleagues and (3) to get the reviews. Firstly, Edinburgh Fringe is an opportunity for the spectators to see their dream comedians and popular people appearing in front of their eyes and even to have closer interactions with them in the shows or in the streets. The revelation of artists’ schedule or events on social media allows spectators to have wonderful and intimate face-to-face experiences with them. Secondly, to have a great experience under the premise of limited time and money, the spectators tend to search for the performance guidelines from the two types of sources: (1) public figures, especially their beloved comedians, and (2) their friends who have a certain knowledge about the theatre. Here, the author could see the potential of exploiting the uses of comedian’s guidelines in social media due to the trust between the comedians and their followers. Thirdly, Fringe’s Twitter is widely used and recognized as a useful tool for its efficiency to get the necessary information, such as where to go, things to do, reviews and different things which spectators wouldn’t have seen normally. By applying the hashtag searching strategy (“edfringe” and “Edinburgh Fringe”), the spectators could find the latest information and what people are doing in a few minutes (Spectator 10). Lots of published reviews become a reliable source for the audiences to

conduct their show selections. A spectator highlights checking the reviews is what she does on the social media mostly to identify the “buzz” which truly has a nice quality (Spectator 10).

Despite that the physical offline communication and face-to-face contacts no matter in the streets or in the shows are still Fringe’s essential part with so much energy and emotions, social media potentially gives the audiences supplementary information and helps them to recognize who the popular and great comedians are, which makes their festival experiences even stronger. Without surprise, a spectator enjoys a lot to walk around and take some flyers with her Fringe catalog in the festival. Even if sometimes the flyers do not communicate enough, she doesn’t think that scanning a QR code on a poster is nicer than the traditional communication way in Edinburgh (Spectator 13). Yet, the social media contents potentially enrich the emotions and atmosphere. If you don’t have enough knowledge about the famous performers standing upon you, how could you be touched by this incredible meeting? Once, a well-known actor approached my interviewee and me for promoting his show, my interviewee suddenly recognized him and claimed that she has followed his social media accounts, and that she was so excited and honored to see him there (Spectator 7).

Either for social media communication or its integration into art pieces, the goal may not be to totally replace the offline communication or live performance, but using the social media as a way to catch more attention compared to the others’ thousands of shows. Spectator 10 confirmed with me that the overwhelming quantity of flyers persuades her easily not to read them at all if they’re not attractive enough. In case of being neglected by the potential audiences, social media might be positioned as a compatible and complementary way to convey the key messages related to the shows.

Although the 100% show presented on social media is strongly refused by spectators, the hybrid form of art creation, less than half digital and more than half live, is perceived to

provide a more immersive and interesting experience. The spectators here come for a “live” experience rather than “watching another screen” (Spectator 7). The spectator has a positive attitude towards the integration of social media in arts if it helps her have initial ideas before starting the shows (Spectator 3 & 10). What’s more, Spectator 3 is very fascinated by the potential interactions and more “involved” experiences led by social media.

The highly-integrated social media experience is recognized as a future step for further improvement. She argued that most of the time, the Fringe’s tweets compose of “click to find out more” with a link below. The back and forth on the Twitter decreased her immersive experience. She suggested that Fringe could make shorter tweets and directly give the key messages (Spectator 13). Besides, the second improvement is to publish some short key reminders to facilitate the audiences’ journeys, such as event dates and locations, especially by Live, which might be a great option but depend on whether the spokesman is “entertaining” enough (Spectator 13). What’s more, if Fringe truly wants to integrate more the digital approach into the audiences’ experiences, the free and accessible wi-fi is indispensable to make the success. A spectator argued that she could not paid the roaming here to use her social media freely during the festival (Spectator 13).

In terms of the show selection, it’s hard and frustrating sometimes for the spectators to find out the shows which correspond to their wishes. Even if there are offline flyers, posters and Fringe’s social media, the contents are sometimes insufficient to make the suitable selections. Spectator 3 stated that the catalog readers just bet on the shows’ titles. The following figure represents a hard time of the show selection based on a true-life experience of one of the interviewees.

Spectators - (55-57.5 yr old, 4 people, Spectator 4, 8, 9, 12)

In terms of social media uses in usual, the spectators tend to use Facebook (mentioned 4 times), Instagram (mentioned 2 times) and Twitter (mentioned 1 time). One of them is active to use social media. In general, the spectators tend to read the status updates, get the information and participate in political debates on Facebook.

The low Facebook engagement during the festival might reveal the necessity to create the value-added contents mainly for the middle-aged group, which uses Facebook quite often. With regard to preparation for coming to Edinburgh, they tend to use the big catalog or other offline publications, such as newspaper. Spectator 4 even told me genuinely that she “loves” the catalog, please keep it continuing. Yet, their suspicious attitudes towards social media somehow lower their willingness to use social media as much as the youths. According to Spectator 8, he didn’t trust social media so much due to the fake news so he tried not to read the social media posts too much. Spectator 4 even indicated that she doesn’t need the social media for Fringe. What’s more, Spectator 12

stated that he enjoyed getting “surprised” by leafleteers rather than getting information from social media.

Related to the social media integration in art creation, the insistence on keeping the live show is quite similar to the youth group. But again, they could accept the interference of the social media if the support on it could make them more “engaged” (Spectator 4). They also think that sometimes the shows are too difficult to understand. If they could have some “flavors” before the shows, even in the streets, they surely took less risk to have something they don’t want. Besides, the spectator proposed to do this in the form of podcast so it’s more acceptable than videos for this group.

About the show selection, they tend to do it with the offline publications or with the traditional word-of-mouth. Spectator 8 shared with me that he has adjusted his show selections every day according to the flyers and the reviews based on the credible newspaper, *The Scotsman*, during the three weeks, while Spectator 12 does his selection according to word-of-mouth from the leafleteers and from his friends.

Lack of understanding about how to get the necessary from the huge amount of data on Fringe’s Twitter, the spectator prefers to directly visit the comedian’s websites which. Spectator 9, the only Twitter user in this group, found that Fringe’s Twitter is quite useful and easy to find the information. Yet, due to the overwhelming tweets on the platform, she always goes to the comedians’ social media as an information filter. She argued to have more comedian links directly on Fringe’s Twitter in addition to the poster and venue info.

Chapter 3. Findings and Discussions

- 1) Overall, the social media contents of both Edinburgh Fringe and Avignon Off are more emotional, informative but lack of “Stimulation” and “Program.” That is, at first, Fringe and OFF did not use the social media to truly stimulate the audiences to participate in the events or the shows by their official accounts. Even if having so many powerful photos and elements to enhance the customers’ experiences and also to help the artists to promote their shows, the social media of Fringe and OFF did not have an active role. That is to say, the audiences could not find the links or the information about the shows directly at the official festival accounts but could find some emotional photos and practical information about the venues.
- 2) Fringe’s online audiences are more diverse and international. The social media posts which have mentioned “Avignon OFF” are mainly from Avignon and Paris; however, the posts mentioning “Edinburgh Fringe” are more diverse and mainly from different regions in the UK.
- 3) The traditional communication still plays a leading role in both festivals. According to the interviews conducted by the author, most of the interviewees love to interact with the leafleteers in the streets for not only knowing more about the show but also having some practical information and some reviews about the shows. In Avignon Off, the performers wore the remarkable costumes and interacted with the visitors during the lunch time happily and energetically to promote their shows. Even some of the performing groups played a short version of their shows directly in the streets to catch the potential audiences’ eyes. This face-to-face communication by giving the free samples of their shows is quite efficient for the visitors. According to two Taiwanese tourists, because they could not speak French at all, they firstly wandered in the streets and had a look on all the free performances to help them make their show selection wisely. Yet, in Edinburgh, the atmosphere was totally different. Most of the leafleteers in the Fringe simply gave the practical information for the shows without truly acting or interacting with the visitors passionately. According to one

interviewee, she, from Manchester, hoped to have more interactions with the leafleteers to have more unforgettable experiences. She believed that if the leafleteers in Edinburgh had a more vivid approach which could entertain the visitors, the word-of-mouth effect would definitely help the ticket sales.

- 4) Concerning the flyers in both Avignon and Edinburgh, not so many flyers did have enough elements to differentiate themselves from the others, such as web references, social media references, awards or marketing labels. Yet, the percentage that Fringe's flyers mentioned the social media, such as Facebook logo, is three times more than OFF's percentage, which might indicate the essential difference in terms of social media roles in the two festivals.
- 5) In terms of the textual length on social media, OFF's posts are generally too long compared to Fringe's posts. Based on the top 15 posts, OFF's average characters per post are 304 characters for Facebook, 245 characters for Twitter; while Fringe has 54 characters for Facebook and 109 for Twitter.
- 6) It's worth mentioning that both Fringe and OFF did not use a lot Instagram and Youtube but merely focused on either Twitter or Facebook. Nowadays, the young people like generation Y or Z tend to receive the information in the audio-visual form. Instagram is the social media which focuses on visuals the most. With such a low quantity and engagement on Instagram, OFF and Fringe might have difficulty to pass festival-oriented messages to the young public. Especially, lots of the young people currently stop using Facebook but using more Twitter, Instagram and Youtube. According to the interviews in Edinburgh, a performer pointed out that the first thing that Fringe shall improve in social media is its Instagram account. Fringe had enormous resources and elements to further promote the festival, but it didn't do valorize them. Another interviewee said that maybe Fringe could use Instagram's stories to indicate some venue information to help the newcomers enjoy their stays.

- 7) Social media is useful to attract more younger audiences to join the festivals, and also enrich the participants' festival experiences. Yet, social media in Avignon was not generally used by the public based on the interviews. Even the young people they preferred to keep the same traditional, classical position for Avignon Off rather than highlight the social media role in the festival. According to one interviewee, she claimed that meeting people in the streets is the spirit of Avignon Off. Then, in Edinburgh, the public was more open-minded to the social media during the festival and truly used it as a tool to search for the reviews, practical information and the potential opportunity to enjoy the great moments with their companions.
- 8) In terms of the acceptance of having a half-digitalized and half-live show, the public in Edinburgh has a much higher acceptance than the public in Avignon. In Avignon, only one respondent in more than 10 interviews gave the author a positive answer. The rest of the interviewees they preferred to have the shows from the beginning to the end in the venues. On the opposite side, the public in Edinburgh did have confusion about this new form in the beginning, but when they understood that it's a mixture of digital and live experiences, most of them accepted the idea. Even some of them said that they could expect to have a more immersive experience thanks to this new approach, and that if there is any mention about the show is presented partially in the digital form, it will be more attractive for sure.
- 9) It's quite hard to have an immersive festival experience in OFF and Fringe in 2019 edition because visitors, especially newcomers, may not know where to find the key information, and because the information on social media is quite fragmented.

3.1. Roles of Social Media

3.1.1. Advertising

- Both of the festivals relied a lot on the offline communication, the flyers. In terms of the information on them, the significant difference between Avignon Off and

Edinburgh Fringe is that Fringe's flyers tend to show the social media references more often than OFF's ones. With regard to the visualization of the front page, Edinburgh Fringe has a higher proportion compared to Avignon Off. Shows in Avignon Off tend to highlight their shows with casts and directors. Both festivals have a low proportion to mention the discount, the marketing labels and prizes won by the shows.

- Most of the participants like the big catalogs to do their show selections.

3.1.2. Marketing & Promotion

- In Avignon Off, the great festival atmosphere has been in the streets. Performers interact with the people and present a part of the shows; while in Edinburgh Fringe, the leafleteers sometimes work like a nice robot without vivid performances.
- Both are old cities with all the wonderful buildings.
- More organized in Edinburgh Fringe, for example, the way of sticking posters on the walls and the organization of open air performing sites
- Giving flyers in the streets is the main technique to promote shows.
- More comedians in Avignon Off gave a small part of their shows directly in the streets for free. After the "free samples," the comedians handed out their flyers to the audiences and invited them to come; while there were not so many promotional, short performances in Edinburgh Fringe. The street performances in Fringe were too organized that they were not as flowering as OFF's ones.
- In both festivals, the traditional press still plays a leading role in social media due to their high credibility and enormous follower base.
- Compared to the bustling streets in Avignon Off, Edinburgh Fringe had a quieter atmosphere in public and a great feeling in the theaters still.
- Even for young local audiences in Avignon, she claimed that she preferred that Festival Avignon Off kept the current traditional communication than had a more modern, digital approach.

- The potential of social media shall be in the direction of giving an immersive experience for the festivalgoers. The participants could interact with others, have a nice welcome package, have an app to make new friends or find the others who share the same taste with them easily.
- During the preparation phase before the festivals, the festival event organizers could start to build up some strong online communities which target mainly to two generations (young and the middle-aged).
- During the festivals, the participants could have a few centralized social media pages which not only respond to most of the needs, such as updating the news about the artists, having the attractive event reminders and the reviews from the others, but also give the emotional touches to make the potential online audiences “dream” about the festival. Think about the model of Trip Advisor which provides the users an easy but immersive way to have multi-level information around attractions, gastronomy, reviews, articles and recommendation lists.
- The artists in Edinburgh claimed that they were pushed by the production team and the venue to promote their shows in social media, even if some of them prefer not to do so.

3.1.3. Community Management & Word of Mouth Marketing

Figure 3.3.a. Awario – Mentions A.O.

Figure 3.3.b. Awario – Mentions E.F.

- (Figure 3.3.a.) High quantity of mentions of Avignon Off tends to concentrate during the festival. The mentions in the Facebook and Twitter are more significant than Youtube and Instagram.

- The total mentions of Avignon Off are lower than the ones of Edinburgh Fringe, but the structure of Avignon Off has a more balanced quantity from both Facebook and Twitter, while the structure of Edinburgh Fringe relies more on Twitter alone.

Figure 3.3.c. Awario – Reach A.O.

Figure 3.3.d. Awario – Reach E.F.

- It's not evident that the “phygital” approach is nicely implemented and integrated in both festivals.
- On their official accounts, Fringe’s online conversations started much earlier and also ended up earlier than OFF’s ones.
- Both Avignon Off and Edinburgh Fringe do not have an integrated and interactive platform which permits festivalgoers to make reviews or engage in social activities.
- Although there were lots of events, Avignon Off did not hold the networking events enough to stimulate the meeting of the participants, especially for the professionals.
- The participants in Avignon Off neither followed the official accounts of the festival nor used the app to do any preparation for their coming.
- Compared to Avignon Off, Edinburgh Fringe has a more digital-minded, international audiences. Most of Fringe’s interviewees said that they were quite satisfied already about the social media and the app.
- While analyzing the mentions by city, the posts from Paris have a significant power in terms of communication for Avignon Off, while the ones from London have the biggest voice in Edinburgh Fringe.

3.1.4. Customer-oriented Information

- The lack of emotions and stimulation conveyed by the official festival accounts might decrease visitors' willingness to utilize the social media during the festivals.
- Both the official accounts of Avignon Off and Edinburgh Fringe do not promote the shows, the performers or the directors directly on their social media, which might be a reason that the social media use is limited to check the updates and reviews.
- Give more reminders for the users: a spectator claimed that it's quite confusing for the newcomers to find the right directions due to lots of venues in the festival even if there are signs everywhere.

3.1.5. Art and creations

- The attitude towards integrating social media into art creation in Edinburgh Fringe is more open than the one in Avignon Off. Most of the interviewees in Avignon Off rejected this concept.
- The interviewees who agreed on this concept preferred to have the short digital part before the live show to help them better understand the pieces.
- In addition, Live on social media might have a potential to make the audiences engage even more in the festivals with the entertaining and informative contents.

Chapter 4. Recommendations/Conclusions

4.1. Recommendations

4.1.1. FES-visor

(Assembly Festival, n.d.; Cooper, n.d.; Cyst-er Act, n.d.; Die! Die! Die! Old People Die, 2019; Edinburgh Festival Fringe, n.d.; Guardian News & Media, n.d.; MacLeod, n.d.; Pollock, 2019; Sold, n.d.; Suzi Ruffell, 2019; Time Out London, n.d.)

By adapting the concept of Trip Advisor, Fringe's or OFF's visitors could have a centralized assistant called FES-visor which helps the visitors to enjoy their festival experiences from the beginning to the end. FES-visor has 7 main functions:

(1) Show searching and ticket booking: Thanks to GPS system and filters, such as ticket prices, proximity and reviews, festivalgoers could rapidly find the most suitable shows as requested. Having as well the short clips of the shows and the comments from the press and the public, the potential audiences could have an integrated experience from show searching to ticket booking at all-in-one FES-visor.

(2) Events: visitors could review and book the events easily.

(3) Selections: To decrease the anxiety of selecting the ideal shows, FES-visor provides the recommendation lists in four categories: Press Selections, Stars' Selections, Performers' Selections and Public Selections.

(4) Live: potential audiences could have a glimpse on the stream live performances before buying tickets.

(5) Gallery: participants could share the photos or clips on their social media to express their joyfulness and satisfaction in the festivals.

(6) Chat Room: visitors could connect and hang out with new friends who might share the same interests with them.

(7) Info: there are general festival updates and also personalized practical information based on the booking records.

4.1.2. Events and social media campaigns

To stimulate the festival social media and to consolidate the festival community, organizing the events and contests might be a good option to keep in touch with the festival communities. In this way, the festival online audiences are expected to have more connections with the festivals' social media, which is expected to bring more traffic and higher visibility to the festivals.

4.1.3. Customer-oriented contents

For truly welcoming the international and the young participants, Fringe's and OFF's social media contents shall be based on the fundamental needs of the festival-goers and on the added values which they could bring to the customers and enrich their festival experiences.

4.2. Conclusions

This thesis argued that the two most representative art festivals in Europe, Edinburgh Fringe and Avignon Off, might have the difficulty to have more audiences, and that digital approach and social media will be a solution to maintain the arts diversity and avoid elitist by bring more audiences, especially the young people. With the regular ups and downs of online popularity, 2019 has extremely high mentions in social media than ever, which motivates the author to examine the social media landscape of the two festivals in 2019.

With the aims of maintaining the sustainability of the two festivals and of contributing to the recent social media studies in Event and Festival industry, the research strategy was chosen to be the multiple case study approach with the embedded mixed method, which includes (1) the quantitative studies about mentions and reach of the two festivals in 4 social media platforms, including Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Youtube, and the analysis of offline flyers and (2) the qualitative study about stakeholders' perceptions towards social media with semi-structured interviews.

Based on the 11,267 data collected via Awario and 1,300 collected via Metricool around the two festivals, the author finds that social media in the two festivals still have such a huge room for progress. At first, concerning the festivals' contents and social media accounts, the main contents focus on the general and practical information about the festival itself, rarely present the shows or the artists and seldom go deeper on the contents which stimulate the visitors to take actions and attract them with the wonderful program. Secondly, about the public's social media contents, Fringe has a more diverse and international online audiences than OFF; yet, it's not evident that any community or marketing campaign was implemented to increase the audiences' satisfaction and have a higher visibility and media coverage. Thirdly, festivals' offline flyers, which are highly visualized, do not extremely make use of the elements which could give the competitive

advantages, such as marketing labels, mentions of prizes and special discounts. Fourthly, the two festivals' stakeholders have a relatively conservative position in terms of the “phygital” art creations.

In the end, the author proposed three points to improve the social media policy in Fringe and OFF: (1) a centralized digital assistant, FES-visor, which help the visitors from the beginning to the end of their festival journey, (2) events and social media campaigns which enhance the festival experiences and enlarge the media coverage and (3) customer-oriented contents which directly satisfy the needs of the customers. By implementing the recommendations above, the festival experiences could expect to be enhanced and enriched and attract more potential audiences to participate in the future.

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Chapter 6. Appendix

5.1.1. Qualitative interviews

AA-1. Spectator 1 & 2, a couple (FR) (age: 55/60)

[00:03] L'auteur : Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[00:11] Spectatrice 1 : Oui.

[00:13] Spectateur 2 : Oui.

[00:15] Spectatrice 1 : Lui non, moi oui.

[00:21] L'auteur : Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour une festival comme Avignon ? Qu'en pensez-vous ?

[00:29] Spectatrice 1 : C'est utile, oui. Je pense que oui.

[00:33] Spectateur 2 : C'est utile. En fait, nous, ce n'est pas... c'est sur peu particulier ou n'est pas au festival d'Avignon parce qu'on a suivi une publicité. C'est simplement parce que notre fille joue.

[00:54] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous suivez les réseaux sociaux d'Avignon ?

[01:03] Spectatrice 1 : Non. Non.

[01:06] L'auteur : Mais comment vous pouvez récupérer toutes les informations ?

[01:12] Spectatrice 1 : On regarde les parades. On écoute, ce que nous racontent les gens qui représentent des spectacles en faits qui parquent, et puis ...

[01:23] Spectateur 2 : Les informations par les gens dans la rue.

[01:25] L'auteur : C'est-à-dire que vous n'avez pas réservé des billets de spectacle en avance ?

[01:29] Spectatrice 1 : Non, non, parce qu'on est tout en début, on reste jours et on se douter qu'il y aurait la place.

[01:39] L'auteur : Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue d'ici ?

[01:46] Spectatrice 1 : eh non, non. Eh Airbnb ?

[01:54] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous pensez que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour un festival comme Avignon ? Si oui, dans quelle dimension ?

[02:05] Spectatrice 1 : Oui, je pense que c'est utile surtout pour les jeunes. Voilà. Parce que les jeunes, ils sont plus connectés entre eux. Voilà !

[02:17] Spectateur 2 : Bien-sûr ils sont utiles, les réseaux sociaux. Ça c'est le moyen d'information le plus simple, et puis eh, maintenant ... je pense que toutes les personnes... c'est plus rapide ou a des informations très rapidement, que tout le monde c'est un moyen pour se renseigner surtout, que ce soit pour un logement, sur les pièces de théâtre. C'est un évident que les réseaux sociaux, c'est une information.

[02:51] L'auteur : Quelle type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur le festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux?

[03:12] Spectateur 2 : Une information plus globale sur le festival officiel. Depuis quand il existe ? Comment ça se déroule entre le festival Off ? Entre le festival officiel ? Qui va voir quoi ? Et un peu plus d'informations peut-être sur les pièces qu'on peut voir...voilà ! L'information plus globale sur pourquoi le festival Avignon, présenter plus la ville sur les réseaux sociaux, les informations plus globales qui connaît d'avantage le festival.

[03:59] L'auteur : Est-ce que c'est la première fois que vous venez au festival d'Avignon ?

[04:02] Les deux : Oui.

AA-2. Spectator 3-5, (FR) (age: 60)

[00:06] Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[00:11] Spectateur 3 : Ça moi, non.

[00:14] Spectateur 4 : Alors moi, non.

[00:15] Spectateur 5 : Moi non plus.

[00:24] Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour le festival comme Avignon selon vous ?

[00:31] Spectateur 3 : Moi, je ne vais pas les réseaux sociaux donc je ne peux pas...

[00:34] Spectateur 4 : Je pense que c'est très utile pour que les gens partagent leur avis, leurs opinions, leur ressentir, oui. Très important.

[00:42] Spectateur 5 : Ça peut être utile pour connaître des événements qui peuvent se produire. Mais ça limite à ça. Je veux dire que, j'utilise ça comme source d'informations plus que comme un échange ou une interaction.

[00:58] Mais vous ne les avez pas utilisé, les réseaux sociaux ?

[01:02] Spectateur 5 : Je les regarde mais je ne réagis pas. Je ne like pas.

[01:10] Vous savez qu'il y a les réseaux sociaux d'Avignon ou d'Avignon Off ?

[01:17] Spectateur 5 : Je ne sais pas. Je ne sais pas. H2 : Moi pareil.

[01:30] Avez-vous utilise les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue d'ici ?

[01:37] Spectateur 5 : Je suis Avignonnais. Donc je n'ai rien à préparer.

[02:04] Quelle type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur le festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux?

[02:13] Spectateur 4 : Par exemple, mon ami Pavel aimerait trouver des célibataires. Les gens qui aiment les mêmes choses que lui ...

[02:17] Spectateur 5 : Mêmes choses de lui. Pour voir des pièces du théâtre.

[02:37] Spectateur 3 : Oui eh, je ne sais pas. Je ne peux pas dire parce que je ne consulte pas.

AA-3. Spectator 6 & 7, (TW) (age: 30/40)

[00:06] 作者: 平常有使用社群媒體的習慣嗎?

[00:10] 觀眾六(女): 有, 只是看別人的而已, 自己沒有主動發表。

[00:19] 觀眾七(女): (發表占)少數, 對。

[00:24] 作者: 這次外亞維儂藝術節的社群媒體, 有 Facebook, Instagram, Youtube 等, 妳們覺得他們好用嗎?

[00:33] 觀眾七(女): 因為我們沒有看到適合的語言...

[00:39] 觀眾六(女): 對!(笑) 無法理解。

[00:42] 觀眾七(女): 像我們身邊很多人會一起討論愛丁堡音樂節。但這次來這, 其實是因為我們自助旅行, 後來才發現有外亞維儂藝術節。待在法國的朋友有說: 你

們去那，可能會剛好遇到喔。對，在知名度上，可能在台灣只接收到愛丁堡的資訊，這一聽就曉得。可是，(外)亞維儂藝術節需要先 google 一下。

[01:11] 觀眾六(女): 我也是初次聽聞這個藝術節。本來來南法是為了薰衣草，後來在搜尋的過程中發現了(外)亞維儂藝術節。

[01:25] 觀眾七(女): 他(外亞維儂)盡可能先用他的法語做宣傳，因而對我們來說有些距離。

[01:39] 作者: 那妳們有用(外)亞維儂藝術節的社群媒體，為這一趟旅行做準備嗎？

[01:46] 兩觀眾: 沒有。

[01:48] 作者: 請問妳們如何蒐集資料？

[01:52] 觀眾六(女): 靠朋友。

[01:53] 觀眾七(女): 到處閒晃。

[01:58] 觀眾六(女): 我有個待過法國的朋友，他有跟我分享他的經驗，或者有些部落客會分享他們的經驗，或者有遇到什麼樣的表演團體，然後可以怎麼(挑戲)看。因此我們開始蒐集傳單，然後再做挑選。

[02:19] 作者: 所以妳們都沒有先買票？

[02:26] 觀眾七(女): 本來有想要先買票，但就沒辦法看懂他在表演什麼，就也不敢購買...

[02:30] 觀眾六(女): 無從下手...

[02:32] 觀眾七(女): 想說人先到了再說。

[02:33] 作者: 今天是妳們在亞維儂的第幾天？

[02:34] 兩觀眾: 第二天。

[02:37] 作者: 你們昨天有看表演嗎？

[02:37] 觀眾七 (女): 昨天有, 先在路邊看。

[02:39] 觀眾六 (女): 先看街頭表演。我們打算明天買票。

[02:43] 觀眾七 (女): 先看個一兩場。

[02:44] 作者: 你們會待幾天啊?

[02:47] 觀眾六 (女): 在這裡待上四五天。我們會出城後再返回, 因為我們住這旁邊。早上可能會先到其他地方走走。

[03:07] 作者: 何種資訊妳們會想在外(亞維儂)的社群媒體上找到?

[03:32] 觀眾六 (女): 時間節目表和表演團體的相關資訊。我覺得有一個可以直接看到表演日期, 時間, 資訊與戲院地點的社群媒體很重要, 因為這裡有分好幾個地點展演。

[03:50] 觀眾七 (女): 或許已經有此平台, 只可能看不懂。

[03:56] 作者: 那你們心目中有沒有哪個藝術節社群媒體做比較好?

[04:02] 觀眾六 (女): 我同事在搜尋愛丁堡(節慶)的經驗上, 他就覺得資訊都非常清楚, 包含訂票, 參訪團 (tour) 等。他聲稱他可以很快地得到資訊, 這跟我們一上頁面所面對的全法文網頁的落差有些懸殊。

AA-4. Spectator 8-12, (FR) (age: 25/30)

[00:26] L'auteur : Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[00:33] F : Oui

[00:34] F : Oui, oui.

[00:36] H : Oui aussi.

[00:37] H : Non. Non. C'est vrai, je n'utilise pas.

[00:45] L'auteur : Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour le festival comme Avignon ? Et comment ?

[00:51] F : Oui, c'est l'information facile rapide

[00:56] F : Pour nous là, pas vraiment parce que c'est plus un événement qu'on connaît. Du coup, on va regarder directement sur le site internet mais pas forcément pour suivre la page Facebook festival quoi.

[01:13] H : Oui, je pense que ça peut être utile ouais, pour les gens justement qui ne viennent pas forcément d'ici.

[01:18] H : Je pense que c'est utile pour savoir la programmation et avoir une idée des avis de spectateurs etc. pour choisir sa pièce de théâtre.

[01:34] L'auteur : Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue pour festival d'Avignon ?

[01:41] F : Non, pas du tout. Pas du tout.

[01:43] Mais comment avez-vous préparé pour ce voyage par exemple ?

[01:47] F : Là, c'était plus pour voir quelque 'uns qu'on connaissait donc, on a regardé sur site internet directement.

[01:54] F : Oui, c'est plus par le bouche-oreille en fait.

[01:58] H : Nous connaissons la région, donc on connaît bien déjà ce festival. On n'est pas servi, des réseaux sociaux.

[02:03] L'auteur : Donc cette fois, ce n'est pas la première fois que vous venez ici ?

[02:05] Non, non, ce n'est pas la première fois.

[02:07] Du coup, comme on disait, grâce à eux, notre réseau social, c'est la famille et les amis finalement.

[02:18] L'auteur : Quelle type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur le festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux?

[02:29] F : La programmation, les avis des personnes sur les pièces.

[02:34] F : Ouais, des recommandations pour chaque journée en fonction de l'âge, les horaires, que ce soit plus facile à trouver. Nous on a regardé le site internet du festival il y avait énormément de propositions, et du coup, c'est vrai qu'une page Facebook, ça peut être pas mal pour un choix du coup.

[02:51] H : Je pense que le plus intéressant, ce sont les avis surtout qu'on peut avoir grâce aux personnes qui sont venu voir les pièces et les avis externes.

[03:00] H : Justement, une page pour festival, ça permettrait de regrouper toutes les informations, plutôt que d'aller site de chaque de théâtre

[03:09] F : Je pense que c'était dur aussi de ne pas savoir si les pièces étaient complètes ou pas. Avec les réseaux sociaux pourrait voir le remplissage en direct, ça permet de savoir où est-ce qu'on peut appeler, parce que sinon on fait qu'appeler, pour savoir s'il y a des dispos.

[03:26] L'auteur : Mais en ce moment, les réseaux sociaux d'Avignon, ne sont pas suffisants pour trouver cette type d'informations ?

[03:34] F : Non, on n'a pas eu le reflex en fait. Je ne sais même pas si ça existe, une page Facebook du festival.

[03:39] L'auteur : Il y en a un, « To see or not to see ». C'est vraiment un endroit où vous pouvez réagir mais les personnes ne connaissent ce site. Il a été ouvert à quatre ans. Est-ce que vous imagineriez que dans cinq ans, on vous donne déjà quand vous êtes en train d'attendre avec un flash code, pour accéder à une petite information sur ce que vous allez voir ? Est-ce qu'on ne pourrait pas vous donner plus d'infos sur ce que vous êtes en train de voir, le thème abordé, quelle est le combat de l'artiste, est-ce que ça vous intéresserait d'avoir des informations en profondeur sur le spectacle ?

[04:19] F : Apres oui, après c'est intéressant.

[04:22] H : Justement là, par exemple, on vient d'aller voir une pièce de théâtre, Le portrait de Dorian Gray de Oscar Wilde, avoir des informations supplémentaires sur l'écrivain, sur les contextes historiques. Ça peut être intéressant.

[04:39] L'auteur : Est-ce que votre génération accepte qu'on commence le spectacle avant. C'est-à-dire que vous allez rentrer dans le théâtre, vous avez déjà reçu des photos, des vidéos qui ont fait « démarrer » le spectacle avant, où est-ce que vous préféreriez de rester de la première minute à la soixantième minute de spectacle ? Le comédien vous parle, ou même Dostoïevski qui vous parle, en disant que cette comédienne vous parle du sujet qui l'a toujours passionné, que ça commence déjà avant, ou ça continue après, où est-ce que vous êtes ? Votre génération ?

[05:22] H : En fait, si le spectacle est si prêt, finalement ce n'est pas un gadget. Ça apportera quelque chose. Oui, pourquoi pas, en fait ?

[05:33] H : Je suis d'accord mais pour moi, ça sera plutôt après. J'aime bien arriver avant sans savoir.

[05:46] F : Je pense que si c'est une histoire qui est en lien avec les réseaux sociaux, la technologie, ou c'est un outil que le public utilise, ça me parlait intéressant, rigoureux. Mais sinon, j'aime bien le côté traditionnel, on rentre dans un truc quand on est dans la salle. Pour moi, ça sera un peu pareille, ça sera plutôt après du coup.

AA-5. Spectator 13 & 14 (F) from Alsace (FR) (age: 25/28)

[00:01] L'auteur : Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[00:08] Spectatrice 13 : Oui. Facebook oui, mais pas Twitter.

[00:09] Spectatrice 14 : Pas Twitter non plus. Facebook et Youtube.

[00:17] L'auteur : Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour un festival comme Avignon ? Et comment ?

[00:24] Spectatrice 14 : Eh non, on n'a pas eu l'utilité. Non.

[00:27] L'auteur : C'est la première fois que (vous participez au festival Avignon ?)

[00:28] Spectatrice 14 : Non, on était là l'année dernière aussi, et on n'a jamais eu l'utilité en tout cas. On n'a jamais utilisé ni Facebook ni YouTube pour l'évènement en tout cas sur Avignon.

[00:40] Spectatrice 13 : Pareil, généralement on vient Avignon, et ensuite on regarde les affiches, un petit peu programme sur internet, pour un spectacle ou j'ai un peu regardé la bande-annonce sur YouTube voilà.

[00:52] L'auteur : Mais vous savez il y a le compte de Facebook ou Youtube d'Avignon ?

[00:58] Spectatrice 13 : Non, je ne savais pas.

[00:59] Spectatrice 14 : Moi non plus.

[01:03] L'auteur : Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue pour festival Avignon ?

[01:08] Spectatrice 14 : Non, non parce qu'on a changé les messages, par SMS, on n'aime pas utiliser messenger de Facebook.

[01:23] L'auteur : Vous avez utilisé (utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue pour festival Avignon ?) ou ?

[01:24] Spectatrice 13 : Non, non, en fait, on se rappelé tous les deux par téléphone. C'est tout.

[01:28] L'auteur : Et après ça, vous êtes cherchez quelques informations sur internet, c'est ça ?

[01:33] Spectatrice 13 : Pour le camping. Pour trouver un logement, on utilise le site pour camping. C'est pas un réseau social.

[01:40] Spectatrice 14 : Et puis le site du Festival d'Avignon aussi. On a regardé le site, mais du coup, ce n'est pas réseaux sociaux. C'est le site quoi.

[01:48] L'auteur : Quelle type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur le festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux?

[02:05] Spectatrice 13 : Parfois sur les affiches (ou dans la grand livre), ils n'ont pas marqué les différents tarifs, ça peut être intéressant qu'on n'a pas forcément la place sur les affiches. C'est difficile de dire. Je ne sais pas qu'est-ce qu'on peut trouver sur les réseaux sociaux alors, c'est difficile de dire qu'est-ce que nous aimerions trouver parce qu'on ne sais pas qu'est qu'il y a déjà.

[02:40] Spectatrice 14 : Peut-être, oui peut-être la bande-annonce des spectacles, peut-être le prix des tarifs, le lieu et l'horaire.

[02:52] L'auteur : Quelle sont les potentiels, les usages potentiels des réseaux sociaux pour le festival comme Avignon ?

[03:03] Spectatrice 14 : Peut-être que chacun donne son avis, ça peut être intéressant, l'avis des autres et tous.

[03:08] Spectatrice 13 : Après il y a Messenger, si on parle en groupe, c'est plus pratique pour communiquer. Mais sinon, je n'utilise pas trop Facebook pour partir en vacance, je ne sais pas. Instagram, j'utilise beaucoup, après je regarde un peu qu'est-ce que d'autres font, mais je n'utilise pas pour des événements. Par exemple, j'ai vu il y a une page d'Instagram, justement pour, je crois c'est juste une application qui proposait des événements et tout culturel a cote chez moi, mais je l'ai suivi et finalement, je n'ai pas trouvé utilité en tout cas, je préfère, moi cherchais l'information sur l'internet plutôt qu'on la donne via réseau social en fait.

AA-6. Spectator 15 & 16 (age: 55/60)

[00:09] L'auteur : Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[00:17] Spectatrice 15 : Oui, franchement oui.

[00:19] Spectatrice 16 : Oui, oui.

[00:23] L'auteur : Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour une festival comme Avignon ?

[00:28] Spectatrice 15 : Pour moi non. Parce que vous avez 1 500 spectacles, et que je pourrais avoir le brochure pour garder ; sinon, je ne peux pas trier. Pour moi, le papier est important.

[00:46] Spectatrice 16 : Pour moi, c'est important les réseaux sociaux. Je vois les commentaires sur les réseaux sociaux.

[00:51] L'auteur : Vous avez suivi les réseaux sociaux d'Avignon, par exemple ?

[00:55] Spectatrice 16 : Non, pas celles d'Avignon, mais des amis sur Facebook qui disent quelle pièce est bien. J'écoute ça tout d'abord, la recommandation des amis.

[01:05] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous avez suivi Facebook ou Twitter d'Avignon ?

[01:10] Spectatrice 15 : Non.

[01:11] Spectatrice 16 : Je ne survivrais pas, non.

[01:22] L'auteur : Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue du Festival Avignon ?

[01:28] Spectatrice 15 : Non, non, c'est vraiment... J'avais cherché le bouquin. Je fais le festival depuis des années. C'est ma technique. Je trouve le bouquin. Je regarde le théâtre et des heures.

[01:44] L'auteur : Combien de fois que vous êtes venue ici ?

[01:48] Spectatrice 15 : Moi, je fais dix ans ce festival, peut-être plus même.

[01:53] Spectatrice 16 : Moi je viens depuis 4 ou 5 ans. J'habite ici. J'habite la région.

[02:00] L'auteur : Quel type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux ?

[02:10] Spectatrice 15 : Critiques de personnes.

AA-7. Spectator 17 (age: 18)

[00:18] The author: How do people use social media in Avignon Off?

[00:23] Spectatrice 17 : Most of the people all the time at my age are in the social media, and I have never really seen the communication about the festival Avignon on social media. It's more on physical offline communication with flyers and posters. Everyone is in the town, which is the thing of Avignon. We have posters everywhere in the street, and nobody really want to see them in the social media. People go in the street to see the colorful walls everywhere, and to see the posters, and to hear people sing and to see people dance in the street. So there is something to use in social media, but people don't really do that, especially because that the clientele of the festival Avignon is really older. I think the average age of the spectators, they are like 40 years old, especially for the festival in. The Off is a bit different. But once again, it's not really in the social media. Of course, you have some group on Facebook so that you can share the shows that you have seen, and that you think they are really great, but having more than a thousand shows, Avignon is really difficult on social media to differentiate them.

[01:50] The author: Did you follow the Twitter, Instagram or Facebook of Avignon International or Off?

[01:57] Spectatrice 17 : No, I don't. I only follow "la collection Lambert," which is a museum here in Avignon like contemporary art museum, so it's not really link to the festival Avignon. But during the festival, there are always special activities, and I follow them in Instagram. I don't think we have anything special in social media in festival Avignon. Maybe there is, but it's not famous.

[02:20] The author: What do you think the potential of social media in this festival?

[02:32] Spectatrice 17 : I know my mom uses a lot Facebook, and she's the typical age of the people who go to the Avignon, so I think there is something to do on Facebook, not really Twitter or Instagram because young people don't really go to the festival Avignon because it's really expensive, we want to see everything, but everything is like so expensive.

[02:49] The author: I know that the festival Off issues the reduction cards.

[02:53] Spectatrice 17 : Yes, we can have reduction cards, but still if you want to see just one show, it's like around 10 euros. If you want to see ten of them, it's a hundred euros.

[03:01] The author: Are the spectators here more local or more international?

[03:04] Spectatrice 17 : No, I think it's mainly tourists. So there are a lot of international people, but in the festival Off, I don't know if you read in the huge book where everything is written, there is not so many plays in English. So most of them are in French. So most of the people here they come from Paris, come from Monaco and come from, I don't know (whether there are people coming from) Bordeaux, but mainly from Paris, and they all come here to the Avignon because it's really, really famous, especially for the people in the cinema and theater industry, they want to see a lot of journalists and stuffs, and they also come here to become famous.

[03:44] The author: How would you use the social media in the festival? What would you do if you are the social media manager?

[03:52] Spectatrice 17 : It's a really tough question because as I said, there are so many different plays, more than one thousand I guess. So I think it would be difficult to make a difference, but maybe we could. Do you mean to let people have place to do the advertisement?

[04:18] The author: Anything in any direction. Which are the different direction that you could use for social media?

[04:24] Spectatrice 17 : I think advertisement, it would be great because then people could share the short videos like trailers of their shows.

[04:32] The author: Don't they do that today on Youtube? Don't they have an Avignon in or Avignon off Youtube channel?

[04:38] Spectatrice 17 : Maybe it exists, but once again, it's really not famous at all, and nobody uses these, nobody uses that.

[04:43] The author: Does anybody use them for promotion and information?

[04:45] Spectatrice 17 : No. No. People they all have this huge book. And the main thing is in French we say “la bouch-l’oreille (word-of-mouth)” so it’s the people talking with each other. I think social media could be very useful but it’s not developed right now.

[05:08] The author: I just saw a play about the basque county and basque culture, and I hadn’t the enough knowledge to understand nicely the play. I was thinking maybe the social media could bring sort of introduction for each play.

[05:30] Spectatrice 17 : I think there is an app, the festival Off app, or something I’m not quite sure, but I think it exist, but if it doesn’t exist, it should exist. I think it could be very, very useful. With just one app, you have every place for the entire month and all the information that you need. Or Instagram, I think, now they develop something in their stories, where you can interact between the posters and the followers.

[06:03] The author: In the festival Avignon (Off), where could people give the stars?

[06:13] Spectatrice 17 : On the journals, in the news.

[06:15] The author: So is it made by the journalists?

[06:17] Spectatrice 17 : So most of the time, yes, it’s made by the journalists. So actually I know one of my friends in high school, and she works for la Provence, which is a local newspaper, and she has free access to every piece that she wants to do, and then she just wrote comments and critics. So you can work even since 15 years old, and they wants people from every age to make critics for the shows.

[06:47] The author: Is there any way for the public to make their reviews?

[06:52] Spectatrice 17 : You can do this, for example, if one show has a Facebook page, and you can go and rate on the Facebook page, but not a lot of people do it, and the spectators they don't always think about doing this.

[07:09] The author: Do the shows merely use the reviews from the journalists (as a promotion tool)?

[07:13] Spectatrice 17 : Yes, most of the time, yes.

[07:26] The author: What's your conclusion about the social media (in Avignon Off)?

[07:31] Spectatrice 17 : I think that social media might be useful, but it's not really in the spirit of festival Avignon.

[07:36] The author: What is the spirit of festival Avignon (Off)?

[07:38] Spectatrice 17 : It's going out for seeing by yourself where you want to go, is people interacting in the street, or people talking, advertising for their shows, but you know, in the real life, giving flyers, or making like the small shows in the streets and the colorful walls everywhere... I think this is really the spirit of Avignon.

[07:56] The author: As an 18 year old lady, do you think that it's good to do it (like this)?

[08:00] Spectatrice 17 : Yes, because I'm a learner of social media, I am not going to lie. And sometimes that I even learnt several social media which I'm not aware of. But really in the festival Avignon, I never learn anything on social media. Everyone goes out in the street and see by themselves. I think it's really amazing, and then we have the occasion to have so many people out there in the street, which is really making me happy, making me feel in the holidays and making me feel in the summer. If everything is on the social media, nobody really goes in the streets and meet. Here is the location to meet the actual actors and talk with them. Of course people take pictures with them and post them on social media, but that's really better and has always been for 70 years in this period of festival Avignon to go out in the street, and physically see everything by yourself, meet people and talk with them.

[09:02] The author: Tourists might have the difficulties to prepare for the arrival of Avignon for the first time (without the support from the social media).

[09:15] Spectatrice 17 : Ok, then, everything is in the book. So most people like French people they come from Paris, and they just go to the tourism office and take the huge book and then just look by themselves.

BA-1. Artist 1 (age: 35/40)

[00:44] L'auteur : Comment vous pensez les réseaux sociaux ?

[00:50] Artiste 1 : Les réseaux sociaux si c'est important dans le festival ? Oui !

Aujourd'hui c'est important. Nous en tant qu'artistes, on fonctionne plus avec Facebook, Instagram, un peu petit peu Snapchat, mais pas du tout avec Twitter. On ne twitte pas. On n'a pas non plus ... je ne me sers pas de twitter. Où se marche plus sur l'Instagram. On a beaucoup regardé, beaucoup vus, d'un coup, ça ... on fait c'est pub pour le spectacle. Les gens, ils te voient sur téléphone sur Instagram, ils croisent sur dans la rue, ils croisent au coin de la rue. Tout de suite, ils y font la référence ils te disent ... « Tiens je l'ai vue sur Instagram. Elle est là ». Ça fait retour. C'est des petites pointes, des petites touches... c'est une pique de rappel pour dire aux gens : « Voilà ! Il y a ça à Avignon sur festival. » On se croise dans la rue, ils viennent découvrir ou pas de spectacle par la suite.

[01:55] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous pensez que les réseaux sociaux d'Avignon (Off) sont vraiment utiles pour vous (ex : promouvoir votre spectacle) ?

[02:05] Artiste 1 : Mais complètement. C'est très important.

[02:13] L'auteur : Est-ce que les comptes du festival Avignon (Off) sont actifs cette année dans les réseaux sociaux ?

[02:18] Artiste 1 : Je trouve que Avignon cette année, oui ! Parce qu'avant ils étaient moins actifs sur les réseaux, et cette année ils sont plus actifs avec l'hashtag « Avignonleoff2019 ». Moi, j'ai suivi un petit peu ... ils me mettent des vidéos de parades, le début du festival, l'affichage tout ça. Je pense qu'ils sont obligés de se développer. Nous les artistes, les producteurs, ils le font à fond ! Il faut que le festival s'y mette ouvrir. Ils sont en retard comparé à d'autres. Ça fait des années que les réseaux sociaux fonctionnent. Déjà quatre, cinq ans, ou fait beaucoup de pub avec les réseaux sociaux. Avignon avant il n'y avait pas cette dynamique sur les réseaux sociaux. Cette année, je pense que c'est déjà un peu plus présent que les autres. Je pense que de toutes façons, ils sont obligés de le faire. Sinon, ça ne peut pas suivre. On est obligé de s'y mettre les réseaux sociaux aujourd'hui c'est la nouvelle communication. Tout le monde est sur un portable, smartphone, ordinateur.

[03:24] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous en tant qu'artiste, vous êtes intégré les réseaux sociaux dans votre inspiration d'artiste ? Est-ce que vous dites je pouvois dire les choses, ou je ne peux pas dire cela, faire les choses parce que c'est promu par les réseaux sociaux donc c'est plutôt bon, faire de l'images faire des vidéos parce que vous pensez ce geste la va être intégrer dans une identification des réseaux sociaux ? Ou est-ce que vous nous dites je ne peux pas y aller, parce que politiquement, je ne peux pas le faire ?

[03:47] Artiste 1 : Si, nous, on fait la vidéo. On a fait beaucoup. On fait attention à ce qu'on dit et à ce qu'on fait. On ne parle pas trop de l'actualité. On fait plus de petits vidéos comiques. On fait très attention mais on a fait beaucoup parce que c'est regardé. Tout de suite on fait beaucoup de vue. Nous on s'en aperçoit aujourd'hui parce que nous, on est à Paris, que les vidéos à Avignon elles sont gardées. Ce que les gens nous disent : « A tiens, c'est elle qui s'est retrouvée dans Instagram, qui a fait cette vidéo-là. Mais non, on a fait beaucoup parce que c'est important. Elles identifient. Ça fait de la promotion, de la communication.

[04:19] L'auteur : Est-ce que du coup vous trouvez que grâce à réseau sociaux, un lien entre deux éditions. Vous êtes à Avignon aujourd'hui, demain vous êtes à autre endroit. Entre deux apparitions sur scène, est-ce que les réseaux sociaux c'est un lien pour vous avec votre public ?

[04:31] Artiste 1 : Tout à fait. Toujours à la fin on filme pour mettre sur les réseaux sociaux.

[04:34] L'auteur : Les gens vous suivent ?

[04:37] Artiste 1 : Tout à fait. Il y a eu beaucoup, beaucoup. On a au moins cinq mille, sept mille personnes qui nous suivent tout le temps.

[04:43] L'auteur : Du coup, ils vous suivent aussi sur la scène derrière ?

[04:45] Artiste 1 : Sur scène derrière en tournée, en province partout, il y a des gens qui viennent aussi voir le spectacle, et qui ensuite nous suivent par ce ils sont vu le spectacle.

[05:01] L'auteur : Comment utilisez potentiellement les réseaux sociaux en tant qu'artiste ? Encore plus ?

[05:05] Artiste 1 : Moi, je les utilise déjà beaucoup.

[05:09] L'auteur : En tant qu'artiste, en tant que spectacle, par exemple, s'il y avait une transmission, live Facebook, si vous pouvez parler en même temps à l'autre public ?

[05:19] Artiste 1 : Non, ça, je ne fais pas, mais c'est vrai que ...

[05:22] L'auteur : Est-ce que ça pourrait vous influencer et modifier votre façon de faire votre travail ?

[05:25] Artiste 1 : Peut-être faire des Live, mais de cinq minutes. Ce ne me paraît plus. Les cinq croient minutes de spectacle par exemple le Live FB... Oui, le live Facebook. Voilà, parce que comme ça, ça donne envie aussi de venir découvrir le spectacle. Et à cinq, dix premières minutes, il y a beaucoup d'artistes maintenant qui fais ça... Ils lancent le spectacle en live, et ils la coupe au bout cinq minutes... Oui au bout de cinq minutes c'est coupé, et en fait, ça donne envie aux gens de dire « tiens, j'ai envie de voir la suite, ou je n'ai pas envie de le voir quoi. »

CA-1. Professional 1 (Producer) & 2 (team member), Artist 2 & 3

[00:26] L'auteur : Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[00:35] Professionnel 1 (Producteur) : Oui, c'est obligatoire maintenant que ce soit à Avignon ou ailleurs.

[00:38] Professionnelle 2 (Membre de l'équipe) : Tous les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour la promotion bien-sûr.

[00:43] L'auteur : Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour un festival comme Avignon ?

[00:49] Professionnel 1 (Producteur) : Oui, oui, c'est très utile. Il n'y a pas que ça, mais ça fait pour les annonces du spectacle, pour montrer les petites extraits vidéos, c'est un moyen de communication qui est quasi obligatoire, mais qui va être complètement compensé par d'autres moyens.

[01:11] Artiste 2 : Un peu pareil. Dis que les réseaux sociaux, il faut que le festival Avignon commence un mois à l'avance. On commence à annoncer ou envoie des vidéos tout ça. On peut plus faire semblant quoi. Voilà ! Il y a un festival d'Avignon effectivement, il y a toute cette communication autour des réseaux sociaux est très utile oui.

[01:27] Professionnelle 2 (Membre de l'équipe) : Oui, c'est ça. En fait, il y a la communication de préparation. Donc, un mois d'annonces et d'affichages, et ensuite il y a la communication au jour le jour sur le festival, et ça les réseaux sociaux, pour ça c'est très précieux

[01:45] L'auteur : Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue d'ici ?

[01:52] Professionnel 1 (Producteur) : Oui, oui, pareil, pour annoncer les spectacles qui se jouent. Moi, je suis producteur du spectacle, donc j'ai publié les visuels avec ça joué à tel endroit, à telle heure avec les liens de réservation. Ça c'est plus mon travail de prévenir qu'il y aura un tel spectacle, tel type, tel théâtre, à telle heure.

[02:29] Artiste 2 : Oui. Pour savoir qui sera sur le festival. Pour préparer les premières parties, et puis pour faire sa pub évidemment. C'est indissociable, on est obligés de faire les deux.

[02:40] Professionnelle 2 (Membre de l'équipe) : Oui, pareil. On a utilisé en particulier l'actualité sponsorisée et la promotion sur Facebook, la promotion ciblée qui est pratique pour faire la communication sur la région d'Avignon, ou sur la région en particulier. L'avantage des réseaux sociaux c'est que vous avez l'aspect de la communication et l'aspect de la publicité payante en fait, qui peut aussi vous permettre d'avoir non seulement des promotions ciblées mais des statistiques sur la façon dont les gens réagissent à vos publicités. C'est très intéressant pour préparer un événement comme Avignon qui est très spécifique pour savoir exactement comment cibler son public,

comment s'adressez son public, et qui est le public. Donc, les réseaux sociaux, double intérêt des réseaux sociaux évidemment, ils sont sur la communication et sur l'information qu'on peut en tirer.

[03:28] L'auteur : Quelle type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur le festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux?

[03:42] Professionnel 1 (Producteur) : L'application de festival, je ne l'ai même pas téléchargée cette année parce que l'année dernière ce n'était pas bonne. On ne trouvait pas du tout les infos... la pour le coup. On a été mieux servi avec un document papier, qui s'appelle « le bible », donc après moi ce que je veux une application, c'est je tape le nom d'un spectacle, qu'on me tout de suite a quel l'heure il joue, où il joue, et puis autrement ou l'inverse. Se prendre le théâtre et voir toute la programmation. Cette année je ne sais pas mais je sais que l'application de l'année dernier, été trop compliquée à utiliser. Je me rappelle que si je tapais le nom d'un spectacle, l'information n'arrivait pas. Je ne sais pas. L'année d'avant ça marchait très bien. Ce que je veux par rapport du festival, plus en tant que spectateur. En tant que producteur, ce que j'ai envie c'est que les gens qui cherchent un spectacle que je produis, ils pourraient le trouver tout de suite quoi. Avec les bons mots-clés, on pourrait avoir très facilement accéder aux informations.

[05:00] Artiste 2 : En faits, je trouve que les gens se sont approprié les réseaux sociaux plus rapidement que les institutions. Ce qui fait que tout ce qui est site, application sont « un peu obsolètes » parce que on va plus vite qu'eux dans l'information. Donc, c'est-à-dire que ça sera bien de pouvoir savoir qui participe un festival afin de préparer les premières parties. On est plus vite obligé de le faire en se communiquait entre nous, ou on crée un groupe qu'en allant sur l'application du Off... Le Off est un peu en retraite par rapport à la réalité. Tu sais ils vivent leurs trucs, ils ont leur village. La, concrètement, on n'est pas avec eux en fait. Et l'application regrette ça assez bien ça. C'est-à-dire que je ne me vois pas promouvoir mon spectacle via l'application. Je ne vois pas comment... Ils sont beaucoup plus lents quoi. Sauf si vous êtes des planqués du Off, et qu'on fait ça pour qu'on dise des choses pour nous permettre : « VOILA ! CA SE TROUVE... »

[05:58] Professionnelle 2 (Membre de l'équipe) : Je pense qu'il faudrait plus d'évènements en fait, qui réunissent tout le monde, et les médias sociaux, c'est pratique

pour ça organiser des soirées avec les artistes, les producteurs tout le monde. Je trouve qu'il n'y a pas assez d'évènements communs à tout le monde. Donc, organiser plus d'évènements pour rassembler les gens. Exactement. Ça ce serai utile.

[06:18] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous pensez que les réseaux sociaux d'Avignon sont actifs ?

[06:28] Professionnel 1 (Producteur) : Je ne sais pas. Je n'ai pas du temps d'aller voir. Je ne sais pas du tout.

[06:32] Professionnelle 2 (Membre de l'équipe) : Ils sont tous actifs et très réactifs.

[06:38] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous avez envisagé de faire commencer maintenant des spectacles avec un live Facebook par exemple, trois jours avant, intégrer les réseaux sociaux, non plus dans la promo seulement, mais dans la création ? Par exemple, vous choisirez la fin du spectacle dans les réseaux ?

[07:04] Professionnel 1 (Producteur) : Il faut aussi que le spectacle vivant reste dans les salles aussi. Donc, l'idée ça peut être de montrer cinq minutes pour donner envie aux gens pour voir la suite.

[07:19] Artiste 2 : C'est comme l'application de la vidéo dans un spectacle. Ça peut être fait mais c'est un cas particulier. En plus, on n'a pas sûr d'avoir le réseau qu'il dans toutes les salles.

[07:30] L'auteur : Par exemple, pourriez-vous avoir une partie de l'histoire qui commence à la maison, et quand vous rentrez dans le théâtre, vous continuez la même histoire ?

[07:40] Artiste 2 : Ah, oui, oui.

[07:42] L'auteur : Est-ce que la création pourrez commencer grâce à réseaux sociaux ou eux-mêmes de rentrer dans le théâtre ?

[07:45] Professionnelle 2 (Membre de l'équipe) : Je pense que ça pourrez faire une happening un petit buzz, mais ça pourrait pas être intégré dans la création parce que vous avez un spectacle, c'est un live devant les gens, c'est ça qui fait que c'est vivant, vous

êtes en face de l'artiste. Donc, effectivement, ça pourrez être amusant pour faire une promotion surprise mais pas intégré ça complètement au spectacle.

[08:09] Artiste 3 : D'autant moins qu'un artiste, il a besoin de le répéter son spectacle pour qu'il soit bien. Une vidéo, si vous faites un début live, et que ce n'est pas convainquant, vous venez de planter le spectacle derrière. Hors des mauvaises représentations, même après cinq cents, on en fait tous. Donc, si on intégrait ça, ce serait tellement dangereux. On n'est pas l'abri du « bad buzz » qui vous plante une carrière parce que la vidéo elle ne disparaît pas. Une nouvelle représentation, il y a trente personnes ou deux cents personnes qu'ils ont vue, mais après c'est fini. Une mauvaise, vidéo elle peut atteindre potentiellement deux cent millions personnes. Et donc là, ce n'est pas la même chose. Donc en tant qu'artiste, moi je ne ferai jamais un truc pareil par exemple parce que c'est du suicide.

CA-2. Professional 3 (Director) & 4 (Project assistant) of a crowdfunding / sponsoring platform

[01:10] L'auteur : Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[01:16] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : Oui.

[01:17] Professionnelle 4 (Accompagnement des projets) : Oui. Oui. On a en tant que Proarti, on a un compte Facebook, on a un compte Twitter, et un compte Instagram aussi.

[01:28] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : On est sur LinkedIn. Les gens qui viennent à cette plateforme utilise aussi beaucoup Youtube.

[01:40] L'auteur : Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour le festival comme Avignon ? A votre avis ?

[01:48] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : Oui, d'ailleurs, il faut prendre une photo ! Ils sont utiles en complément, en fait. Mais c'est comme toutes les outils de communication : plus on affiche, plus de se montre, par différents canaux, plus ça marche. Donc en fait, entre les flyers, les affiches, et les réseaux sociaux, ça vient « imprimer » plusieurs fois la

même information ; ça sert d'annonces et de rappels. Donc, oui, c'est très utile et, c'est très utilisé. On fait c'est l'outil principal de notre communication. 50% ou légèrement plus par rapport à tout le reste. Le papier est indispensable mais c'est impossible sans les réseaux sociaux.

[02:50] Professionnelle 4 (Accompagnement des projets) : Je pense la même chose.

[02:55] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : Juste par exemple, il y a des choses qu'on voit sur la typologie d'utilisation des réseaux. (1) Les artistes communiquent directement sur le spectacle, et activent leurs communautés. (2) Il y a tout l'évènementiel organisé par les institutionnels comme nous par exemple, qui soit font des postes qui sont de contenu, rappellent tous les éléments, soit ils font des histoires, des petites choses, un peu éditoriales, un d'infos teasing, et tout ça. (3) Et puis, la troisième typologie de poste, c'est la communication institutionnelle des compagnies. Il y a les artistes qui communiquent entre eux, les institutions qui font un peu deux types de communication, et puis il y a les compagnies qui font leur propre communication, qui annoncent, pour que les gens aillent acheter les billets et voir le spectacle.

[04:14] L'auteur : Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue pour festival Avignon ?

[04:21] Professionnelle 4 (Accompagnement des projets) : Oui. On a une communication en amont du festival d'Avignon qui est institutionnelle. On organise pendant toute la durée du festival, un « parcours » d'accompagnement. On a cette table de « rendez-vous » 5 heures par jour, pour que les gens soient en courant. On a aussi beaucoup utilisé notre newsletter, qui fait un rendu des canaux principaux utilisés par la plateforme. On diffuse le tout à vingt mille personnes à peu près, et sûr Facebook pendant toute la durée de festival, Facebook, Instagram. On va prévenir les gens qu'on est présents. Je pense c'est la façon qu'aura d'utiliser les réseaux sociaux pour le festival.

[05:11] L'auteur : Quelle type d'information aimeriez-vous trouver sur le festival grâce aux réseaux sociaux?

[05:22] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : Le plus intéressant, c'est les commentaires, les avis, un peu des articles qui sont écrits, qui sont une analyse des spectacles. Je trouve c'est ça qui est le plus intéressant. Alors il y en a déjà, mais plus on en a, mieux c'est.

[05:47] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous pensez les comptes réseaux sociaux d'Avignon sont assez actifs ?

[06:09] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : Il y a beaucoup de plateformes. Comme il y a plusieurs plateformes, il y a comme mêmes une dispersion de l'« œuvres ». Honnêtement, je n'ai pas d'idée magique d'autres utilisations possibles des réseaux sociaux... Mais globalement, c'est suffisant.

[06:36] L'auteur : Vous pouvez toujours trouver les informations nécessaires d'Avignon Off sur les réseaux sociaux?

[06:44] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : Dès qu'on cherche, on trouve, ouais. Il y a tout. Donc il y a comme mêmes aucune excuse. C'est plus le temps qu'on consacre à chercher l'information, qui est un sujet. C'est penser à quelle information on cherche, et le temps investi pour chercher l'information. Ça prend beaucoup de temps en fait. Il faut qu'on passe le temps à collecter les infos à la traiter. C'est un gros enjeu, ça, mais c'est ce qu'on essaye à faire un peu tout le temps d'ailleurs. C'est ça qui est compliqué. Je n'ai pas du tout de suggestions à donner sur comment améliorer ceci.

[07:18] L'auteur : La communication d'Avignon, c'est plutôt sur le « grand livre », c'est ça ?

[07:24] Professionnel 3 (Directeur) : Ouais. Le catalogue. L'intérêt de catalogue, c'est quand même de présenter les choses « offline ». On peut feuilleter, ça reste un outil très ergonomique, très utile en fait. C'est vrai que c'est lourd. Vachement ! Il faut les deux vraiment. C'est-à-dire quand on a une table, honnêtement, c'est plus facile d'aller vérifier ça et de cocher les choses. Effectivement, quand on est mobile, il faut avoir le catalogue, et accéder aux réseaux sociaux et interagir mais... je ne sais pas. Je pense qu'il y a des questions liées à la « cartographie géographique ». Il y a quelque chose à construire une carte et on peut dire voilà je veux savoir les spectacles notés cinq étoiles qui vont commencer dans moins une heure. Et on a ce besoin d'une telle carte. Et on sait ou on

est, où sont nos spectacles. C'est une carte digitale. Mais ce n'est pas dans les réseaux sociaux ça. C'est un autre outil. Mais Il n'existe pas. L'ergonomie de ce outil n'est pas encore abouti.

CA-3. Professional 5 (Show Producer) & 6 (Show diffuser)

[02:10] L'auteur : Utilisez-vous en général les réseaux sociaux ?

[02:18] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Oui. Et bien évidemment aujourd'hui si on veut communiquer et faire connaître notre savoir-faire, on est obligé d'être, presque malheureusement, connecté. Malheureusement, parce qu'on perde un peu d'humain avec les réseaux, mais c'est comme une toile qui nous permet de communiquer spontanément sur l'artistique, sur le contenu, sur l'expérience, sur les horaires, sur les dates, sur la structure de spectacle, sur la communication du spectacle, et c'est indispensable aujourd'hui de pouvoir « manipuler » dans le bon sens de la « chaîne » de réseaux.

[02:52] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Ouais, pour compléter ça, c'est aussi le lieu d'expression de la presse aujourd'hui. Tous ce qui est compte rendu de la presse. Donc tous les articles qu'on récupère sur le spectacle, on les diffuse sur les réseaux sociaux. L'outil « principal » des réseaux sociaux sont les blogs. Maintenant ils ont un gros impact auprès du public, du grand public. Ils ont même supplanté la presse écrite. C'est eux qui « gouvernent » le plus le public pour que la presse écrite aujourd'hui.

[03:25] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Donc, ces bloggeurs sont très influents, et parlent à des milliers de personnes. Leur contenu pour permettre fédérer les gens sur le spectacle. Il faut d'abord garantir la qualité de spectacle, et après ça diffuse.

[03:42] L'auteur : Est-ce que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles pour un festival comme Avignon ? Et comment?

[03:48] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Moi, de mon point de vue, purement l'organisateur d'évènement, évidemment que les réseaux sociaux sont utiles malgré à la foulditude d'infos. Le spectacle sera important, après... Qu'est qu'on va chercher dans les réseaux sociaux ? Dans quel type de réseaux ? Quel type de communication est faite... pour avoir,

s'orienter sur les sujets qui nous intéressent ? C'est ça ce qui est un peu plus difficile parce que sur les réseaux, on met tout, et son contraire. C'est la difficulté aujourd'hui pour quelqu'un qui veut aller sur les réseaux, c'est d'aller chercher le spectacle qui peut correspondre à la cible. Ça peut être un peu compliqué. Crois-moi ! C'est bien évidemment utile pour le développement du festival, le contenu et qu'on peut y voir.

[04:35] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : La chose la plus importante sur Avignon ce ne sont pas les réseaux sociaux pour faire du public, parce qu'il y a trop de choses à faire, il y a trop d'information. C'est le bouche-à-oreille ! Le plus ancien mode de promotion qui existe, c'est le bouche-à-oreille. C'est-à-dire quelqu'un a vu le spectacle, en parle à d'autres, ça c'est la meilleure publicité qu'on peut voir le spectacle. Ça va mieux devant ce qui est sur les réseaux sociaux parce qu'ici le bouche-à-oreille prend très peu de temps... une foultitude de choses, donc ça va très vite. Par contre, pour nous, ce qui est important, c'est de récupérer ce qui est dit sur les réseaux sociaux pour mettre dans les dossiers après pour vendre la pièce, pour promouvoir, le spectacle en récupérant ce qu'ils ont dit sur les réseaux sociaux.

[05:14] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Le « post-événement ». Avec tout ce qui est fait, après, évidemment, quand on produit un spectacle, on aimerait la salle est remplie tout le temps, à 90 pour-cent. Mais, à Avignon, on ne vient pas obligatoirement chercher ça. On vient chercher la qualité, l'écoute, la qualité aussi dans la production, dans le développement du projet avec ceux qui viennent voir le spectacle, et qui peuvent ensuite le promouvoir. Et comme tu le disais, en effets, on se sert de là qui, et de tous les bons articles. On les quantifie, et ça permet un peu de développer le spectacle, et l'image du spectacle, le contenu, et enfin le dossier presse.

[05:58] L'auteur : Avez-vous utilisé les réseaux sociaux pour préparer votre venue d'ici ?

[06:03] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Non, très peu. On a communiqué, on a créé un site avec la « compagnie des sens », mais ça n'a pas vraiment de sens en amont. Ça donne des informations, mais la vraie information, c'est le direct, et c'est ce que les gens qu'on voit, disent le rendu que l'on entend. Ce que vous allez voir, si ça vous plaît, vous avez envie d'en parler. Si vous en parlez à d'autres vous allez intéresser d'autres personnes, et c'est

le réseau qui va se mettre en place. Mais on a créé, en fait un site de la « compagnie des sens » en amont. Maintenant c'est un passage obligé. On utilise, on n'utilise pas, mais c'est utile pour les gens qui veulent aller chercher de l'info. On l'a fait, oui !

[06:44] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Ce qui est utilisé ici, c'est un peu le parallèle avec des réseaux sociaux. Il y a des applications, comme « Ticket Off », « To see or not to see ». Sans les applications, les spectateurs se retrouvent. Ils peuvent choisir le programme, ils ont le catalogue du festival dessus, ils peuvent choisir leurs spectacles, ils peuvent réserver leurs places. Et après, mettre leurs commentaires. Donc nous, on a la rien pour récupérer ces commentaires. Mais ça c'est le vrai réseau social interne au festival, qui fait la promotion en direct du spectateur au spectateur. Ça complète, c'est une application, c'est du réseau social, mais ça complet le bouche à oreille, ça le remplace parfois. On dit plus j'ai vu « quelque trucs », « vas-y c'est bien », on met « j'ai vu ce spectacle, c'est bien. Vas-y c'est bien ».

[07:26] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : C'est exactement ce que j'ai fait ce matin.

[07:29] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : C'est le réseau social qui est utilisé comme ça.

[07:31] L'auteur : Est-ce que les comptes Avignon qui existent déjà facilitent les gens qui veulent laisser des commentaires ?

[07:43] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Il y a « Ticket Off ». « To see or not to see ». « Ticket Off », c'est pour acheter les billets. « To see or not to see », c'est pour parler des spectacles. Ça c'est le terme de « Festival Off ». To see or not to see, ça fait partie du Off ouais. Ça fait trois, quatre ans maintenant. C'est le catalogue que vous avez le « e-catalogue », il est sur un application.

[08:18] L'auteur : Ce n'est pas le mêmes que le Facebook Avignon Off ?

[08:20] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Ce n'est pas la même application. Ça c'est juste le compte Facebook du festival. Tout le monde peut mettre un truc dessus, tout le monde peut commenter, ça soit précis pour être vraiment une chose importante. C'est un peu notre communication là-dessus, ou parle nous-mêmes, et entre nous. Cependant, « To see

or not to see », c'est vraiment un truc qui se développe, qui va remplacer, un jour le catalogue.

[08:48] L'auteur : To see or not too see, c'est déjà actif ?

[08:49] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Oui, oui, depuis quatre ans au moins. Et maintenant on l'utilise beaucoup. Voilà. C'est une certaine forme, application, de réseau social en interne quoi.

[09:06] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Il y a un point aussi important, c'est que au théâtre, chacun a sa propre connotation, son propre réseau par rapport aux spectacles qu'ils présentent, et aussi on leurs sites internes et, leur réseaux pour développer les spectacles que chacun présente.

[09:22] L'auteur : Est-ce que dans la création, les artistes pourraient, ou les producteurs pourraient intégrer les réseaux sociaux ? Démarrer par exemple le spectacle par les réseaux sociaux, et continuer les « terrestre » dans le théâtre ou on pourra créer un post commencer à contacter les publics avant d'être en théâtre. Est-ce que pour vous ça vous ça dénaturez tous ?

[09:43] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Je ne pense pas ça denature... C'est quand même le concret et le terrain, qui porte le projet. Aujourd'hui ce qui est virtuel, on le voit bien quand il y a une sortie de film, c'est la promotion, Non le virtuel c'est totalement différent, mais sur la partie artistique... Vous dites spécialement pour Avignon, ou en général ?

[10:04] L'auteur : En Avignon et en général.

[10:06] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Mais on ne peut pas. Si une vraie bonne référence, si une vraie bonne communication, en ce cas, ça porte.

[10:14] L'auteur : Mais ça c'est de la promotion. En création, par exemple, hier j'ai vu un spectacle sur la culture basque. Avoir déjà un démarrage un contact avec le public via les réseaux sociaux avant le spectacle, est-ce que ça pourrez être intégré dans la création ?

[10:28] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Ca peut, mais...

[10:33] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Déjà, l'image de clip. On a un mot peut-être un peu vieillot au théâtre, on appelle ça la « bande-annonce ». C'est du théâtre filmé. Et le théâtre filmé n'est jamais bon.

[10:46] L'auteur : Mais est-ce que les créateurs ne pouvaient pas intégrer autres choses que du théâtre filmé ? C'est-à-dire, une fois Off, une photo... la bande-annonce... Est-ce qu'on pourra démarrer un jour à votre avis la création, par une phrase sur les réseaux sociaux ?

[11:10] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Non. Je ne crois pas. Dans la cadre du spectacle vivant, ce que les gens viennent voir c'est 100% du vivant. Ça ne veut pas dire que la pièce ne peut pas intégrer la vidéo, la musique, voilà, il y a plein de chose comme ça.

[11:16] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Non je ne crois pas.

[11:31] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Ce n'est pas ce que nous préférons. C'est le souhait des spectateurs. Ils viennent voir ceci, à chaque fois ils viennent voir du spectacle vivant.

[11:40] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Qu'est-ce qui porte vraiment c'est ce qu'on dit ce tout le critique en faites. C'est qu'est qui se passe après. Parce qu'avant, c'était très virtuel. Aujourd'hui, l'humain reste le vecteur numéro un.

[11:54] L'auteur : Et avec la promo terrain vous faites le vrai remplissage pour vos spectacles.

[12:02] Professionnel 5 (Producteur) : Oui. Parce que on vie ce qu'on propose. Le fait du vendre pour comment le faire. Tout d'abord, on croit qu'est qu'on vent. Je sais artiste est remarquable en scène, qui a un vrai talent, donc qu'on ne va pas du vendre du vent.

Cependant, qu'elle commence avec un public nombreux sur un projet comme suis-la, je ne suis pas étonné à Avignon, parce qu'il y a bouche-à-oreille qui démarre. Je pense que ça va suivre sur cours, mais pour moi l'humain, la promo sur le terrain joue beaucoup.

[12:39] Professionnel 6 (Diffuseur) : Absolument. Aller tracter ici c'est essentiel ici si on n'est pas complètement efficient sur le tractage, c'est raté. Les spectateurs Avignonnais qui sont à leurs tables des bistrots ou des restaurants de midi, ils veulent parler aux comédiens. On peut même embaucher une équipe quinze tracteurs, ça va être efficace, à

force. Les gens qui sont juste là pour les flyers, on pourrait leur apprendre un petit texte, ça va peut-être marcher. Mais si les comédiens viennent à la table des gens, ça change tout.

CA-4. Professional 7 (Stage Manager, Avignon Village Off, age: 30)

[00:09] L'auteur : On veut juste vous questionner sur le rôle des réseaux sociaux à votre avis en Festival d'Avignon Off. Qu'est-ce que vous en pensez vous votre fenêtre ?

[00:19] Professionnel 7 : Moi, je pense que, en fait c'est une communication qui peut être efficace. Je pense que parfois il est efficace parce que du coup tout le monde maintenant va par exemple sur Facebook, sur Twitter et cherche, avoir tes informations qui sont accessible sur le même endroit. C'est très bien parce que on s'y connaît sur un truc. Pour n'importe quelle personne qui n'a pas accès aux réseaux sociaux justement, c'est un manque d'accès informations en fait. Et du coup, je trouve que c'est bien mais il ne faut pas de contrôle sur dessus.

[00:56] L'auteur : Et aujourd'hui vous trouvez il y a beaucoup de communication sur les réseaux sociaux sur le Off ?

[01:02] Professionnel 7 : Sur le Off, moi, c'est vrai que, j'ai vu pas mal de compagnies avec forcément qui joue. Il y a des messages qu'on cherche, qui vous êtes et tout, mais ce n'est pas parce que c'est moi qui ai choisi les suivre. Après là où l'on trouve la meilleure communication pendant le festival, c'est vraiment les compagnies que l'on croise dans la rue, qui font, soit juste un spectacle pour nous faire envie, ... Je trouve que c'est bien les gestes, ces échanges pendant ce festival. Et en plus, ça permet pour une fois de sortir un peu de ce côté numérique où dans le fond, il y a trop d'informations.

[01:44] L'auteur : Quel est votre rôle au festival ?

[01:46] Professionnel 7 : Moi je suis régisseur au théâtre au Village Off.

[01:54] L'auteur : Donc ça ne vous choque pas que sur la bannière, il n'y a aucune mention de Facebook, Twitter, de QR code, il y a rien ? Il y a que les sponsors à la ligne.

[02:10] Professionnel 7 : Moi ça me choque pas. Si j'avais vu un truc « suivez-nous » ou « restez connectez ».

[02:15] L'auteur : To see or not to see, vous connaissez ce site ?

[02:17] Professionnel 7 : Non. C'est un endroit où les gens peuvent réagir sur leur vision aimé ou n'aimé le spectacle qu'ils ont vu. Il a été lancé il y a quatre ans sur le Off... Moi, je ne suis pas en courant. Je ne suis pas en Avignon depuis longtemps.

[02:33] L'auteur : Vous habitez Avignon ou dans la région ?

[02:36] Professionnel 7 : Non. Je suis de Montpellier. Et là pour le festival, j'y pendant un mois.

[02:43] L'auteur : Vous savez, quand même, il faut rester terre à terre, il faut rester très concret. C'est ça je suis fait l'ADN ?

[02:47] Professionnel 7 : Clairement, c'est comme ça, ce qu'on voit, même si ça nous parle, ou ça nous parle pas, au moins, ça fait vivre le festival. Je pense que c'est typiquement le spectacle, généralement, à voir, mais n'empêche que les voir là comme ça, au moins je sais ce que ça va présenter, et qui est la personne qui joue.

[03:11] L'auteur : Est-ce que la promo en « social media », ça permet son sens, son intérêt ?

[03:16] Professionnel 7 : Ouais, c'est, surtout, qu'en fait, ça fait vraiment. Moi je trouve vraiment ce qui est marrant, c'est le fait qu'on a, dans la ville, il y a toutes ces affiches, tous ces gens tout le temps en train de tracter, nous parler de spectacle. Et en fait, c'est dommage parce que je pense que ça avec les réseaux sociaux serait juste Avignon « classique » justement.

CA-5. Professional 8 (Film Youtuber, age: 36) from Avignon (FR)

[00:02] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous avez l'habitude d'utiliser Facebook, Twitter, Youtube, Instagram ?

[00:07] Professionnel 8 : Oui.

[00:29] L'auteur : Je sais ce que vous faites, vous êtes plutôt une référence sur Youtube pour certaines de choses, est-ce que ici vous venez en tant que professionnel, ou est-ce que vous venez en tant que de visiteur ?

[00:36] Professionnel 8 : Je viens comme une personne qui habite à Avignon, donc oui, oui, je ne suis absolument pas venu au festival par les réseaux.

[00:49] L'auteur : Donc vous venez comme un voisin, et vous venez en auditeur normal ?

[00:53] Professionnel 8 : Exactement.

[00:54] L'auteur : Qu'est-ce que vous pensez de la présence des réseaux sociaux et de leur utilisation par le OFF ?

[00:59] Professionnel 8 : Je n'ai pas vu quelle était la présentation par les off dans les réseaux sociaux. Je ne sais pas quelle est la stratégie qui est mise en place, donc je ne peux pas en faire l'analyse, mais aujourd'hui c'est essentiel d'utiliser les réseaux sociaux pour certaines professions, c'est sûr.

[01:15] L'auteur : Est-ce qu'ils sont utilisés par les compagnies mais pas par le Off ?

[01:21] Professionnel 8 : Je ne peux pas te dire.

[01:22] L'auteur : Et certains disent, les vieux comme les jeunes (moins de trente ans), que c'est naturel. En fait il y a trop des réseaux sociaux, il faut rester très terrestres ici. C'est le point de vue que vous partagez. L'ADN de Festival Off et de festival d'Avignon, c'est d'abord les affiches les tracts, les comédiens dans les rues.

[01:41] Professionnel 8 : Non, c'est juste comme les affiches, ça c'est juste des outils, et tous les outils pourraient être bien ou mal utilisés. Les réseaux, c'est comme tout, il faut juste arriver à trouver un bon équilibre. C'est sûr si on est en festival, on reste

constamment sur son portable en traversant en les rues. On loupe le festival. Donc, c'est une question juste, une fois, de plus, d'équilibre comme toujours à mon avis.

[02:01] L'auteur : Vous trouvez c'est sous utilisé pour ce que vous en avez vu ?

[02:05] Professionnel 8 : Non, non. Encore une fois, je ne connais pas la stratégie numérique de Festival d' Avignon. Je ne l'ai pas regardé.

[02:10] L'auteur : Quand vous voyez les « banners », les choses comme ça, les tracts, les documents, il y n'a jamais de références, dans 90 % des cas il n'y a aucune référence, ni Twitter, ni Facebook, il n'y a rien.

[02:19] Professionnel 8 : Quelles sont ces références par exemple ?

[02:21] L'auteur : On pourrait avoir, par exemple chaque spectacle pourrait mentionner qu'on peut les suivre sur Facebook, mais ça n'est jamais mentionné. Il y a un site, ou il y a une connexion possible on l'apprend hier qui s'appelle « To see or not to see ». Vous pouvez donner votre avis « émotionnel » mais pas dans une site « officiel ». Il n'y a pas une présence pour les participants qui veulent intervenir. Ils peuvent intervenir sur le Facebook des compagnies ou du spectacle, mais pas vraiment sur le Off. Et les gens disent : « Non, on savait pas en fait ».

[02:52] Professionnel 8 : Mais je ne sais pas parce que je ne connais pas la stratégie qui accompagnait du Off

[03:02] L'auteur : Mais comment vous pourrez récupérer les informations sur le Off ?

[03:04] Professionnel 8 : Je ne les récupère pas en fait. J'habite ici. Je vois quelques pièces, mais je ne suis pas tellement client pour répondre à ces questions.

[03:15] L'auteur : Et la plupart des gens disent ce que vous dites, quand ils sont à Avignon dans le festival, ils sont en fait un mois assez dans les rues... il n'y a pas en fait de place pour les réseaux sociaux

[03:23] Professionnel 8 : Oui, oui, oui. Pour que In du festival ou Off du festival, par rapport aux réseaux sociaux, ça change pas du tout. C'est la même chose.

[03:32] L'auteur : Est-ce que vous pensez que les artistes un jour pourraient commencer un spectacle sur les réseaux sociaux, pas la promo, mais commencer sur les réseaux sociaux, par une petite vidéo, par une bonne sens. Quand les gens achètent un billet, ils commenceraient à avoir le contact avec le spectacle, pas la promo, et le finira après. Est-ce que c'est quelque chose que vous pourriez envisager, vous ?

[03:54] Professionnel 8 : Bien entendu, ouais, ouais, toutes les formes culturelles sont évoluées devient hybride, d'une manière d'une autre. Bien sûr pour moi, j'ai un souci de la distinction entre la vraie vie et le virtuel. Pour moi, le virtuel, ça labélise le réel reste par l'impact des communications. Il y a certaines formes qui vont devenir hybride, il y a entendu qu'on pourrait imaginer la manière de faire des interactions entre de théâtre classique et une présence sur la réseau, en streaming ou en transmission direct, les gens qui sont derrière, on pourrait tout faire dans ce cas, ouais.

[05:36] L'auteur : De 25 jusqu'à 70 ans. Et vraiment, c'est quasiment blocage partout.

[05:41] Professionnel 8 : Ouais, une fois encore, je ne pense pas que ça devient juste la norme, mais entendu, ça restera majoritairement dans le théâtre, théâtrale traditionnel théâtre, encore une fois à la marge. Aucun soucis avec l'idée d'être pionnier. Au contraire, c'est intéressant de voir comment ça interagir avec d'autres manières.

5.1.1.1. Edinburgh Fringe

**AE-1. Spectator 1 (M) & 2 (F), a couple from Manchester (UK)
(age: 60/70)**

[00:01] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:06] Spectator 1 (M): No. Not at all.

[00:15] The author: Do you use social media to prepare your coming?

[00:22] Spectator 1 (M): We use social media to come. My wife did it.

[00:27] The author: So what kind of social media (do you use)?

[00:32] Spectator 1 (M): Facebook.

[00:45] The author: Do you think the social media of Edinburg (Fringe) is useful?

[00:51] Spectator 1 (M): Yes, quite useful.

[00:55] The author: In terms of which kinds of aspect? For example, (it's useful for you) to prepare (for this trip), to know more about the program or to know more about the events?

[01:10] Spectator 1 (M): Yeah definitely, definitely. Before we go for a show, we always review on the social media.

[01:18] The author: Do you use more their app or (directly) on their social media?

[01:23] Spectator 1 (M): Social media. We use... Facebook to find that.

[01:36] The author: What kind of additional information you would like to receive from their Facebook or from their social media?

[01:46] Spectator 1 (M): Non. I don't like social media.

[01:49] The author: So how do you get information (for the festival) for example?

[02:00] Spectator 1 (M): I don't do Facebook. If I want to know something... I don't like to let the people know what I'm doing. I don't like... I think it's too intrusive. People know where you are and know what you're doing. I don't like it. If I want to see something, I just go on and look at the things.

[02:22] The author: Did you visit each venue's website for doing your selection?

[02:30] Spectator 1 (M): We spent a while at the vary spaces to look for reviews. And If I want something, I just search something that I'm interested in. And That's it. Above that, I don't do Facebook. (I) don't tell anybody anything.

[02:46] The author: Did you use a specific platform to have all the information?

[02:53] Spectator 1 (M): For my information, I use Google.

[03:06] The author: Do you think it's possible that one day a (live) show, which might start from the social media, or the show might be prolonged after the live show thanks to social media? That means social media becomes a part of the creation of the show, which is not just like teaser...

[03:35] Spectator 1 (M): Yeah, I think it could start from social media now, doesn't it? Especially the kids like your age... Well, I just don't follow it on social media. Person like you will watch everything on the iPad. He doesn't watch TV.

[04:13] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[04:15] Spectator 2 (F): Yes. Quite a lot. A couple of hours... around 2 hours per day.

[04:27] The author: Which kind of platform do you use mostly?

[04:29] Spectator 2 (F): Mainly Facebook, and a little bit Twitter, Instagram tiny bit.

[04:34] The author: Do you use social media to prepare for your coming to Edinburgh?

[04:39] Spectator 2 (F): Definitely yes. For reviews as well as the things. Yeah.

[04:43] The author: Are you a local here?

[04:44] Spectator 2 (F): No, I'm from Manchester.

[04:55] The author: Do you think the social media of Edinburgh (Fringe) is quite useful for your preparation and for everything, any kind of information to help you?

[05:06] Spectator 2 (F): Definitely, yes. Definitely.

[05:08] The author: Which kind of contents are specifically helpful for you?

[05:11] Spectator 2 (F): Twitter probably... Twitter is good for the Fringe. We've come especially for the Fringe Festival. So it's very useful for finding and knowing (whether) the shows are good or bad. That's mainly what it is.

[05:25] The author: Reviews you mean?

[05:26] Spectator 2 (F): Yes, yes.

[05:30] The author: I heard that (Edinburgh) Fringe has its own app?

[05:33] Spectator 2 (F): Yes. I do use that as well. It's really good, too. Yes.

[05:36] The author: So you did the both?

[05:37] Spectator 2 (F): Yes, I did the both. It's everything.

[05:43] The author: What kind of additional information you would like to receive thanks to social media? ... What kind of additional contents might be a plus for you in its social media in the future?

[06:12] Spectator 2 (F): I don't think it could be. This is enough for me, for me anyway.

[06:19] The author: Is this your first time to come to Edinburg (Fringe)?

[06:21] Spectator 2 (F): No, we came last year. This is the second time.

[06:24] The author: Do you enjoy a lot?

[06:25] Spectator 2 (F): Yes, we like the theater very much, so we came especially for the theater.

[06:31] The author: Do you think it's possible that social media is truly engaged into the creation of a show? For example, the show might be started much earlier than the live show, which means that the audiences might receive a small video after they book the tickets?

[06:51] Spectator 2 (F): Oh, definitely.

[06:53] The author: Or it might be longer after the live show, and you get more clues, and you will have another perspective of the show, do you think it's possible?

[07:02] Spectator 2 (F): Yes, yes, yes, yes, yes!

[07:11] The author: Do you think it (the show) might be more interesting? Or what's your feeling about this if it really comes true? Is it more attractive for you?

[07:20] Spectator 2 (F): We want to see the actual live show.

[07:39] The author: Normally, the show starts when you get in the theatre and ends when you get out. But what if the show starts earlier or finish later thanks to social media?

[07:55] You mean it's a longer show, right?

[07:56] Yes, yes. So what do you think about the potential of this kind of new form?

[08:00] Spectator 2 (F): Well, it is very clever. Yes. By being out there, everybody can see it. You can learn from it.

[08:10] The author: Does it might enrich your experiences?

[08:12] Spectator 2 (F): Possibly yeah, yes, yes, yeah.

AE-2. Spectator 3 (F, age: 15/20), 4 (F, age: 55), 5 (F, age: 15/20) from Glasgow (UK)

[00:02] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:07] Spectator 3 (F): Yes. Yes.

[00:10] The author: What kind of social media specifically?

[00:13] Spectator 3 (F): I'm mostly use Instagram, but sometimes I use a little bit of Twitter as well.

[00:20] The author: How about you?

[00:23] Spectator 4 (F): Facebook.

[00:26] Spectator 5 (F): I mostly use Instagram as well.

[00:31] The author: Do you use social media to prepare your coming to Edinburgh?

[00:36] Spectator 3 (F): Sometimes, yeah. I mean, if it's like planning with friends, mostly just like getting organized, like people that were coming with, but that's about it.

[00:47] The author: Did you see some reviews (on social media)?

[00:52] Spectator 3 (F): We use the catalog actually. So like, we didn't really look on online for it much. We mostly just use the catalog.

[01:06] The author: And how about you?

[01:10] Spectator 4 (F): Oh, for preparing for social media?

[01:12] The author: Yeah. Do you use social media to prepare your coming to Edinburg Fringe?

[01:15] Spectator 4 (F): No. Just the internet, yeah. The Edinburgh website, yeah, Edinburgh Festival website... No blogs, just the official website.

[01:28] Spectator 5 (F): I mean, we looked at the catalog as well, just like my mom brought home the book, so I shall look at that.

[01:39] The author: Do you think social media of Edinburgh Fringe is useful?

[01:45] Spectator 3 (F): It might be for others. But I didn't really have too much of a look to say. So I can't really say.

[01:55] Spectator 4 (F): I didn't use it. So I don't need it.

[01:57] Spectator 5 (F): I didn't really use it either. But I think it could be useful.

[02:00] The author: I heard the application (of Fringe) is super useful for some of the people...

[02:07] Spectator 4 (F): We didn't use it. We just used the internet and got everything there. And also, we looked at the catalog. So the catalog for me was what made me decide. The big book made me decide to everything so keep the catalog going. I like the catalog.

[02:24] The author: What kind of additional information do you want from the social media of Edinburgh Fringe, which might makes it more useful for you?

[02:36] Spectator 3 (F): I'd say maybe directions to... I'm not sure if it already provides directions, but I'd say directions to the venues and stuff. And like the week dates... and

just like the certain dates is playing and stuff, and maybe like comments on people who've seen it. So people know what to expect and what people think of it.

[03:02] The author: Yeah. How about you?

[03:03] Spectator 4 (F): Yeah, I think all of this. This is very true and very useful. Yeah.

[03:09] Spectator 5 (F): Yeah. Excellent. And I think reviews would be especially helpful as well.

[03:15] The author: For example, like now, how do you see the reviews if you didn't use the social media? How do you get the information about the reputation of each piece?

[03:28] Spectator 5 (F): I think you have to look at this, because I don't think they have it in the catalog. But few reviews, but not many.

[03:37] The author: Okay, and how did you see saw those reviews?

[03:41] Spectator 5 (F): I just mainly use Google to find them.

[03:47] The author: Do you think it's possible that one day, thanks to the social media, the show starts much earlier than the live show, or maybe, ends much after the live show? For example, like the show may start from a small videos which you will receive once you book a ticket. Thanks to it, you could also know more about the show. Or you might get a small video after the (live) show, which might change your (original) perspective?

[04:24] Spectator 3 (F): I think that would be quite useful. Yeah. I think using like social media and the internet is a good way to do that. Because sometimes with the catalog, you don't really know what you're getting yourself into, you just bet on, you know, whether it's good or not by the title. So I'd say like a short clip of what it's going to be like, could be useful.

[04:45] The author: In this case, social media involves in the creation of the piece and is not just a teaser.

[04:56] Spectator 3 (F): Interaction, interaction! I think that'll be really fun, actually. Yeah, kind of using social media to maybe interact with the actors or people involved. That would be cool.

[05:08] The author: Will it be more interesting for you?

[05:10] Spectator 3 (F): Yeah, it would be more, you get involved more, and you'd feel it more. So I think social media is quite useful for that.

[05:17] Spectator 4 (F): We are the same, we're very much into any positive aspect of social media that you can have people get engaged with the Edinburgh Festival, but we still wanted to attend the live shows. We don't want to do it virtually. We want to be able to come and interact, engage and enjoy. Not just in our bedroom, okay?

[05:40] Spectator 5 (F): And yeah, I think it will make it much more interesting. So when you go see the show, you have an idea of writing, and then someone comes up after it can change your idea.

[05:56] The author: Is this your first time to come here?

[05:58] Spectator 4 (F): No, several times already.

AE-3. Spectator 6 & 7 from Yorkshire (UK) (age: 25/30)

[00:01] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:05] Spectator 6 & 7 (F): Yes, we both do. Yes, we do.

[00:07] The author: What kind of (social media) platforms?

[00:10] Spectator 6 (F): Facebook, Twitter, Instagram to an extent, but not really to be honest. Yeah. Mainly Twitter.

[00:16] Spectator 7 (F): I'll say mainly Twitter. Yeah, maybe a bit of Instagram, but also Facebook as well.

[00:21] The author: What types of content you see on Instagram and Twitter?

[00:26] Spectator 6 (F): A lot of stuff that goes on around here. Actually, I'm constantly on Twitter looking for stuff that's good. And throughout the rest of the following what people are doing. So it's very much a kind of big week when we come because everyone we follow on Twitter comes here, and we get to see them live. So yeah.

[00:44] The author: Do you use social media to prepare your coming to Edinburgh?

[00:49] Spectator 6 (F): Yes, I do. Yes. I do a lot of research on social media and Twitter. Yeah.

[00:52] The author: What kind of dimensions or what kind of information (do you search on social media)?

[00:56] Spectator 6 (F): We use the hashtag “@edfringe” or “Edinburgh Fringe,” and we see who gets good reviews and see people whom we have followed on social media for a while, see what they will do this year. And yeah.

[01:09] Spectator 7 (F): Just see who's popular, to see who's doing really well. And just keep scrolling down and just see what see what comes up.

[01:17] The author: Are you searching mainly for the reviews?

[01:18] Spectator 6 & 7 (F): Yeah.

[01:20] The author: Or any other information?

[01:23] Spectator 6 (F): Just recommendations really. We know someone who I worked with years ago, who comes over regularly. And she's been recommending us a few things. I'm not sure we'll take you upon them because she's got a different sense of humor to us. Yeah, just recommendations from people as well.

[01:38] The author: How about you?

[01:39] Spectator 7 (F): Yeah, personal recommendations. Yeah, I have a few people I work with have been and they put on social media as well. It's just all about word of mouth. And it's not necessarily what's popular, but what's good. So we're trying to look for stuff what people talk what the “buzzes” is really. We look for the “buzzes”. Yeah.

[00:55] The author: What kind of additional information you would like to see more on their social media?

[02:07] Spectator 6 (F): I don't know really. Flyers and things? I don't know.

[02:12] The author: In addition to the reviews, and what kind of information which might make this festival more attractive?

[02:21] Spectator 6 (F): Good question! I don't think there is anything really I mean, as long as you can see what people, how people are doing and how, yeah, that sounds good.

[02:35] The author: How about you?

[02:35] Spectator 7 (F): I think it will be interesting to see how well things are selling before you buy your tickets. Because sometimes you might think oh, God looks good but might be the other two people in the audience. Or you might can think I've just bought the last two tickets, but you obviously don't know, I think be quite nice to see how well a show is sold before I take it because we don't like being in a quiet audience. Neither was like being in a full audience. That makes sense. Yeah.

[02:58] The author: So that means sometimes you get some information on it, but it's not sufficient for you to select good programs.

[03:07] Spectator 7 (F): Yeah, sometimes. Yeah, sometimes.

[03:08] The author: But how could it be improved according to your point of view?

[03:12] Spectator 6 (F): I don't really know. I don't know. I don't know, sorry.

[03:19] The author: Do you think it's possible that one day, the show starts, much before the live show, with a small video which is actually part of the creation of the show. Afterwards, you have a live show. And perhaps in the end, you have another video that helps you to have another perspective, do you think it is possible?

[03:53] Spectator 6 (F): Yes, I do. Yeah. Because it's all I suppose it's all performance at the end of the day, but I think when you come up here, you pay to see live shows really. Obviously, the little bit recorded things do feed into live shows, but I think generally you

would pay to see a live show, not a recording appear. So I think it will be possible, but I don't know how popular it would be.

[04:22] The author: That means thanks to social media, it might be possible. But what's your feeling about this?

[04:34] Spectator 6 (F): I don't know. I think lots of people pay to see the live performances.

[04:40] The author: So personally you prefer to keep the performance from the beginning to the end in the theater?

[04:47] Spectator 6 (F): Yeah. Yeah. Personally yeah. Something kicks up can be a bit of a mean, obviously, depending on what the actual show is about. I think it's better to see a live performance rather than recorded things because it can be a bit, not lazy, but that's not what you paid to see in the end of the day.

[05:05] The author: How about you?

[05:06] Spectator 7 (F): I think we watch enough screens at the rest of the... it's nice to actually see the people in real life rather than watching yet another screen because you spend all the time on the tele or your phone.

[05:17] The author: Do you also prefer to start the show from the beginning to the end in the theater?

[05:23] Spectator 7 (F): Yes. Yes.

[05:46] The author: Spectator 6 & 7 (F): Is this your first time to come here?

[05:47] Spectator 6 & 7 (F): No, it's the fifth time.

[00:54] The author: What makes you come here every year?

[00:55] Spectator 6 (F): We look for Theatre. I used to work in marketing and advertising of a theatre in a small place in my hometown, and a lot of people there like 10 years ago. I used to advertise all the shows and host them. And a lot of people used to come up and do shows here, or they have done and you have to come. It's just something that you cannot do really so.

[01:55] Spectator 6 (F): Theater is so wonderful, isn't it? It so much better than watching TV.

(While the actor, Willy from West end producer appeared in front of us to promote his show...)

[02:55] Spectator 6 (F): I know who you are.

[02:56] Mr. Willy: Oh my, how are you?

[02:59] Spectator 6 (F): I'm following you on your Twitter.

[02:59] Mr. Willy: Do you?

[02:59] Spectator 6 (F): Yes. (I follow) all of your tweets and your Facebook (posts).

AE-4. Spectator 8 from Niigata (JP) (age: 55/60)

[00:05] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:09] Spectator 8 (M): Yeah, yes.

[00:11] The author: What kind of platform?

[00:13] Spectator 8 (M): Just Facebook. Just to show that I'm still alive to my friends, yeah, because I'm far from Japan. So as always, I have to show my face to my Japanese friend to show I'm here and surviving.

[00:35] The author: Do you use social media to prepare your coming for the festival?

[00:42] Spectator 8 (M): No, not at all.

[00:45] The author: But how can you get all the information?

[00:47] Spectator 8 (M): Well, you have the newspaper like The Scotsman, newspaper. Of course sometimes I see some about the reputation of the shows, but I don't use Facebook for this. I use a lot published information, such as catalog, as much as I could.

[01:08] The author: Do you think social media of Edinburgh (Fringe) is useful for you?

[01:16] Spectator 8 (M): That's difficult to say because that I don't use so much about it so I don't know... I just use Facebook. But I don't use it for the Edinburgh (Fringe). No. Not at all.

[01:41] The author: What kind of additional information do you want to have from the social media of Edinburgh Fringe?

[01:57] Spectator 8 (M): It's a difficult question because I don't trust so much about it so... because there are many fake issues, fake information or anything so that's why. I don't believe it so much, and I tried not to read it so much.

[02:24] The author: Do you think it's possible that one day a show it starts from the very beginning, when you just book a ticket, with a small video, which is not an advertisement like a teaser but truly a part of art creation, and after that you come to the (live) show, and maybe it ends much later than the live show?

[03:05] Spectator 8 (M): My preference is (to have this support) before I purchase a ticket because many of the Fringe events are very difficult to understand the content itself from the brochure because many, many shows anyway. What I mean is just a small introduction if they can provide, it's much better of course.

[03:33] The author: Is this the first time you come here?

[03:36] Spectator 8 (M): No, no, no, I'm working and staying here for 15/19 years in Edinburgh. Yeah, so every year I'm coming for 50/60 shows a year here. You can see here... this is my plan, all the dates and the shows I take just, I change every time, every day to see which one I can. The red one I've already done, then because day by day my preference changes based on the brochure and on the information, I try to find out which is the best and try to select them.

[04:19] The author: How do you do the selection?

[04:24] Spectator 8 (M): Yeah, based on this information.

[04:28] The author: Based on the catalog? Where do you get some reviews?

[04:31] Spectator 8 (M): Mainly Scotsman, mainly Scotsman, because it's more trustful. Some other newspaper does not take any words in their reviews. In addition, my taste is quite closer to the selection made by Scotsman. That's why I choose it. So every morning I have to buy and check it for around three weeks.

AE-5. Spectator 9 from Manchester (UK) (age: 55/60)

[00:02] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:05] Spectator 9 (F): Yes.

[00:07] The author: What kind of platform specifically?

[00:09] Spectator 9 (F): Instagram, Twitter and Facebook.

[00:12] The author: What kind of contents for each platform?

[00:15] Spectator 9 (F): Instagram for Instagram stories. Facebook for finding out information. And Twitter for conversation, really, I find it easy, with friends and comedians and people who are going to see at the Fringe yet.

[00:34] The author: Do you use social media to prepare for your coming to Edinburgh?

[00:39] Spectator 9 (F): Yes. Yes, I do, I promote the shows that I'm coming to see. So I will tweet about whom I'm booked the tickets for, and I will tweet about when they are. So I will spread the word of, and I will give reviews as well. So I will review the show after I've been to, to help spread the word again.

[01:01] The author: You're an active user!

[01:04] Spectator 9 (F): Probably not as active as many people but I'm quite active yeah.

[01:09] The author: In addition to posting your reviews and the information via your own personal accounts, do you also post them in other type of platforms or review (platforms)?

[01:21] Spectator 9 (F): No, not really. I just post them on my personal Instagram and social media feeds. Yeah. I don't have a public review sites or anything like that. No, just my normal personal social media.

[01:40] The author: Do you think the social media of Edinburgh Fringe is useful for you?

[01:46] Spectator 9 (F): Yes, yes, because it's quite easy when you're on the go to find out what any, any extra information that you may have missed. But also know, in a way, because again, there is so much to find out, that can be a bit overwhelming at times. So I think unless you kind of know where to look, it could be quite a lot to take in. So unless you knew that the sites to go to.

[02:15] The author: So for you, there are lots of, lots of information on social media. And is it sometimes a bit difficult for you to find the information which you want?

[02:23] Spectator 9 (F): Yes. And I actually tend to go to the people that I'm actually going to see to find out information that way. Because it narrows it down a little bit more so that if it's a comedian, I know that I'm going to see, I will go to their sites to find out the information. It's much easier, if that makes sense.

[02:42] The author: Now you know about the social media of Edinburgh Fringe, and what kind of additional information you would like to know more on their social media, which might make the social media more attractive or more practical for you to use?

[03:03] Spectator 9 (F): I think possibly have more of the links to the people as well, not just a slight have the general venue information, but that the links, because as I said, I tend to go to the comedians and the shows that I'm going to see first. And if those links are available on the other social media sites that might make it look a bit easier.

[03:41] The author: But normally Edinburgh Fringe doesn't share any link...?

[03:46] Spectator 9 (F): No, not necessarily. It's just, it's obviously just the poster information that users have tend to get really. So unless it's on the poster. Okay. You wouldn't know really where else to look. I don't think. If that makes sense as well. I think I would probably say maybe have more links available... I think that would be the first thing many, I think would be perhaps to have more links available, I think.

[04:21] The author: And did you participate in also a lot of events of Edinburgh Fringe?

[04:27] Spectator 9 (F): Yes. quite quite quite a lot, comedy shows tend to be what I tend to watch. I've also seen some music shows and a few plays as well. But it's mostly standard comedy is what I come to see.

[04:42] The author: Do you as well prefer to have more links to go to their social media accounts?

[04:45] Spectator 9 (F): Yeah, I think so. I think so. And I think particularly for people who wouldn't know, I think that would be helpful. Yeah.

[04:57] The author: Do you think is possible that one day, a show, which actually start much earlier than a live show. For example, after you pay the ticket, you get a small video, which is not a teaser but truly a part of the creation of the art... And after that you have a live show. And maybe also after the live show, you have another hint from the production, which might change your feeling and your perspective of the whole projects?

[05:39] Spectator 9 (F): I think that could be a good idea, because it could give you the flavor of the show. So if you might not have perhaps gone to see it. Otherwise, you might think about going to see it again. Because sometimes you take a risk on some shows that you don't know anything about. And so maybe to have those clips available.

[06:00] The author: Does this (situation) happen in Edinburgh Fringe also?

[06:01] Spectator 9 (F): Oh, yeah. Yeah, yes.

[06:03] The author: Do you currently feel either online or offline information is sufficient for you to do your selection?

[06:13] Spectator 9 (F): No, and I think sometimes with flyers as well, people just sometimes telling you who it is and the time, and they kind of just hand it to you very quickly. Okay. And of course, everybody is moving very quickly.

[06:25] The author: So there's less people here who truly do some small performances in the streets...

[06:31] Spectator 9 (F): And yeah, I think so. And I think maybe just to have that more of that background information on the streets as well. I think that would be quite helpful. Just to have the time to interact a bit more. I think.

[06:42] The author: Do the people who promotes the shows mostly just give you the flyers?

[06:45] Spectator 9 (F): But that's been my experience. Yes. Yeah. I know. It's kind of to me. I don't think they've promoted it, probably, enough for me to maybe go and see it.

[06:55] The author: And are you a first-comer of the Edinburgh Fringe?

[06:57] Spectator 9 (F): No, no, this is my 10th time.

[07:12] The author: So for you. We don't have so much artist or performer they act, they play and interact with the people when they are having lunch?

[07:25] Spectator 9 (F): I think so. I think it's nice to get that connection. I think that's how the audience is filled in my eyes. I think if you've got that connection with the performer, yeah, it sort of helps. So I think that's how they can promote and spread the word a bit better. Because once you've had that experience, you can then tell somebody else. Yeah. So I think that helps.

[07:48] The author: Are you working in communication industry?

[07:51] Spectator 9 (F): No, I work as a teacher, primary school teacher. I also volunteer at my local theater. I live in Bury, which is near Manchester. Just like I said, customer services advice from to house helper, really. And so yeah, I kind of do that as a sort of extra hobby, really.

[08:23] The author: And what makes you come here every year?

[08:25] Spectator 9 (F): Atmosphere, I think. Just sort of keep track of the comedians that I see and see how they're progressing and follow their careers really.

[08:37] The author: But I observed that actually in Edinburg, everything is so separated, and at which moment you feel the emotion or atmosphere is the strongest?

[08:49] Spectator 9 (F): I think probably when you are absorbed in the show and I think for this smaller venues that you can get an Edinburgh that helps. And I quite, that's what I do quite like Edinburgh with those small venues to get that, more of a contact in the actual performance itself. In a big venue. Sometimes you lose, you lose that atmosphere.

[09:13] The author: Are you agree that the atmosphere you mean is the one in the theater rather than out of the theatre?

[09:19] Spectator 9 (F): Yes, when you're actually there watching the performance. Yeah.

AE-6. Spectator 10 from Ireland (UK) (age: 25/30)

[00:04] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:09] Spectator 10 (F): Yes, I do.

[00:08] The author: What kind of (social media) platforms (do you use) specifically?

[00:13] Spectator 10 (F): Probably Facebook and Twitter.

[00:16] The author: Do you have different use for different platforms?

[00:18] Spectator 10 (F): Yeah, I use Facebook with friends. Twitter I just read, and I don't put anything on it.

[00:24] The author: Do you use social media to prepare for your coming to Edinburgh?

[00:30] Spectator 10 (F): Yes, I looked up reviews on Twitter and found the shows that I got to see.

[00:38] The author: Do you do any other thing (on social media) in addition to reading the reviews?

[00:43] Spectator 10 (F): No. If I follow certain comedians that I probably will see here, yes.

[00:48] The author: So you also follow the news on their Facebook?

[00:52] Spectator 10 (F): Yeah, mainly on Twitter. Yep.

[00:55] The author: Do you think social media of Edinburgh Fringe is useful for you?

[01:01] Spectator 10 (F): Yeah, it's been useful. I find different things to see that I wouldn't have seen normally. Yeah.

[01:07] The author: What's the usage of social media of Edinburgh Fringe for you?

[01:12] Spectator 10 (F): You can search the hashtag on Twitter, and you can see what people are doing. So you can spot things.

[01:18] The author: Can you find everything quite quickly there?

[01:19] Spectator 10 (F): Yeah!

[01:23] The author: You knew already the social media of Edinburgh Fringe this year. And what kind of additional information you would like to get, which might make the social media more attractive to you as a user?

[01:38] Spectator 10 (F): Maybe some of the free shows more, so. Maybe some food places or different things. It's just so much going on so it's hard to know how much more you can put online. But yeah, that's probably yes.

[01:50] The author: Didn't Edinburgh Fringe put anything (on social media) in terms of food and reduction?

[01:55] Spectator 10 (F): I didn't notice, it was more about the shows which I want to do.

[02:00] The author: Do you think it's possible, one day, the show will start much earlier than a live show. For example, like after booking the ticket, you get right

away a small video, which is not a teaser but a part of the creation of the art. What's the potential of this?

[02:31] Spectator 10 (F): It's possible because you get an idea of what the show is about and get an idea what to think about. Yeah, it'll be an interesting idea to try.

[02:38] The author: Will it be helpful?

[02:40] Spectator 10 (F): Yeah, it will give you an idea. Yeah. It will be good to make you think before you see the show, I guess. Yes.

[02:45] The author: Now, even if we have all the information on flyers and on social media currently, is it still not enough for you to select (the shows)?

[02:52] Spectator 10 (F): Flyers or how to keep a track off because they are just coming at you everywhere. It might catch your attention more.

[03:00] The author: Basically, do you agree that you didn't read the flyers?

[03:02] Spectator 10 (F): Some of them, but there are still too many of them. Like, sheer amount of papers.

[03:06] The author: You have all the similar flyers. How can you do your selection (of the shows) based on them?

[03:13] Spectator 10 (F): There's just so many. There's too many. You just take them. I did read some of them, but I haven't done for the cards which could not catch my attention.

[03:19] The author: How do you select all your shows?

[03:23] Spectator 10 (F): Because I probably know a lot of the comedians, I have them actually on Twitter, yes.

[03:29] The author: Don't you take the risk to do your selection?

[03:30] Spectator 10 (F): No, it's my first time here. Next year maybe but not this year

[03:42] The author: Do you like Edinburgh Fringe?

[03:43] Spectator 10 (F): Yeah, it's good. It's bad it's so busy. But yeah, no, it's good.

[03:46] The author: Does communication or everything go well here?

[03:50] Spectator 10 (F): Yeah, it's easy enough to speak English. Everything starts on time and it's very well organized and have signposts.

[04:00] The author: Will you come here next year?

[04:02] Spectator 10 (F): Hopefully, yes.

AE-7. Spectator 11 (M) from Edinburgh (age: 75/80)

As a participant of Edinburgh Fringe for over 25 years, he thought that Fringe's quality has maintained at a nice level. He has the impression that the ticket this year is cheaper than usual. He could not tell the big change during this 25 years in the festival maybe because he hasn't seen the shows intensively. His wife tends to use social media, but he doesn't use social media at all. His methodology of choosing the shows is mainly by checking the big catalog. The most emotional moment in Edinburgh Fringe he got while he saw a show presented in King's theater once.

AE-8. Spectator 12 from Manchester/London (UK) (age: 55)

[00:01] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:06] Spectator 12 (M): Yes. For Instagram just not much, kind of mainly looking at... I put up pictures and stuff on Instagram. Yeah.

[00:16] The author: Do you have different usage on Facebook and on Instagram?

[00:20] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah, Instagram, I just do nice pictures and stuff, whereas Facebook tends to be more kind of political, kind of debating, kind of... it feels like they're two separate places. All my friends who are on Facebook say that they all keep Instagram very nice and lovely. A peaceful version of the world. Facebook looks like a terrible version. You have two views at the same thing basically.

[00:56] The author: Do you use social media to prepare for your coming to Edinburgh?

[01:02] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah. With friends and stuff we use WhatsApp, Messenger and Facebook. And yeah, so we use it a lot with my friends who are here will post on Facebook, where we are and stuff. There's a lot of us coming from all over... We use social media on status updates and messenger as well. We also tend to use WhatsApp as well. We've got a couple of separate groups and stuff, but we got whatsapp group as well.

[01:38] The author: So what are you looking for on social media?

[01:45] Spectator 12 (M): I do like lots of theaters in London. I see which my friends are here and which shows because they promote their shows in London. I'm living in London, and I'm from Manchester. Edinburgh Fringe is amazing, I like it. I came last year, and I loved it. So yeah, coming back again.

[02:22] The author: Did you use the social media to see the program?

[02:27] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah. And to see what friends do I know who in shows they promote their show. So I know who's here and stuff.

[02:40] The author: Do you think social media of Edinburgh Fringe is useful?

[02:48] Spectator 12 (M): Yes, but I'm using WhatsApp more with my friends, which is a local group. Less and less Facebook as it was a few years ago. But yeah, I still see the status updates.

[03:07] The author: Do you know Edinburgh Fringe has the official (social media) accounts?

[03:08] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah. Yeah. So I followed the both on Instagram and Facebook, yeah.

[03:19] The author: What kind of additional information you would like to know from the social media accounts of Edinburgh Fringe, which could make it more attractive and useful?

[03:40] Spectator 12 (M): I think the problem of Facebook, what's happening now, it seems to filter to my opinions and my thoughts. So what I don't see is something that I wouldn't normally see. Everything that I'm looking for tends to be something that I've searched and things that I'm looking for. I don't get many surprises on Facebook. I get more surprises walking around and someone handed me a flyer than on Facebook. Well, on Facebook, it's tends to work that what you look at, and what you're searching, what your friends who all have similar opinions. When I was here, somebody coming up to me, a random person. I get completely random ideas thrown at me. So that's why I like the flyer which is good in the stuff.

[04:31] The author: How could the social media (of Edinburgh Fringe) be improved?

[04:37] Spectator 12 (M): I think I didn't see a lot of things like podcasts and stuff like that. I think they could do more podcasts and lead up to the nightly shows and stuff. And just like more review shows, and that kind of thing.

[04:54] The author: Do people basically promote their shows by the critics, the stars and the comments from the audiences?

[05:03] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah, I mean, word of mouth happens a lot here. And if I'm that's on Facebook, then my friends will say I've seen this, you must see this. So that happens quite a lot on Facebook.

[05:15] The author: But it's not on the official account...

[05:16] Spectator 12 (M): No, that's just like people just putting status updates.

[05:20] The author: Does it (Fringe) have the online space for word of mouth, like an E-EOM?

[05:28] Spectator 12 (M): I don't know. I mean, probably there is but I'm not in any forum or anything.

[5:37] The author: Do you think it's possible like one day, we start the show much earlier in a (live) show? For example, when you book your ticket, Fringe might use

its social media to send you a small video, which is not a teaser but kind of part of the creation of the art?

[06:14] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah, so it's more like a multimedia, kind of. I think that certain play could do that with podcasts and videos and to make a more immersive kind of... depends what the subject is, if it's a subject that's quite detailed and stuff, I think that podcaster is really useful because you could listen to it on the train coming up, and video's good but I like podcast and spoken words. I just think it's really intimate, and you can listen to it on the train whereas the videos, I don't watch a lot of videos on my phone... I think that the video sometimes, it just goes over your head because it's just like a flash. Whereas when it's a podcast, you actually sat down and you're listening in while video is... I don't watch that much kind of YouTube and stuff like that. I don't watch a lot of the videos that come up and when they tend to come up on Facebook, I tend to like to scroll up quickly on videos, same with Instagram stories. I don't really click on them because sometimes they just too long, and I just get bored.

[07:33] The author: And how about Facebook Live?

[07:37] Spectator 12 (M): Facebook Live seems to have died to death with my friends. They were there all day. I'm sure lots of people are still did it. Well, I can go while ago that everybody seems to be doing it. But yeah, I've not seen it.

[07:48] The author: Is that mostly the influencers do Facebook Live?

[07:50] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah. Yeah. I don't follow a lot of those influencers. Because I have a girl who's been 19. And she is constantly following stuff on camera behind which she sees on Snapchat. And she seems to be more video-based. I'm a bit older. That's probably where they grew up with the televisions 24 hours a day. Yeah. So it could be just a generation thing. Yeah.

[08:32] The author: Is there anything specifically different this year from the last year's edition?

[08:43] Spectator 12 (M): To me, it seems to me fairly familiar, which is what I like about it... I tend to use the app more than the program. I find my program is just like a

big telephone directory. So I've got the Fringe app. Now I can just go near me. And it will show me everything close to me.

[09:20] The author: Is it (the app) quite efficient for you?

[09:22] Spectator 12 (M): Yeah, I can search by, and I can filter it...

[09:27] The author: Where can you find the reviews?

[09:30] Spectator 12 (M): They don't have the reviews. It's purely... actually they do on the show. I think keep they go nearby now, I think if you click on the show, you might find some details or reviews. The app is really useful so I'm using the app more than the big catalog. It's just so easy to search. But you have no way to know what's happening now. It's just a list of show...

[10:05] The author: Did you do your selection far before your coming?

[10:08] Spectator 12 (M): No, (it's a) mixture. So we, my friends and I, tend to just book maybe one thing a day, but most things we don't (book them before). What we hear, someone will hang out his flyer. Somebody would tell us about something that they say last year happened a couple of times where people say you must see this amazing.

AE-9. Spectator 13 from Dublin (UK) (age: 24)

[00:17] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:22] Spectator 13 (F): Yes, I do.

[00:24] The author: What kind of platform specifically? What are the contents you post for each platform?

[00:31] Spectator 13 (F): I use Instagram, Facebook, Twitter. YouTube, Reddit, Twitch and Discord. Twitch is a streaming like a gamer. People will just stream, live streams, generally for games and stuff. The last one is Discord, which lets you have communities that you're interested in, sort of a forum. So I mainly use them for. YouTube, I just have a lot of YouTubers that I like to watch, lots of videos and stuff to watch. I don't really post

my own content. It's more like consume other people's content. And like keep up to date with news and stuff. Facebook, I don't really use it. It's only for university. So I can have messenger and assignments. I don't really use it at all anymore. I used to a lot but not anymore. Yeah. Instagram, I'm posting photos, my holiday and stuff. But you know... I do post every couple of days just while I'm on holiday, but usually I don't really use it. I look at other people's stuff. And then Twitter I just follow comedians, people who are in the fringe.

[02:25] The author: Do you use social media to prepare your coming to Edinburgh for this festival?

[02:33] Spectator 13 (F): Yes, yeah. So I was already following a couple of comedians and people who I liked in general, and then when I knew I was coming here, I would like look on their social media to see who they recommended for other shows to go to. I also followed the fringe on Twitter, and to find out information about where to go, things to do, tips and stuff like that.

[02:57] The author: Are the comedians you follow more local or international base?

[03:02] Spectator 13 (F): Comedian I mainly for was Sophie Hagen, she's from Denmark. I think she loves and lives in London. She was the main person I followed. And then she just recommended a bunch of people. So I would like follow them and get tickets to go see their shows as well... Sophie Hagen is an international artists whom I follow. Yeah.

[03:41] The author: Do you think social media of Edinburgh (Fringe) is useful?

[03:47] Spectator 13 (F): Yeah, definitely. Fringe's Twitter account is really good. They have like a lot of info, including ticket collections and mainly informative things about the logistics and how to do things. Yeah, it's good. But I don't really follow Edinburgh as a city itself, but I follow the festival. And they (Fringe's social media) are quite useful.

[04:12] The author: What's the difference between the official accounts of Edinburgh (Fringe) of Facebook and Twitter?

[04:20] Spectator 13 (F): I only follow them on Twitter. I haven't really seen them on Facebook... Just because I don't use Facebook that much. Facebook is more for old

people to use. And I'm more often on Twitter. So it's easier to see... the way Facebook's used that if you're posting more than once a day, it can get really annoying for a Facebook page. But Twitter, you can post regularly and post as much as you want. And it won't annoy someone. If the Fringe is posting on Twitter, they can post a lot, and it's fine. But if I was on Facebook, and they were posting a bunch, that would be annoying because I don't want to see these. Different platforms have different uses. And it's more acceptable on Twitter to post more often and provide more information.

[05:14] The author: Is it because Twitter is more like a conversation?

[05:18] Spectator 13 (F): Sort of. And just because the timeline itself is constantly refreshing if you're following a lot of people on Twitter. It moves so quickly, and the content moves so quickly that you almost need to post a lot to make sure that your contents to be seen. But the way Facebook's timeline is set up is that you can see the same thing over and over and over and over again. So you don't need to post a lot... Twitter I need them to posting a lot; otherwise, I'm not gonna see anything, I'm gonna miss it, and I'm going to miss out on things.

[05:59] The author: What kind of information you would like to know more in the future on Fringe's social media, which might make the festival more attractive and more user-friendly for the online visitors?

[06:24] Spectator 13 (F): Fringe's Twitter account will just post links to things. But I don't always want to click through to a link to find out more, I want the information there in the tweet. In the Fringe, the tweet will be: this is happening at the fringe, click through to find out more information." But I almost want the tweet to tell me, for example, where the half price hut and the locations are rather than having to click and find out more. Clicking takes you out of the app and out of the experience. I really like the account but it would be even better if the tweets had more information within the tweet itself, rather than just a link to something.

[07:07] The author: I think sometimes it might be because of the limitation of the characters...

[07:12] Spectator 13 (F): Yeah, I'm sure it is. But because you have the option to tweet more often, there's potentially the opportunity to have some tweets that are more informative. I've seen the ones that they do like the bad joke Friday is really funny, and I enjoy that. But like every once in a while, it'd be nice to have like a reminder, this is where the location is. I'm not your social media person. But like, that's, it's definitely there's limitations and everything. But if there was anything to change, it would be to make things a little bit more in the tweet rather than just on a link.

[07:49] The author: Do you think it's possible to use live or stories (to cover the part you said)?

[08:11] Spectator 13 (F): I think it does if you've got lots of followers and stuff. The tricky thing about live is that people might not be online and in different time zones. If most people are in Edinburgh for the festival, then you don't have to worry about time zones and everything. But live are tricky because the person who's doing the live, who's filming themselves, they might be waiting or be slow. And you're watching them on their live. They're not telling me what I want. And I'm just going to click off. They're not entertaining enough, or they're too quick. I think you need to find the right person to be your spokesperson for the live if you want to be good, or show some which is really useful. And then pinning that tweet, making it or like retweeting it a bunch so that we went live, here's this info. I think they are useful, but I'm not a huge fan of live.

[9:17] The author: Do you think Edinburgh Fringe is compatible with this kind of live Facebook, live Twitter or stories of Instagram?

[9:26] Spectator 13 (F): Yeah, I think there's an opportunity to show locations by this. I mean, it would be really cool to show in stories or in live because some of the venues are a little bit confusing. Although they've got really good signage and everything, sometimes if you're new to the city, and you're like, "Oh my gosh, where shall I go?" "Where's the venue?" ... a live or Instagram stories where you show that "Hey, if you're coming on to this venue, this is where everything is," that would be really useful. And people might really enjoy that.

[10:00] The author: Didn't Fringe do it at all?

Spectator 13 (F): No, I haven't seen it. They might, but I haven't seen it. I'm not sure. I don't think they do it currently, yeah.

[10:15] The author: Do you think is possible one day, we start the show from a small video on the social media while you book the ticket, which is not a teaser but part of the art creation. Do you think it's attractive for you? What's the potential of this new art form?

[11:13] Spectator 13 (F): I think it depends on the show, depends on the creators and depends on the performer... I think some shows that could be really good, but some shows that might not be suitable for the medium or for the stories they're trying to tell... It's something I'd be interested in. If I was buying the ticket, and description told me that part of the show is online or whatever, I'd be definitely interested in.

[11:40] The author: Do you think it's more immersive?

[11:42] Spectator 13 (F): It could be, yeah, it's definitely an option. I think that you just don't want it to be a gimmick, and that you want it to be good. But yeah, it's an option. I think it's really interesting if it happened.

[12:00] The author: You have so many support, offline support with a big catalog. You have flyers everywhere, which have lots of the remarks from the press with the star scoring system. For you personally, you have a limited of time (here). How do you do your selections?

[12:23] Spectator 13 (F): My initial selections were recommendations from the comedians and the people I followed. When I got here, I am just getting flyers, and then I would look and anything that caught my eyes. I went to a few shows that were interesting but they weren't my favorite. But I was like, okay, that's interesting. So then I will keep an eye out for the posters that are highly rated. I went to a show, and there was only 11 people in the audience. Even if it was a fun show, I felt awkward. I'm just like, "Oh, no, there's not enough people in the audience today, I don't want to be interactive. I don't want to interact." So I did like the flyers and so from now. Flyers plus a good writing allows me to know whether it's slightly more popular. I'm not here long enough, and I don't have enough money to take a chance on every single show. So I'm going to filter it

by seeing the posters and everything. If it's a bigger poster, I suppose that it must be probably a better show, because they have got more money to spend on a bigger poster. And then, if I've got lots of stars, ratings and everything, I suppose that they must be well-received, and that there are more people there. This is something that's worth spending my time and money on. If I was here for the whole festival, I would just go to whatever shows, it wouldn't matter. But because I'm only here for a week, and I've got limited budget and limited time. I am trying to be selective by flyers and writings.

[14:02] The author: But there's not so much the flow between the digital and non-digital, for example, like on the poster, you might have a small QR code that can brings you to the digital part, which might have a specific effect (for your experience).

[14:18] Spectator 13 (F): Not as much for me because I cost money to have telecom and Internet service right now. I don't have a UK data plan. I'm using roaming, which costs me extra to use my phone. I only use my phone if I have free Wi Fi or if I'm lost, and I'm using Google Maps to try and find stuff. If I'm not here, then I'd be able to be all in digital. But while I'm here, I'm not so much to have a lot of flow between offline and online. Because I can't afford.

[14:49] The author: What do you think the potential of this new type of communication? My feelings about Edinburgh Fringe are more based on the offline flyers and all these

[15:06] Spectator 13 (F): Personally, I don't feel it's necessary. I like the offline stuff. I like walking around and just like taking an Edinburgh (catalog) and seeing shows there and exploring... I just don't know personally about what you could tell me more if there was a QR code that I scan. I'm already sort of already interested around that.

[15:59] The author: It's still based on the content.

[16:00] Spectator 13 (F): Yeah. I think maybe it would work. But personally, it's not something that I would be super interested in. I wouldn't really bother. I wouldn't like scan anything. You know, it's like it's too much hassle sometimes to like, go there and

then go into my phone and do they're like, I don't know, just for me not, but maybe for other people it works.

BE-1. Artist 1

[00:33] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:39] Artist 1: For myself, I tend not to, but for the company, everyone's pushing me to have to.

[00:45] The author: From everyone? You mean like from company and venue?

[00:47] Artist 1: For example, the venues Oxford playhouse, the rest of the team, everyone's saying that social media is really important for getting younger audiences and wider audiences.

[00:57] The author: Do you personally use the social media?

[01:01] Artist 1: Not really, I'd much rather speak to people or contact friends rather than some virtual somebody, somewhere.

[01:07] The author: DO you have your own Facebook or Twitter account now?

[01:12] Artist 1: I don't have my own personal (account). But I have the company one. So to sell the show to the public. But for my own personal, it's not something that I like, really... because it seems faceless and it seems to take up time. Sorry, I'm not a social media fan. It takes time and energy, and you miss life I think if you're just looking at your phone. I'm sorry. The company has one. And lots of other people are working on it. Which aren't me. Thank God! (laugh.)

[01:48] The author: Did someone help you do all the social media stuff?

[01:53] Artist 1: Yes. Because they keep trying to tell me, but I don't give that time, to give that energy to take away from real interactions.

[02:05] The author: Do you use social media to prepare for your coming to Edinburgh this time?

[02:13] Artist 1: Some people have been trying to say yes, that was lots of... “We're going to this,” “Come to see us here,” and “If you're Edinburgh at this time, our shows are around on this, that and the other.” So it was used in a way to prepare, but it's been used daily as we've gone as we open here.

[02:26] The author: So mostly is to promote the show. Is there any other use of social media here?

[02:37] Artist 1: To me, not really, if I'm talking about me personally, for the company is probably lots of other things. There's also things about finding out what other people are doing and similar type shows. But I would probably go on recommendations or looking them up, as opposed to Twitter or Facebook or Instagram or whatever.

[02:56] The author: Do you think the social media of Edinburgh Fringe is useful for an artist?

[03:02] Artist 1: Yeah, I think it is. I think it is for trying to find out what's happening. And it seems that I haven't been following but lots of people on my team are saying that we've got reviewers coming in, and that we need people to come and support our shows. And so it seems to be able to galvanize audiences in some ways when you need to, and it seems to a way of spreading ideas, but could be generational. It's just not my preferred.

[03:52] The author: Is there anything specific happened this year compared to the editions before?

[04:04] Artist 1: I heard people said that there aren't as many audiences, but I'm not sure, I've never done a full run before. So I've only ever come and done a week or two weeks. So this is our first time of doing a show for the whole weeks... I think I'd heard that maybe there's been a dip in audiences this year. And I don't know if that's true, because I've never done the full Fringe before. So definitely the first few weeks seem busier than this week (the third week) for example.

[04:35] The author: What kind of additional information that you will want more from the social media of Edinburg?

[04:49] Artist 1: I don't know, I don't think I have fully embraced it. Because I think there's some people who obviously use a lot.

[04:55] The author: But if you don't use social media to get all the information, what kind of channel you use?

[05:02] Artist 1: Word of mouth. I still like actually opening, touching something and reading it. So speaking people, yeah, I actually like going and seeing things and reading and looking where our reviews are because they not appear. But anyway. And yeah, maybe next year, I've changed, but it's not my favored use.

[05:21] The author: Do you think it's possible to integrate social media in the creation of art, that means we have a live show, but maybe we start much earlier with a small video, which truly integrates into the creation, or maybe the show might end much later the live show?

[05:47] Artist 1: Potentially, I've seen ones where they use texts or phone calls, or the audiences can change what happens. Sometimes you've got the film that's on the screen is something that's happening in the audience or at some part. I've seen it in that way. But maybe that's film rather than social media, because I think texts are still quite safe because you say what you're saying yeah, potentially... I think it probably really would work. There's generational because I'm close to being 50 that I've ever been so lots of the 20 and they love it but to me, I'm saying why. I love to see something I can touch.

BE-2. Artist 2 from Hull (UK)

[00:15] The author: Do you use social media in general?

[00:20] Artist 2: Yeah. A lot.

[00:22] The author: What kind of platforms specifically?

[00:24] Artist 2: Twitter, Instagram and Facebook are the main three.

[00:28] The author: Is there a bit different about the contents on Twitter and Facebook?

[00:31] Artist 2: Yeah, we find that professionals and other artists tend to use Twitter more, and elder people tend to use Facebook. So we kind of adjust accordingly.

[00:45] The author: Do young people use Twitter more?

[00:47] Artist 2: Yeah. Yeah.

[00:51] The author: Do you use social media to prepare for your coming to Edinburgh Fringe?

[00:58] Artist 2: Yes, we do a lot on social media before we got here to make sure that people knew that we were coming.

[01:07] The author: how long before your arrival had you do this?

[01:09] Artist 2: About three months before. We knew that we'll come in January. And since February, we've started being on social media and talking about it... I'm on all three, Facebook, Instagram and Twitter. Yeah.

[01:32] The author: What kind of audience do you have on Instagram?

[01:35] Artist 2: A really varied audience on Instagram, again, tends to be younger definitely. And again, just making everything very visual.

[01:49] The author: Didn't you use a lot YouTube?

[01:52] Artist 2: Never, never use Youtube from the very beginning because it takes a lot longer to create contents for YouTube. So things like Instagram are a lot easier to use.

[02:09] The author: Normal Instagram is for which kind of contents?

[02:12] Artist 2: It's mainly just photos that we use.

[02:15] The author: Didn't you post the video (in Instagram)?

[02:18] Artist 2: Not really. We found that we don't really get how many people watching the videos. So we decided not to do them.

[02:24] The author: Did you use the functions like "live" or "stories" on Instagram and Facebook?

[02:42] Artist 2: Yeah, so we only use them on Instagram. We don't really use on Facebook. And we've been doing the social media for other companies as well. As like, takeovers, to do it. And yeah, we use the stories, a lot of those things.

[03:33] The author: Do you think the social media of Edinburgh Fringe is useful for you?

[03:40] Artist 2: Very useful. So social media is a massive thing for us. Especially when you're getting reviews and audience comments, we can retweet those, we can post pictures of them when we got stars for my reviews things like that, we put that on photos of our show me, put those to Facebook, Instagram and Twitter. And we talked to other artists on it to see how we use it all.

[04:09] The author: Did the official social media accounts of Edinburgh Fringe post, for example, your interview made with a press?

[04:18] Artist 2: No, not at all, not at all. The official accounts of Edinburgh Fringe don't post anything like that. No. Not for us anyway... They tend to focus more on the festivals.

[04:38] The author: Does it mean that it's more about the practical information?

[04:40] Artist 2: Yeah, absolutely.

[04:45] The author: What kind of additional information you would like to get from the social media of Edinburgh Fringe, which might make it more useful or more attractive?

[05:04] Artist 2: I think the social media is already doing a very good side of it. It's really easy to access, it's really accessible, and it's really quick so a lot of people already love it. I don't know how we can really improve it to be honest. Because the artists themselves take control of their own artists and things. So when the Fringe post their things, that it's very formal — this is what's happening, this is what you can do, and it's more general and festival-related. Yeah. it's already really useful.

[05:46] The author: What kind of additional information might make the social media of Edinburgh Fringe much more attractive for artists, for producers and for the audiences in the future?

[06:02] Artist 2: I'll say definitely to have more visual things. Obviously when the Fringe is here, there are lots of posters and banners and things like that. Yeah. And for online, it isn't as visual. So if they have more photos of what's going on things like that, that would be really useful.

[06:20] The author: I realized that they (Fringe) didn't use so much in Instagram.

[06:25] Artist 2: Yeah, they don't, they really don't.

[06:27] The author: They (Fringe) use Twitter a lot.

[06:29] Artist 2: Yeah, they use Twitter a lot. Instagram is a really visual platform so it will be great that they could really use that but they don't really.

[06:39] The author: Do you think it's possible that one day, we have a live show, but actually, we start the show much earlier thanks to social media? The audiences may receive a small video (firstly), which is not teaser but truly part of the art creation. Do you think it's possible? What do you think about the potential or the threat?

[07:20] Artist 2: I think it would be really interesting to see how that affects particularly sales. And so people can get an idea of what the show is about, absolutely. I don't think it'd be that much of a threat, if people are excited by what they're seeing, then they're going to, want to pay and they want to see the show. Especially towards the very beginning, you don't really give away too much. So it's not an issue.

[07:58] The author: I did some interviews before, and I heard from one artist that he thinks it's risky. If part of his performance is made as a video, if he didn't make it good, it's done for his career. From some of the audiences, they claimed that they prefer to have the live show only from the beginning to the end.

[08:38] Artist 2: I can understand why they might think that. But I think if you know that your show is good, there should be no risk. I think that you actually get "a more useful audience". If they've kind of already seen a bit because they understand kind of the tone,

the content, the contexts and everything about it, rather than the people who just show up to see a show without knowing what the show is. They just bought a ticket, and they sat there for one and half hour. So I think it might create smaller audiences, but those audiences are much more engaged.

[09:23] The author: Is this the first time you come here?

[09:26] Artist 2: Yes.

BE-3. Artist 3

[00:07] The author: So the first question is, do you use social media in general as an artist?

[00:12] Artist 3: Yes, because we have to do it now because a lot of marketing is being relied on artists. So it's quite tiring. I've got Instagram, Facebook and Twitter.

[00:23] The author: And do you give different content on different platforms?

[0:27] Artist 3: Sometimes, yes, and depending on what it is. Sometimes I'll share on all three platforms the same thing, or sometimes I'll do it separately. It really depends. Sometimes I'll share something or retweet something. It really depends.

[00:43] The author: Do you use social media to prepare for you're coming to Edinburgh?

[0:48] Artist 3: This time we did. My colleague, another performer in the show, she actually set up a Cyster-Act Instagram account, but that was literally only two weeks before we came. So it was very last minute.

[01:02] The author: Did you (start to) do all the promotion two weeks before your coming?

[01:05] Artist 3: I've been doing promotion before that. But this particular Instagram account set up two weeks before. Yeah, so, we've been populating that every day with lots of stuff... Instagram, Facebook, and also a bit of tweeting, as well.

[01:23] The author: But not so much YouTube?

[01:27] Artist 3: Uh, no, no. Not so much. No.

[01:31] The author: Do you think official social media of Edinburgh Fringe is useful for you as an artist?

[01:42] Artist 3: I have no idea. I don't know what that's doing in terms of bringing in audiences. I really don't know. I can't really answer that. Yeah, we've done 4 shows so far. So I don't really know.

[01:58] The author: So they didn't do any promotion for your shows?

[02:00] Artist 3: They are not allowed to promote shows because they're just holding 4000 shows. That wouldn't be fair if they were promoting one over the other.

[02:13] The author: Is this the reason that all the information on its social media is quite practical?

[02:16] Artist 3: Yeah.

[02:30] The author: What kind of additional information Edinburgh Fringe could be provided to the audiences, which might be helpful for them to come to the show?

[02:52] Artist 3: Maybe company and cast critics might be quite useful. Okay. But there's just not enough space to have all of that because you need a lot to have a certain amount of words. So you can't actually put that much on. So I would say maybe just a bit more information about who's involved with the show, that kind of thing, yeah.

[03:12] The author: As you said, they are not allowed to do the promotion on the official accounts...

[03:18] Artist 3: I mean, they're allowed to put certain amount of words like 100 words.

[03:27] The author: Is it possible that one day, due to social media, we start the show right after, for example, the people have booked a ticket with a small video. After that, they have a live show. And maybe after the live show, they might receive another materials to give them another perspective of the show?

[04:07] Artist 3: I can sort of see that's working. But the important thing is a live experience. But yeah, I can sort of see that maybe people want have a little taster or another type of media like a song or, something to warm people up. Yeah,

[04:26] The author: Is this your first time to come to Edinburgh?

[04:29] Artist 3: With my own work, yes. I've been here before for other people's work. This is the first time I'm bringing something that I've made.

[04:37] The author: Do you see any change in this year's edition? Or is every year's edition quite standardized?

[04:46] Artist 3: I mean, I would say things are just much more expensive. I just think it's getting harder and harder to bring shows up. If you don't have production companies or marketing companies behind you. I think for people that are doing on their own, it's a lot harder.

CE-1. Professional 1 (Public Relations of a dance group)

作者: 貴團隊有使用社群媒體的習慣嗎?

Silver Yee (公關): 有。我們主要用三個: Facebook, Twitter 和 Instagram。我專注在劇團 Twitter 帳號的管理。我覺得 Twitter 比較官方, 發布的都是比較正式的訊息, 譬如說演出資訊或者宣傳片, 然後轉發評論, 或轉發觀眾的回饋。搭配的照片也都稍微正式了一點。Facebook 跟 Instagram 不是我在處理。Facebook 的訊息也都比較官方。愛丁堡藝穗節 Twitter 用得比較多, 所以我們在 Twitter 貼的資訊也更多。Facebook 也是一樣用途, 但資訊量較少些。這裡社群媒體的使用風氣主要是 Twitter, 人們不太從 Facebook 上看到資訊。Instagram 的內容則比較像是不正式的生活花絮, 像是照片或者限(時)動(態)。

作者: 貴團隊有使用社群媒體以準備藝穗節的部分嗎?

Silver Yee (公關): 有。主要是像我剛剛講得那些。如果是前期，那就是宣傳片與資訊，大概一兩個月前開始宣傳，約略從六月底開始。在更早之前也有，但發文時間間隔比較長，約略一周一次。

作者: 藝穗節的社群媒體策略是否有協助到演出宣傳的部分呢?

Silver Yee (公關): 我覺得他們有想要做，只因為團隊量太多，主辦方無法顧及所有團隊。那像藝穗節的社群媒體，我們可以標記他，但主辦方不會主動分享。... 我想，首要原因是因為團隊太多了，有四千餘組。再者也避免為特定團隊宣傳而引發爭議。但當然更確切的細節須問主辦方，場館方亦是如此。

作者: 您有沒有什麼建言能讓藝穗節的官方社群媒體帳號更實質幫助到貴劇團的節目推廣，或為觀眾帶來更多效益?

Silver Yee (公關): 這點我目前還沒有想到... 我想，如果能幫我們劇團轉發節目資訊，就已經很不錯了。

作者: 有沒有可能有天，藝術的創造不再僅限於現場表演。具體而言，當觀眾訂票後，他們就收到短片，其可望幫助觀眾更了解作品。它不是宣傳片，不是廣告，而是真切的，藝術創作中的一部分。或是欣賞完現場表演後，觀眾將收到短片，其可望幫他們擁有另一種看作品的視角(或詮釋)。

Silver Yee (公關): 我覺得有。現在的表演比較多都是現場互動，現場用媒體去互動。這次藝穗節有個演出，在演出的其中一個環節裡，觀眾可以用 whatsapp 向表演者提出任何有關性工作者的問題。

5.1.2. More photos which have social media potentials

